

Contributions to Robust and Efficient Methods for Analysis of High-Dimensional Data

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Dedication

I tread paths laid by giants, whose towering achievements guide me *philosophically and academically*.

Wir müssen wissen, wir werden wissen.

— *David Hilbert, 8 September 1930*

Gödel's incompleteness theorems [Gödel, 1931]

— *Kurt Gödel*

I dedicate this thesis to you, the reader, who will navigate through my approximately 200 pages of writing with statements that can be deeply traced back to ZFC; I also dedicate this to us, the people, living in the time post-sub $(n, n, 17)$.

Acknowledgements

This dissertation could not have been completed without the invaluable contributions and support from a host of dedicated individuals. I am immensely grateful for their assistance throughout this journey.

I extend my deepest appreciation to my supervisors, Celia M.T. Greenwood, Masoud Asgharian, Sahir Bhatnagar, for their invaluable guidance, persistent support, and expert advice throughout the course of this research. Special appreciation is due to Celia Greenwood for translating the English abstract into French, consistently providing timely and detailed feedback, and fulfilling the duties of a supervisor with exceptional dedication, even while facing significant health challenges. Additionally, Masoud Asgharian made substantial contributions to the discussion chapter by suggesting numerous avenues for future research, which have greatly enriched the scope and depth of this thesis, and offered a profound course in advanced nonparametric statistics that bridged theory with application together with a concise and invaluable reference summary of concepts in probability theory, contained within just a few pages. Their expertise and encouragement have been crucial to the success of this academic endeavor, and they have consistently offered prompt and profound insights throughout the research process.

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Preface

The work presented, including the introduction, literature review, bridging texts, discussion, and conclusion, was authored by myself, Kai Yang, and significantly enhanced under the diligent guidance and thorough revisions provided by my supervisors, Celia Greenwood and Masoud Asgharian.

The author contributions to each of the three manuscripts included in this thesis are as follows:

Manuscript 1:

- Kai Yang (student): Conceptualization (introduced mutual information estimation using FFT Kernel Density Estimation for variable screening); Formal analysis, Methodology, Investigation, and Software (carried out all mathematical proofs and developments, developed the screening method and Python package, designed and executed simulations and case studies); Visualization; Writing - Original Draft (wrote the initial draft); Writing - Review & Editing (revisions).
- Masoud Asgharian (supervisor): Conceptualization (proposed the Linfoot measure concept for variable screening); Investigation (collaborated on design and execution of simulations and case studies); Writing - Review & Editing (manuscript revisions); Supervision.
- Nikhil Baghwat: Data Curation (handled the preprocessing of the ABIDE data).
- Jean-Baptiste Poline: Resources (provided the ABIDE data).
- Celia Greenwood (supervisor): Investigation (assisted in designing simulations and case studies); Writing - Review & Editing (manuscript revisions); Resources (data provision); Supervision; Funding acquisition.

Manuscript 2:

- Kai Yang (student): Formal analysis, Methodology, and Investigation (carried out all mathematical proofs and developments; developed the theoretical part, designed and carried out simulation studies); Visualization; Conceptualization (proposed the accelerated gradient approach); Writing - Original Draft (composed the initial draft); Writing - Review & Editing (draft revisions).
- Masoud Asgharian (supervisor): Formal analysis, Methodology, and Investigation (contributed to the proof of Theorem 2 on $O(1/k)$ convergence by proposing to use HM-GM inequality approach, designed the simulation studies); Writing - Review & Editing (edited the manuscript); Supervision.
- Sahir Bhatnagar (supervisor): Conceptualization (proposed SCAD/MCP in the original problems to be solved); Investigation (designed the simulation studies); Writing - Review & Editing (edited the manuscript); Supervision.

Manuscript 3:

- Kai Yang (student): Formal analysis and Methodology (carried out all mathematical proofs and developments, developed the theoretical part, developed the optimization framework based on variational and nonsmooth analysis and the conjugate gradient method); Conceptualization (proposed to use the conjugate gradient method); Writing - Original Draft (wrote the initial draft); Writing - Review & Editing (subsequent revisions).
- Masoud Asgharian (supervisor): Conceptualization (proposed the use of Tsallis entropy and q Gaussian distribution for modeling); Writing - Review & Editing (reviewed and revised the manuscript); Supervision.
- Celia Greenwood (supervisor): Writing - Review & Editing (reviewed and revised the manuscript); Supervision; Funding acquisition.

This doctoral thesis presents original scholarship and distinct contributions to knowledge, specifically in the area of statistical computing and robust statistical methods for high-dimensional data analysis. The core contributions of this work, which advance knowledge within the field, are the development of new theories and methodologies, comprehensive simulation results, and data analyses. These contributions are thoroughly detailed in the chapters within.

Abstract

A ubiquitous feature of biological data of our era, such as brain functional magnetic resonance imaging or genetic data, is their extra-large sizes and dimensions. However, analyzing such high-dimensional biological data poses significant challenges, since the feature dimension is often much larger than the sample size. This thesis introduces robust and computationally efficient methods to address several common challenges associated with high-dimensional data.

In my first manuscript, I propose a coherent approach to variable screening that can accommodate nonlinear associations. I develop a novel variable screening method that transcends traditional linear assumptions by leveraging mutual information, with an intended application in neuroimaging data. This approach allows for a more accurate identification of important variables by capturing nonlinear as well as linear relationships between the outcome and the covariates. This strategy proves to be transformative in the analysis of neuroimaging data, as demonstrated through a detailed examination of the preprocessed Autism Brain Imaging Data Exchange dataset [[Cameron et al., 2013](#), [Barry et al., 2020](#)].

Then, building on this foundation, I develop new computing techniques for sparse estimation using nonconvex penalties in my second manuscript. These methods address notable challenges in current statistical computing practices, facilitating computationally efficient and robust analyses of complex datasets. While my study in the second manuscript is mainly motivated by computational challenges in sparse estimation using nonconvex penalties, the proposed method can be applied to a considerably general class of optimization problems.

In my third manuscript, I contribute to the development of robust modeling of high-dimensional correlated observations by relaxing some of the underlying assumptions for the analysis of such data. I develop a q Gaussian linear mixed-effects model, designed to surpass the constraints of conventional Gaussian linear mixed-effects models by accommo-

dating a broader class of distributions that are more robust toward outliers. For correlated observations, this q Gaussian model enhances the robustness and flexibility of statistical analyses, providing a more comprehensive tool for modeling the widely-correlated observations frequently encountered in biological and medical studies.

Collectively, these contributions aim at addressing the multifaceted challenges of high-dimensional biological data analysis and paving the way for deeper insights into complex biological systems by seamlessly integrating solutions to nonlinearity, nonconvex nonsmooth optimization, and the need for more robust and adaptable models.

ABRÉGÉ

Une caractéristique omniprésente des données biologiques de notre époque, telles que l'imagerie par résonance magnétique fonctionnelle du cerveau ou les données génétiques, est leur taille et leur dimension extra-larges. Cependant, l'analyse de ces données biologiques à haute dimension pose des défis importants, car la dimension des caractéristiques est souvent beaucoup plus grande que la taille de l'échantillon. Cette thèse introduit des méthodes robustes et efficaces pour répondre à plusieurs défis communs associés aux données de haute dimension.

Dans mon premier manuscrit, je propose une approche cohérente de la sélection des variables qui peut prendre en compte les associations non linéaires. Je développe une nouvelle méthode de sélection des variables qui transcende les hypothèses linéaires traditionnelles en utilisant le concept de l'information mutuelle. Cette approche permet une identification plus précise des variables importantes en capturant les relations non seulement linéaires mais aussi non linéaires entre le résultat et les covariables. Cette stratégie savère transformatrice dans l'analyse des données de neuro-imagerie, comme le montre mon analyse de données d'imagerie cérébrale sur l'autisme [[Cameron et al., 2013](#), [Barry et al., 2020](#)].

Ensuite, en m'appuyant sur cette base, je développe de nouvelles techniques de calcul pour la sélection de variables parcimonieuse en utilisant des pénalités non convexes dans mon deuxième manuscrit. Ces méthodes abordent des défis notables dans les pratiques actuelles de calcul statistique, facilitant des analyses efficaces et robustes d'ensembles de données complexes. Alors que mon étude dans le deuxième manuscrit est principalement motivée par les défis de calcul dans l'estimation parcimonieuse utilisant des pénalités non convexes, la méthode proposée peut être appliquée à une classe très générale de problèmes d'optimisation.

Dans mon troisième manuscrit, je contribue au développement d'une modélisation robuste d'observations corrélées en haute dimension, en assouplissant certaines des hypothèses sous-

jaçentes pour lanalyse de telles donnes. Je dveloppe un modle linaire mixte q Gaussien, conu pour dpasser les contraintes des modles linaires mixtes Gaussiens conventionnels. Ceci permet une adaptation à une classe plus large de distributions qui sont plus robustes vis-à-vis des valeurs aberrantes. Pour les observations corrles, ce modle q Gaussien est robuste et flexible , fournissant un outil plus complet pour modliser les observations largement corrles, qui sont frquemment rencontres dans les tudes biologiques et mdicales.

Collectivement, ces contributions visent à relever les dfis à multiples aspects de l'analyse des donnes biologiques à haute dimension, et à ouvrir la voie à une meilleure comprhension des systmes biologiques complexes en intgrant de manire transparente des solutions à la non-linarit, à l'optimisation non convexe et non lisse, et à la ncessit de modles plus robustes et adaptables.

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Abbreviations

*k*NN *k*-Nearest Neighbors

ABIDE Autism Brain Imaging Data Exchange

AG Accelerated Gradient

BSM Black–Scholes–Merton

CG Conjugate Gradient

CRLB Cramer–Rao Lower Bound

DFT Discrete Fourier Transform

FFT Fast Fourier Transform

FFTKDE Fast Fourier Transform-based Kernel Density Estimation

GMM Generalized Method of Moments

GMRES Generalized Minimal Residuals

GWAS Genome-Wide Association Studies

ICA Independent Component Analysis

KDE Kernel Density Estimation

KL divergence Kullback–Leibler divergence

LASSO Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator

MCP Minimax Concave Penalty

MRI Magnetic Resonance Images

NSADAQ National Association of Securities Dealers Automated Quotations

NYSE New York Stock Exchange

PCA Principal Components Analysis

SCAD Smoothly Clipped Absolute Deviation

SNR Signal-to-Noise Ratio

Chapter 1

Introduction

In the domain of biostatistics, the prevalence of high-dimensional biological data stands as a testament to the field's intricate relationship with complex datasets, notably within genetic research and brain neuroimaging. The breadth and complexity of these data landscapes emphasize the vital role of biostatistics in deciphering meaningful scientific insights from extra large high-dimensional datasets.

High-dimensional genetic data reflect a wealth of information about individual susceptibilities to diseases, physiological traits, and other critical biological attributes. This intricate dataset has been the foundation for numerous groundbreaking studies aimed at deciphering the molecular underpinnings of diseases, subsequently leading to innovative therapeutic approaches. Genome-Wide Association Studies (GWAS) have been instrumental in identifying genetic factors that contribute to the biology of diseases, thus paving the way for new therapeutic developments [Visscher et al., 2017]. Moreover, the interpretative analysis of statistical genetic models has enriched our understanding of heritability [Yang et al., 2017]. The application of genetic information to identify individuals at an elevated risk of specific diseases enhances disease screening strategies [Chatterjee et al., 2016], while genome analysis initiatives have refined diagnostic and screening processes for complex disorders, illustrat-

ing the capacity of genetic data to revolutionize healthcare practices [Khera et al., 2017, Pashayan et al., 2015]. Technology advances in the last decade have dramatically increased the volume and complexity of genetic datasets. For example, the UK Biobank project, with its extensive collection of genetic variants from approximately half a million individuals, embodies this evolution, presenting more than 800,000 attributes of unique genetic markers [Bycroft et al., 2018].

In parallel, neuroimaging data emerge as another example of high-dimensional biomedical datasets. The complexity and high dimension of neuroimaging data have catalyzed advances in variable selection techniques, as evidenced by a notable increase in related research publications: [Adeli et al., 2017, Fan and Chou, 2016, Febles et al., 2022, Gómez-Verdejo et al., 2019, Hao et al., 2020, He et al., 2018, Hunt et al., 2014, Ivanoska et al., 2021, Mohr et al., 2006, Martino et al., 2008, Pereda et al., 2018, Roy, 2021, Schlögl et al., 2002, Sofer et al., 2014, Suresh et al., 2022]. Acquisition of magnetic resonance images (MRI) produces data on an unprecedented scale, capturing measurements in millions of voxels [Bell and Drew, 2018, Liang et al., 2022, Linn et al., 2016, Fan and Chou, 2016]. The advent of multiple imaging modalities has introduced multiple sets of high-dimensional features, each providing different insights into brain function and exhibiting complex correlation patterns. This multiplicity of data accentuates the critical need for sophisticated analytical techniques capable of managing and interpreting the intricate details captured within and across these modalities.

The analysis of large high-dimensional biological datasets, common in fields such as genomics and neuroimaging, presents ultimate challenges in statistical computing. Often, these datasets are so voluminous that they exceed available memory capacity, necessitating strategies for dimension reduction to perform statistical analysis on the data. In this context, feature selection emerges as a crucial technique. Unlike other dimension reduction methods such as Principal Components Analysis (PCA) and Independent Component Analysis

(ICA), univariate variable screening stands out for its computational efficiency. Additionally, univariate variable screening adapts to limited memory resources, as it processes only the outcome and a single covariate at each iteration, making it especially suitable for analyzing extensive datasets. Moreover, it offers the advantage of straightforward interpretability; the variables selected through this process directly correspond to features of interest, providing clear insights without the obfuscation that can accompany other dimensionality reduction techniques.

Another critical benefit of univariate variable screening is its compatibility with parallel computing frameworks. This adaptability allows the simultaneous processing of data segments, significantly speeding up the variable screening step of high-dimensional large datasets that are typical in genetic research and neuroimaging studies. Such computational efficiency is crucial in these fields, where rapid and effective interpretation of data can lead to significant scientific advancements.

Furthermore, when comparing univariate screening with multivariable selection methods, univariate approaches maintain consistency in variable selection. This consistency stems from the fact that the calculated measure of the association between each covariate and the outcome is independent of the influence of other covariates. This feature ensures that the introduction of additional covariates into the analysis does not necessitate a re-evaluation of existing associations, a requirement that multivariable approaches cannot circumvent. In scenarios where new covariates are added to the dataset, univariate screening only requires the calculation of associations with the outcome for these new covariates, whereas multivariable dimension reduction or variable selection methods would need to reassess the entire dataset, including both established and newly incorporated covariates. This distinction underscores the practicality and computational efficiency of univariate variable screening in the dynamic environment of high-dimensional data analysis, making it an invaluable tool for researchers navigating the complexities of genetic studies and neuroimaging data.

Hence, in my first manuscript, I introduce a coherent approach to univariate variable screening that is robust to nonlinear associations. The variable screening methods in my first manuscript are incorporated in a Python package `fastHDMI`, which stands for *Fast Mutual Information Estimation for high-dimensional Data*. This innovative tool consists of three mutual information estimation techniques for variable selection within neuroimaging analyses. Using extensive simulation studies based on the preprocessed *Autism Brain Imaging Data Exchange (ABIDE) dataset* [Cameron et al., 2013, Barry et al., 2020], my screening methods are evaluated under various conditions, highlighting the superiority of mutual information estimation through *Fast Fourier Transform-based Kernel Density Estimation (FFTKDE)* for variable screening when the continuous outcome is nonlinearly associated with the covariates, as well as the advantage of variable screening using mutual information estimation by binning continuous variables when the binary outcome is nonlinearly associated with the covariates. Furthermore, based on case studies to predict the continuous outcome age and the binary outcome autism diagnosis, my research showcases the package’s capability in variable screening by comparing the performance of various predictive models built using the selected variables from screening, demonstrating `fastHDMI`’s significant contribution to enhancing neuroimaging data analysis and expanding the repertoire of variable screening tools for researchers when it comes to high-dimensional data prevalent in biomedical studies.

Building upon the foundational work presented in my first manuscript, my second manuscript ventures into the realm of developing new statistical computing techniques for sparse estimation, specifically addressing the challenges posed by nonconvex penalties. These innovative methods tackle significant obstacles encountered in current statistical computing paradigms, enhancing the computational efficiency of analyzing high-dimensional large datasets. Central to this exploration is the adaptation of Nesterov’s Accelerated Gradient (AG) method [Nesterov, 1983, 2004a] to nonconvex nonsmooth settings — a notable departure from its conventional application to convex nonsmooth penalties such as ℓ_1 penalty [Tibshirani, 1996] or the

elastic net penalty [Zou and Hastie, 2005]. This adaptation is particularly crucial given the convergence challenges associated with nonconvex penalties such as Smoothly Clipped Absolute Deviation (SCAD) [Fan and Li, 2001] and Minimax Concave Penalty (MCP) [Zhang, 2010]. This adaptation is established upon the methodologies outlined in [Ghadimi and Lan, 2015], setting a foundation for the algorithmic analysis and development presented in this manuscript.

My second manuscript details a sophisticated algorithm focused on the selection of critical optimization hyperparameters, pivotal for its practical implementation. It delves into the intricacies of selecting these hyperparameters, proposing a strategy based on complexity upper bounds to accelerate convergence, thereby making a significant contribution to sparse learning in a high-dimensional context. Furthermore, by establishing the rate of convergence and presenting a novel bound to describe the optimal damping sequence, this work not only underscores the algorithm's theoretical underpinnings but also demonstrates its superior performance over existing methods through comprehensive simulation studies by nonconvex penalized linear and logistic models. This manuscript, while primarily motivated by computational challenges in sparse estimation with nonconvex penalties, ultimately presents a methodology with broad applicability across a diverse spectrum of optimization problems, marking a significant step forward in the field of statistical computing. This manuscript has now been recognized and disseminated through its publication in the journal *Statistics and Computing*, an achievement that highlights its contribution to the field [Yang et al., 2024].

Biostatistical datasets often feature correlated observations, a notable example being genetic data, which inherently embodies structured correlation between observations [Bycroft et al., 2018]. Neglecting population structure often leads to a considerable lack of fit: previous research demonstrates that the predictions obtained by the expectations of linear models do not predict as accurately as the maximum a posteriori (MAP) predictions obtained by linear

mixed models (LMM), with the latter incorporating population structure [Bhatnagar et al., 2019]. The population structure can also be a confounder for the phenotype and the genetic data; hence, it might cause spurious correlations discovered if not accounted for. Specific to variable selection, not accounting for population structure might cause some population-related variables falsely selected when they are not, in fact, related to the phenotype — in this view, it might even cause true variables not selected. The motivation behind my third manuscript is driven by the need to address this issue, proposing a linear mixed-effects model based on the idea of Tsallis entropy maximization. This method effectively handles the correlation among observations, while also incorporating variable selection for fixed-effects covariates, utilizing sparse penalties that function as regularizers when the dimensionality of the design matrix surpasses the number of observations.

The developed q Gaussian linear mixed effects model marks a significant advance in statistical sparse learning, providing an approach to analyze high-dimensional and correlated observations robust to outliers and the underlying distributional assumption. This innovation addresses the limitations inherent in traditional Gaussian distribution assumptions that have historically constrained statistical analysis. Based on the principle of maximizing Tsallis entropy, the q Gaussian model excels in navigating the complexities of biostatistical data, characterized by correlated observations and heterogeneity of variances, a scenario frequently encountered in genetic and longitudinal data.

In my third manuscript, I re-derive the multivariate probability density function from Tsallis entropy maximization. This allows for statistical modeling using the likelihood-ist approach, overcoming the constraints imposed by conventional Gaussian assumptions, which often fall short in robustness towards outliers and the accurate representation of underlying distributional shapes. Furthermore, I introduce a novel framework that leverages numerous numerical methods originally designed to find equilibria in flows, thus addressing the composite optimization problems characteristic of statistical sparse learning. The framework is further

applied to the state-of-the-art Hager-Zhang conjugate gradient algorithm [[Hager and Zhang, 2005](#)], which yields a numerically stable and computationally efficient algorithm for sparse statistical learning.

In essence, through the development of robust and computationally efficient methods, this thesis enhances the ability to model and predict using large high-dimensional datasets frequently encountered in biostatistics, such as in neuroimaging and genetics. The groundwork laid by this research promises to propel forward in statistical computing and robust modeling, setting the stage for future investigations that delve deeper into rich, uncharted territories of biomedical data.

Chapter 2

Literature review

In this section, a summary of pertinent literature related to the thesis is provided. For an in-depth exploration of the literature, please consult the literature review sections within each of the three manuscripts included in this thesis. A motivating factor for the research presented in this dissertation stems from the challenge posed by high-dimensional datasets, where the number of features often surpasses the number of observations. This results in a row rank deficiency in the design matrix \mathbf{X} , leading to the null space $\text{null}(\mathbf{X}) \neq \emptyset$. The foundation of many statistical learning methods is the linear predictor $\mathbf{X}\boldsymbol{\beta}$, with the estimation of $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ parameters typically achieved through the minimization of an objective function. Such functions include least-square loss, robust objective functions such as Huber loss function, (negative) log-likelihood, (negative) partial log-likelihood, and the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM), among others. The existence of a nonempty null space indicates that the solutions to these minimization problems with respect to $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ are not uniquely defined, rendering the problem ill-posed. To address this, regularization via a strongly convex function, dimension reduction, or variable selection can be employed. For dimension reduction methods such as PCA, ICA, and autoencoders [Hinton and Salakhutdinov, 2006], as discussed in the Introduction chapter, these methods exhibit certain limitations compared to variable

selection. As elucidated previously in the text, variable selection through the application of penalties can function as localized regularization effects under certain conditions.

2.1 Mutual Information

Mutual information is defined as the Kullback–Leibler divergence between the joint distribution of two variables and their outer product distribution, as described in (2.1).

$$I(X, Y) := \mathbb{E}_{[X, Y]^T} \left[-\log \frac{p(X \otimes Y)}{p([X, Y]^T)} \right] \quad (2.1)$$

This concept can quantify dependencies without assuming a linear relationship between variables, in contrast to conventional methods like Pearson’s correlation, as shown in (2.2) for vector x, y being the realizations drawn from the random variables X, Y , which assumes linearity and does not perform well when there are nonlinear associations.

$$r(x, y) := \left\langle \frac{x}{\|x\|_2}, \frac{y}{\|y\|_2} \right\rangle \quad (2.2)$$

In comparison, mutual information-based variable screening approaches are robust towards nonlinear associations. Previous research has introduced some methods to evaluate the association between outcome and covariates [Rényi, 1959, Reshef et al., 2011, Speed, 2011], where the measures of association detailed in these studies are all monotonically increasing functions of mutual information. Hence, variable screening using any of these association measures yield identical results to variable screening using mutual information.

In the domain of neuroimaging data analysis, mutual information has been extensively employed, demonstrating its versatility and efficacy in deciphering the intricacies of neural datasets. Noteworthy applications include the use of Gaussian copula for mutual information estimation in continuous datasets [Ince et al., 2016, Magri et al., 2009], the application

of mutual information in fMRI data analysis [Nemirovsky et al., 2023, Tsai et al., 1999], and the exploration of EEG-based brain-computer interfaces through mutual information [Schlögl et al., 2002]. Despite its widespread application, there remains a gap in neuroimaging research with respect to the use of mutual information for feature screening when the variables are continuous, primarily due to the challenges associated with estimating mutual information for continuous variables.

Estimating mutual information for discrete variables is straightforward; however, estimating mutual information for continuous variables involves a variety of methodologies. Previous studies have considered techniques such as the binning of continuous variables to transform them into discrete variables [Ross, 2014], kernel density estimation (KDE) [Steuer et al., 2002, Moon et al., 1995, Khan et al., 2007, Gao et al., 2015], and k -nearest-neighbor estimation (k NN) [Faivishevsky and Goldberger, 2008, Kraskov et al., 2004, Victor, 2002, Pál et al., 2010, Lord et al., 2018, Gao et al., 2015] strategies. KDE-based methods, in particular, have shown superior performance in mutual information estimation, especially in settings with small sample sizes and high noise levels [Steuer et al., 2002, Moon et al., 1995, Khan et al., 2007, Gao et al., 2015]. For binning estimation of mutual information, choosing the number of bins is critical. Previous literature [Birgé and Rozenholc, 2006] suggests an approach to find the optimal number of bins based on Castellán’s bounds on risk of penalized maximum likelihood estimators [Castellán, 2000], which therefore enables a data-driven number of bins for the estimation of mutual information. Furthermore, for a detailed description of mutual information estimation using the *Fast Fourier Transform based Kernel Density Estimation (FFTKDE)* or k -nearest-neighbor (k NN), please refer to Appendix A.1 of my first manuscript.

2.2 ℓ_1 -induced Sparse Learning

Sparse learning, also called variable selection, has always been a major approach in multi-variable statistical analysis of high-dimensional data. This approach assumes that only a small number of predictors are relevant to the outcome. The resulting statistical models usually perform better in terms of predictive accuracy and possibly also interpretability. For these reasons, sparse learning has received much attention in the statistical literature over the past two decades (for example, [Tibshirani, 1996, Zou and Hastie, 2005, Bühlmann et al., 2014]). Sparse learning is commonly accomplished by adding sparse penalties to the objective function, either in the main problem or the subproblems, to produce sparsity in the estimation of coefficients. Let ℓ_p denote the sequential space endowed by the sequential norm $\|x\|_p := \left(\sum_{j \in \mathbb{N}_{>0}} |x_j|^p\right)^{\frac{1}{p}}$. In a context of sparse learning, the ℓ_p penalty refers to the penalty term being $\|\cdot\|_p$ multiplied by a positive penalty hyperparameter λ to control the level of penalization. Specifically, ℓ_1 is usually used to achieve sparsity, as Lagrangian duality reveals a geometric interpretation that the solution of ℓ_1 penalized problems will be on the boundary of the ℓ_1 ball of some radius. for any smooth¹ function $f(\beta')$ with L -Lipschitz continuous gradients, when penalized by the convex nonsmooth ℓ_1 penalty, the resulting estimator, denoted by $\hat{\beta}'$, will need to satisfy the first-order (necessary) optimality condition for the objective function $f(\beta') + \lambda \|\beta'\|_1$:

$$-\nabla_{\beta'} f(\hat{\beta}') \in \frac{\partial}{\partial \beta'} (\lambda \|\beta'\|_1) (\hat{\beta}') \quad (2.3)$$

where $\lambda > 0$ controls the amount of penalization and $\frac{\partial}{\partial \beta'} (\lambda \|\beta'\|_1)$ denotes the subgradient set operator for the nonsmooth convex function $\lambda \|\beta'\|_1$. Let $\tilde{\beta}'$ denote the estimator obtained by minimizing $f(\beta')$ itself, we have that $\tilde{\beta}'$ satisfies

$$\nabla_{\beta'} f(\tilde{\beta}') = 0 = -\nabla_{\beta'} f(\tilde{\beta}') \quad (2.4)$$

¹In this thesis, smooth denotes *first-order* continuous differentiable unless otherwise specified

For each coordinate β'_i , if the partial derivative satisfies $\left| \frac{\partial}{\partial \beta'_i} f(0) \right| \leq \lambda$, we'll have $\hat{\beta}'_i = 0$ [Tibshirani et al., 2011]. By Lipschitz continuity of the gradients, a sufficient condition for $\hat{\beta}'_i = 0$ is:

$$\left| \tilde{\beta}'_i \right| \leq \frac{\lambda}{L}$$

In view of (2.4), as an interpretation, should a coefficient be close to 0, the ℓ_1 sparse penalty will set the coefficient estimator zero. The mechanism above to induce the sparsity of ℓ_1 penalization is, in fact, used in almost all sparse penalties for statistical learning, which makes the objective function nonsmooth. Furthermore, Nikolova [2000] suggested that to achieve sparsity by optimizing a penalized problem, the first derivative of the objective function must be discontinuous. In a statistical context, this implies the nonsmoothness of the sparse penalty.

2.3 Penalties with Oracle Property

Oracle property, originally proposed by Fan and Li, is a useful property of statistical estimators for sparse learning [Fan and Li, 2001]: as an interpretation, the oracle property demonstrates that the asymptotic distribution of the estimator yielded by penalized loss function is the same as the asymptotic distribution of the unpenalized estimator based on the loss function fitted only on the true support. In view of (2.3), the estimator yielded by the ℓ_1 penalty, $\hat{\beta}'$, will be biased even when β_i is in the true support — this implies that when applied to statistical learning problems, the penalty ℓ_1 cannot yield oracle estimators.

The vast majority of penalties used for sparse learning consist of ℓ_1 as one of its components to induce sparsity. On the other hand, to satisfy the oracle property, a necessary condition is that the estimator yielded by penalized MLE is unbiased for large β_i [Nikolova, 2000]. That is, for a sparse penalty $p(\boldsymbol{\beta}_{-0}) := \lambda \|\boldsymbol{\beta}_{-0}\|_1 + q(\boldsymbol{\beta}_{-0})$, we need to have [Nikolova, 2000]

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \beta_i} p(\boldsymbol{\beta}_{-0}) = \lambda \cdot \text{sgn}(\beta_i) + \frac{\partial}{\partial \beta_i} q(\boldsymbol{\beta}_{-0}) = 0 \text{ as } |\beta_i| \rightarrow \infty$$

This suggests that data-independent sparse penalties with oracle property must be nonconvex. Two famous penalties, *smoothly clipped absolute deviation (SCAD)* [Fan and Li, 2001] and *minimax concave penalty (MCP)* [Zhang et al., 2010], have been shown to possess oracle properties under certain conditions.

Based on the above discussion, for a data-independent sparse penalty to possess oracle property, the penalty must be nonsmooth and nonconvex. As a result, computation for the penalized MLE must accommodate for this deduced nonconvexity and nonsmoothness.

2.4 Past Approaches to Solve Nonconvex Nonsmooth Penalties

In this paragraph, we summarize the past approaches of computation methods proposed for SCAD/MCP and other nonconvex nonsmooth penalties; that is, problem (2.5), where $p_{\lambda,\gamma}$ is the penalty function depending on penalty hyper-parameters λ, γ , f is the unpenalized loss function – the intercept coefficient, β_0 , is not penalized.

$$\min_{\boldsymbol{\beta} \in \mathbb{R}^{q+1}} f(\boldsymbol{\beta}) + \sum_{j=1}^q p_{\lambda,\gamma}(\beta_j) \quad (2.5)$$

Zou and Li proposed to perform a local linear approximation, which yields a descent majorization-minimization (MM) algorithm [Zou and Li, 2008]. Breheny and Huang proposed to use the coordinate descent method to carry out the estimation for linear models with least-square loss or logistic regression, penalized by SCAD and MCP [Breheny and Huang, 2011]. Mazumder et al. implemented in an R package, `sparsenet`, which carries out root-finding process in a coordinate manner [Mazumder et al., 2011]. Kim et al. discussed difference of convex programming (DCP) method for OLS estimators penalized by SCAD penalty [Kim et al., 2008], which was later generalized by Wang et al. to a class of nonconvex penalties [Wang

et al., 2013]. Lee et al. developed a modified second-order method originally designed for the loss function of Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator (LASSO) with extension to SCAD and MCP [Lee et al., 2016], this attempt was later extended to generalized linear models such as logistic or Poisson, and Cox’s proportional hazard model [Kim et al., 2018]. There are also a few other attempts to apply the quasi-Newton method or a mixture of first and second order descent method on the objective function with nonconvex penalties [Ibrahim et al., 2012, Ghosh and Thoresen, 2016]. Rigorous proof of global convergence and the rate of convergence have rarely been established for these approaches; rather, most of them illustrated their convergence properties using simulated studies. Furthermore, for high-dimensional problems, second-order methods suffer from computational inefficiency when accounting for the computational cost in the evaluation of the secant condition. The first-order methods proposed above are prone to the behavior of “zigzagging” when the problem is ill-conditioned [Watt, 2020]. For a smooth ill-conditioned problem, in view of a local quadratic approximation, the search direction experiences oscillations along the direction of eigenvectors corresponding to a greater absolute eigenvalue while moving very slowly towards the direction of eigenvectors corresponding to a less absolute eigenvalue, resulting in steps that “zigzag,” thus converges in a much slower speed numerically. To address this issue of “zigzagging,” accelerated gradient methods have been initially developed for smooth objective functions [Polyak, 1964, Nesterov, 1983], subsequently extended to nonsmooth convex problems [Nesterov, 2004b], and more recently adapted to nonconvex and nonsmooth problems [Ghadimi and Lan, 2015].

2.5 q Gaussian Distribution

The vast majority of distributions used in biostatistics can be considered as derived by maximizing Shannon’s entropy under certain constraints [Cover and Thomas, 2006]. Specifically, the Gaussian distribution can be derived by maximizing Shannon’s entropy with first-

moment and second central-moment constraints. The Gaussian distribution is widely used in statistical machine learning, but suffers from several disadvantages, notably its exponential tail decay and lack of a shape parameter, which compromise robustness towards outliers and limits distribution shape representation. The q Gaussian distribution is derived from the maximization of the Tsallis entropy, and is a generalization of bell-curve distributions. Therefore, it emerges as a robust alternative capable of accurately modeling the diverse shapes of bell curve distributions and accounting for heavy-tailed characteristics, with wide usage, such as in modeling financial return data [Borland, 2002a,0, Domingo et al., 2017]. Despite its proven advantages in finance, the q Gaussian distribution’s application within biostatistics and statistical sparse learning is limited.

2.6 Existing Algorithms for Optimizing Sparse Learning Problems for Linear Mixed-effects Models

When it comes to variable selection of the fixed-effects covariates in a context of linear mixed-effects models, there have been multiple approaches related to penalized LMMs computation. Most of these previous approaches were based on convex penalties, including LASSO [Tibshirani, 1996], Adaptive LASSO, or elastic net [Zou and Hastie, 2005] (for which the penalty is a linear combination of ℓ_1 and ℓ_2 norms of fixed effects coefficients). Xiong and Shang performed coordinate descent for adaptive LASSO [Xiong and Shang, 2019], Schelldorfer built the R package `lmmLASSO` for LASSO/adaptive LASSO based on proximal quasi-Newton method with Armijo rule [Schelldorfer, 2011], Wang et al. chose to use proximal gradient descent method for sparse penalties [Wang et al., 2018]. Pan and Shang used proximal Newton-Ralphson method for adaptive LASSO [Pan and Shang, 2018]. However, convex methods might not retain global convergence when applied to nonconvex problems.

Proximal methods emerge as pivotal strategies for their effectiveness in handling sparse-induced nonsmooth optimization problems. These methods achieve superior numerical per-

formance over alternative nonsmooth optimization methods (see, for example, [Yu and Peng, 2017, Li et al., 2016]).

One of the most basic proximal methods, the proximal gradient methods, is formulated as

$$\min_x g(x) + h(x),$$

where g is a globally smooth function and h is a convex, possibly nonsmooth function. At each iteration k , the method updates the variable x according to the equation:

$$x^{(k+1)} = \text{prox}_{\alpha^{(k)}h}(x^{(k)} - \alpha^{(k)}\nabla g(x^{(k)})),$$

where $\alpha^{(k)}$ is the step size and $\text{prox}_{\alpha^{(k)}g}$ is the proximal operator of g parameterized by $\alpha^{(k)}$. For a more detailed review of variational and nonsmooth analysis and proximal operators, please refer to Section 5.4.1 of the third manuscript. Simultaneously, various numerical algorithms are examined and utilized in the context of dynamic systems, particularly to find the equilibria of flows. Please refer to Section 2.8 for a brief introduction of dynamical systems. Such capabilities are extensively documented in various scholarly resources on numerical analysis [Quarteroni et al., 2007, Atkinson, 1989, Lubich et al., 2006, Hubbard and West, 1995, Helmke, 1994, Ross, 2019, Riahi and Qattan, 2018]. In my third manuscript, I develop a method to transform the vast majority of numerical methods to find equilibria of flows to a optimization algorithm for nonconvex composite problems with the smooth component being globally Lipschitz-smooth. Moreover, the global convergence of such numerical method is preserved under this transformation.

At the same time, Krylov subspace methods are recognized as the foundational pillars in numerical analysis, providing computationally efficient solutions for large-scale optimization problems [Saad, 2003], with excellent convergence acceleration and enhanced numerical stability. The Krylov subspace methods aim to solve the linear system $Ax = b$, which involve

constructing a sequence of subspaces, known as Krylov subspaces, which are defined as:

$$\mathcal{K}_r(A, b) = \text{span}\{b, Ab, A^2b, \dots, A^r b\},$$

where r is the order of the Krylov subspace; K_r is known as an order- r Krylov subspace. For a detailed explanation of Krylov subspace methods, please refer to Section 2.7. These methods solve linear system $Ax = b$ by iteratively improving an estimate of the solution or eigenvalue/eigenvector, leveraging the properties of the Krylov subspace to minimize computational effort while increasing the accuracy of the solution with each iteration.

The nonlinear conjugate gradient methods, which were developed based on the conjugate gradient method, are highlighted for their excellence in smooth optimization. This is attributed to its computational and memory efficiency, scalability, and numerical stability, making it a method of choice in the optimization landscape. Numerous previous literature has proposed various conjugate gradient methods; among these, the Hager-Zhang conjugate gradient method [Hager and Zhang, 2005], when applied to a globally smooth problem, not necessarily convex, achieves global convergence and has shown good numerical results [Hager and Zhang, 2006]. Building on this algorithm, I applied the framework mentioned above to Hager-Zhang conjugate gradient method, which can achieve fast and numerically stable results for composite optimization problems very often encountered in a sparse learning/variable selection context.

2.7 Krylov Subspace Methods

This section provides an overview of Krylov subspace methods, which aids in comprehending the nonlinear conjugate gradient method discussed in Manuscript 3. A substantial portion of the content presented in this section is based on the notes taken during my numerical analysis course, wherein [Trefethen and Bau, 2022] served as one of the primary references.

Arnoldi Iteration The Krylov subspace methods are best understood based on the idea of projecting onto Krylov subspaces. Given matrix $A \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$ and vector b , *Krylov sequence* refers to the set of vectors b, Ab, A^2b, \dots , and the corresponding *Krylov subspaces* of order r is then defined as the space spanned by the first r terms of Krylov sequence. *Arnoldi iteration* then can be interpreted as performing (modified) Gram-Schmidt on the Krylov matrix

$$\mathcal{K}_n := \begin{bmatrix} b & Ab & A^2b & \dots & A^{n-1}b \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$$

to construct its orthonormal basis. A matrix is in Hessenberg form if it is "almost" triangular: all elements below the first sub-diagonal are zero. In view of A itself, Arnoldi iteration can be considered as an Hessenberg-ized method analogous to Gram-Schmidt, see Table 2.1 – one similarity is, they both can stop at any iteration with a sequence of triangular/Hessenberg factors and a partial orthogonalized factor $Q^{(k)}$, therefore serves as a better iterative method. *Householder's reflector* is a method to numerically compute QR-decomposition. Different from how gives rotations method *rotates* the vector to zeroing an entry, Householder's method will *reflect* the vector by a hyperplane H such that the reflection can point to the desired direction – reflecting one column vector of A at a time. For example, for the first column vector of A , $a_1 \in \mathbb{R}^n$, we try to reflect a_1 to the direction of e_1 by left-multiplying an orthogonal matrix Q_1 such that $Q_1 a_1 = \|a_1\| e_1$, where e_1 denotes the vector with the first entry being 1 and the rest of entries being 0 per usual; the hyperplane H is set orthogonal to $v := \|a_1\| e_1 - a_1$, therefore the orthogonal matrix can be constructed by

$$Q_1 := I - 2 \frac{vv^T}{v^T v}$$

where Q_1 is orthogonal.

Table 2.1: Householder’s reflection vs Gram-Schmidt/Arnoldi process

	QR factorization $A = QR$	Hessenberg formation $A = QHQ^*$
Householder’s reflection	Orthogonal triangularization	Orthogonal Hessenberg formation
Gram-Schmidt/Arnoldi process	Triangular orthogonalization	Hessenbergized orthogonalization

For iterative methods we consider m to be large or infinite, so we only consider the first n columns of $AQ = QH$. Let $Q_n \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$ denote the first n columns of Q ; and let $\tilde{H}_n \in \mathbb{R}^{(n+1) \times n}$ be the submatrix located at the upper-left corner of H , which will also be a Hessenberg matrix itself. Then we’ll have $AQ_n = Q_{n+1}\tilde{H}_n$ as the first n columns of $AQ = QH$. And equating the n th column of both sides gives us $Aq_n = h_{1n}q_1 + \dots + h_{nn}q_n + h_{n+1,n}q_{n+1}$, which is a recurrence relation for q_{n+1} – Arnoldi iteration follows directly on this recurrence relation: let $q_1 = \frac{b}{\|b\|}$ be the initializer, and choose h_{kn} such that $h_{kn}q_k$ is a projection of q_k on Aq_n for $k = 1, 2, \dots, n$; as an interpretation, the updating step first subtracts the projections of the built orthogonal bases from Aq_n , then normalizing the remainder with $h_{n+1,n}$ to ensure $\|q_{n+1}\| = 1$. Because the recurrence formula states that each q_n is formed by a linear combination of Aq_{n-1} and q_1, q_2, \dots, q_{n-2} , each q_n is therefore a degree- $(n - 1)$ polynomial of A times b ; hence q_1, q_2, \dots, q_n form an orthonormal basis for the Krylov subspace

$$\mathcal{K}_n := \langle b, Ab, \dots, A^{n-1}b \rangle$$

(i). In this view, Arnoldi process can be considered as systematic construction of orthonormal bases for successive Krylov subspaces $\mathcal{K}_1, \mathcal{K}_2, \mathcal{K}_3, \dots$. Because Arnoldi iteration constructs orthonormal basis in a Gram-Schmidt manner, the Q_n here will be exactly the same as the Q_n present in the Gram-Schmidt QR factorization of K_n , while here K_n and R per se are never explicitly constructed. And it is called *modified* Gram-Schmidt because at iteration k , we subtract projections of constructed bases q_1, q_2, \dots, q_k from the vector Aq_k instead of the “original” vector $A^k b$.

(ii). Another view of Arnoldi process is a computation of projections onto successive Krylov subspaces. Note that $Q_n^* Q_{n+1}$ is a $n \times (n+1)$ matrix with 1 on the diagonal and 0 elsewhere; then from $AQ_n = Q_{n+1} \tilde{H}_n$ we have

$$\underbrace{Q_n^* Q_{n+1} \tilde{H}_n}_{=: H_n} = Q_n^* A Q_n.$$

Apparently, H_n here will be the $n \times n$ submatrix located at the upper-left corner of H . This is an analogue to change of basis, with Q_n not orthogonal but of shape $m \times n$ – and the resulting interpretation is: given some $v \in \mathcal{K}_n$, applying A to it, then orthogonally project Av back to \mathcal{K}_n .

Note that here H_n and A are *pseudo*-similar. Intuitively, one might then consider the eigenvalues of H_n as estimates for the eigenvalues of A – for this reason, they are called *Arnoldi eigenvalue estimates* (at step n) or *Ritz values* (wrt. \mathcal{K}_n).

Consider a vector $x \in \mathcal{K}_n$, such a vector can then be written as a linear combination of Krylov's vectors $b, Ab, \dots, A^{n-1}b$, put in polynomial form, it will be

$$x = q(A)b$$

Now consider $P^n := \{\text{monic polynomials of degree } n\}$, the famous *Arnoldi-Lanczos approximation problem* is proposed as

$$\min_{p^n \in P^n} \|p^n(A)b\|$$

and the Arnoldi iteration solves this problem exactly (if it doesn't break down ofc...) – the minimizer \bar{p}^n is uniquely given by the characteristic polynomial of H_n . As a proof, let $y := A^n b - \bar{p}^n(A)b \in \mathcal{K}_n$, then the problem can be considered as minimizing $\|A^n b - y\|$ wrt. y ; i.e., minimizing the distance from $A^n b$ to \mathcal{K}_n – thus the minimization can be characterized by $\bar{p}^n(A)b \perp \mathcal{K}_n \Leftrightarrow Q_n^* \bar{p}^n(A)b = 0$ as q_1, q_2, \dots, q_n are a basis of \mathcal{K}_n . Now consider

$A = QHQ^*$; where $Q := \begin{bmatrix} Q_n & U \end{bmatrix}$ such that Q is a orthogonal matrix extended from Q_n , and $H := \begin{bmatrix} H_n & X_2 \\ X_1 & X_3 \end{bmatrix}$, where the entries of X_1 is all 0 besides its upper-right entry and X_3 is Hessenberg – due to the Hessenberg structure of H . Then we have

$$\begin{aligned}
Q_n^* p^n(A) b &= 0 \\
\Leftrightarrow Q_n^* Q p^n(H) Q^* b &= 0 \\
\Leftrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} I_n & 0 \end{bmatrix} p^n(H) e_1 \|b\| &= 0
\end{aligned} \tag{2.6}$$

and (2.6) follows from $q_1 = \frac{b}{\|b\|}$. The interpretation of last equation is, the minimization characterization now becomes that the first n entries in the first column of $p^n(H)$ are 0. Due to the Hessenberg structure of H , the first n entries in the first column of $p^n(H)$ are exactly the first column of $p^n(H_n)$ – in view of this, it is *sufficient* to make $p^n(H_n) = 0$: by Cayley-Hamilton theorem, if p^n is the characteristic polynomial of H_n , $p^n(H_n) = 0$. Proof of uniqueness uses contradiction: if uniqueness is voided, taking difference of two distinct degree- n monic polynomials that both minimize $\|p^n(A) b\|$ will then result in a non-zero polynomial $q(A)$ of degree $\leq n - 1$ such that $q(A) b = 0$ – this contradicts the assumption that K_n is of full-rank.

Based on this finding, (iii). *the Ritz values generated by Arnoldi iteration are the roots of the optimal polynomial to the Arnoldi-Lanczos approximation problem.* And this gives the Ritz values some invariant properties:

- (*translation invariance*) If A is changed to $A + \sigma I$ for some $\sigma \in \mathbb{R}$, and b is left unchanged, the Ritz values $\{\theta_j\}$ at each step will be changed to $\{\theta_j + \sigma\}$
- (*scale invariance*) If A is changed to σA for some $\sigma \in \mathbb{R}$, and b is left unchanged, the Ritz values $\{\theta_j\}$ at each step will be changed to $\{\sigma \theta_j\}$
- (*unitary similarity transformation invariance*) If A is changed to UAU^* for some uni-

tary U , and b is changed to Ub , the Ritz values do not change

Generalized Minimal Residuals (GMRES) *GMRES* is a method using Arnoldi iteration to solve a linear system $Ax = b$, the resulting mechanic is to use $x_n \in \mathcal{K}_n$ at step n to approximate the root by formulating the problem:

$$\begin{aligned} & \min_{x_n \in \mathcal{K}_n} \|Ax_n - b\| \\ \Leftrightarrow & \min_{c \in \mathbb{R}^n} \|AK_n c - b\| \\ \Leftrightarrow & \min_{y \in \mathbb{R}^n} \|AQ_n y - b\| \\ \Leftrightarrow & \min_{y \in \mathbb{R}^n} \|Q_{n+1} \tilde{H}_n y - b\| \\ \Leftrightarrow & \min_{y \in \mathbb{R}^n} \|\tilde{H}_n y - Q_{n+1}^* b\| \end{aligned} \tag{2.7}$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \min_{y \in \mathbb{R}^n} \|\tilde{H}_n y - \|b\| e_1\| \tag{2.8}$$

where (2.7) is because that b is in the column space of Q_{n+1} (because $q_1 := \frac{b}{\|b\|}$), therefore left multiplication of Q_{n+1}^* does not change the norm. Furthermore, note that $Q_{n+1}^* b = \|b\| e_1$, which gives us (2.8).

On another note, the initial assumption for GMRES of $x_n \in \mathcal{K}_n$ is equivalent to $x_n = q_n(A)b$ for some degree- $(n-1)$ polynomial q_n , with coefficients being c mentioned in above equations. Then the residual satisfies $b - Ax_n = (I - Aq_n(A))b$; let $p_n(z) := 1 - zq_n(z)$, then GMRES in fact solves problem $\min_{p_n \in P_n} \|p_n(A)b\|$, but with

$$P_n := \{\text{degree} \leq n \text{ polynomials } p \text{ with } p(0) = 1\}.$$

Lanczos Iteration and Conjugate Gradient If A is symmetric, or Hermitian over the complex space, the Arnoldi iteration will be redundant to find eigenvalues of A – a method called Lanczos iteration was introduced as a simplification of Arnoldi iteration (*mainly sim-*

plified by noticing that H_n becomes tri-diagonal now). With a similar simplification idea, if A is symmetric positive definite, solving $\min_x \|Ax - b\|$ using GMRES will in fact not be efficient – *Conjugate Gradient (CG)* was then introduced based on *minimizing the A -norm of the error*; where the A -norm of $e_n := x^* - x_n$ is defined as $e_n^T A e_n$. Specifically, the famous CG is proposed as Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 Conjugate Gradient (CG)

Input: $A \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m} \succ 0$, $b \in \mathbb{R}^m$

Output: x_n – the solution of linear system $Ax = b$

- 1: Set $x_0 \leftarrow 0$, $r_0 \leftarrow b$, $p_0 \leftarrow r_0$ ▷ Initialization
 - 2: **while** not converged **do**
 - 3: $\alpha_k \leftarrow \frac{r_{k-1}^T r_{k-1}}{p_{k-1}^T A p_{k-1}}$ ▷ calculate step length
 - 4: $x_k \leftarrow x_{k-1} + \alpha_k p_{k-1}$ ▷ approximate solution
 - 5: $r_k \leftarrow r_{k-1} - \alpha_k A p_{k-1}$ ▷ calculate residual
 - 6: $\beta_k \leftarrow \frac{r_k^T r_k}{r_{k-1}^T r_{k-1}}$ ▷ calculate improvement from this step
 - 7: $p_k \leftarrow r_k + \beta_k p_{k-1}$ ▷ calculate next step's search direction
-

And induction on n can show that:

1. (*identity of subspaces*)

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{K}_n &= \langle x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n \rangle = \langle p_0, p_1, \dots, p_{n-1} \rangle \\ &= \langle r_0, r_1, \dots, r_{n-1} \rangle = \langle b, Ab, \dots, A^{n-1}b \rangle \end{aligned}$$

2. (*orthogonal residuals*)

$$r_i^T r_j = 0, \quad \forall i \neq j$$

3. (*A -conjugate search directions*)

$$p_i^T A p_j = 0, \quad \forall i \neq j$$

Following results above, for iteration n , we can show that x_n is the unique point in \mathcal{K}_n that

minimizes $\|e_n\|_A$; and the convergence is monotonic (descent property), i.e.,

$$\|e_n\|_A \leq \|e_{n-1}\|_A$$

and $e_n = 0$ is achieved for some $n \leq m$. The first statement follows some simple calculations, the monotonicity follows $\mathcal{K}_n \subset \mathcal{K}_{n+1}$.

As CG minimizes A -norm of the error in an iterative manner, this enables us to view CG as an optimization algorithm – simple calculations allow us to formulate the following problem for CG:

$$\min_{x \in \mathbb{R}^m} \frac{1}{2} x^T A x - x^T b$$

Lastly, similar to how we build the connection between Arnoldi iteration and GMRES in a polynomial minimization manner at the end of last section, it is similar for CG: CG approximation problem can be formulated as $\min_{p_n \in P_n} \|p_n(A) e_0\|_A$; where $e_0 := x^* - x_0$ denotes the initial error, and $P_n := \{\text{degree} \leq n \text{ polynomials } p \text{ with } p(0) = 1\}$, same as before. To conclude this section, it is worth noting that a plethora of nonlinear conjugate gradient methods have been derived from this original linear conjugate gradient [[Hager and Zhang, 2006](#)].

2.8 Brief Introduction on Dynamical Systems

This section presents a concise overview of certain dynamical system concepts, which enhances the understanding of the topics discussed in Manuscript 3. A substantial portion of the content presented in this section is based on the notes taken during the dynamical system course, wherein [[van den Berg et al., 2023](#)] served as the primary reference.

For a topological space X , a *flow* is a continuous map $\phi : \mathbb{R} \times X \mapsto X$ such that $\forall x \in X$, $t, s \in \mathbb{R}$,

1. $\phi(0, x) = x$
2. $\phi(t, \varphi(s, x)) = \phi(t + s, x)$

As mentioned in the third manuscript, the gradient flow is the flow generated by the ordinary differential equation

$$\dot{x} = -\nabla f(x)$$

for some smooth objective function f . The equilibrium point of a dynamical system, \bar{x} , describes the steady state by setting $\phi(\bar{x}) = 0$. Consider two flows, $\phi_1 : \mathbb{R} \times X_1 \mapsto X_1$ and $\phi_2 : \mathbb{R} \times X_2 \mapsto X_2$, the homeomorphism is a function $\varphi : X_1 \mapsto X_2$ such that φ is bijective, continuous with continuous inverse, and $\forall t \in \mathbb{R}, x \in X_1, \varphi(\phi_1(t, x)) = \phi_2(t, \varphi(x))$, known as *flow intertwining property*. Homeomorphism demonstrates that two flows, or dynamical systems in general, are topologically equivalent, which makes them important in analyzing the behavior of dynamical systems.

For the numerous numerical methods to find the equilibria of flow, the foundation is Cauchy-Lipschitz theorem, as known as Picard–Lindelöf theorem, the theorem states let $D \subseteq \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^n$ be closed and let $(t_0, y_0) \in \text{int } D$. Let $f : D \mapsto \mathbb{R}^n$ be a function that is continuous in t and Lipschitz continuous in y ; then $\exists \varepsilon > 0$ such that the initial value problem (IVP)

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{y} &= f(t, y(t)) \\ y(t_0) &= y_0 \end{aligned}$$

has a unique solution $y(t)$ on $\overline{B(t_0, \varepsilon)}$, the closed ball centered at t_0 with radius ε . This theorem ensures the existence and uniqueness of the underlying dynamical system governed by an IVP. The vast majority of differential equations can not be solved analytically; in this view, this theorem gives the condition that the underlying dynamical system is unique, further allowing various numerical methods to solve the system or to find the equilibria of the dynamical system.

2.9 Conclusion of Literature Review

To conclude this chapter, it is worth reiterating that a more detailed literature review is available in each of the three manuscripts included in this thesis. Specifically, the *Fast Fourier Transform-based Kernel Density Estimation (FFTKDE)* method as well as the k -nearest-neighbour method for estimating mutual information is elaborated in the Appendix [A.1](#) of the first manuscript. Furthermore, a foundational overview of variational and non-smooth analysis is presented in Section [5.4.1](#) of the third manuscript, providing the necessary theoretical underpinning.

Chapter 3

fastHDMI: Fast Mutual Information Estimation for High-Dimensional Data

Preamble to Manuscript 1.

Introduction to the Study and Its Place in the Workflow:

Manuscript 1 introduces `fastHDMI`, a Python package that carries out variable screening, representing a significant advancement in the initial stage of high-dimensional data analysis. This study is crucial because it directly addresses the challenge of efficiently analyzing complex neuroimaging datasets, which are characterized by their high dimensionality. The manuscript's approach, which is based on three different mutual information estimation methodologies, ensures that only the most relevant variables are selected for further analysis while maintaining robustness to nonlinear association, thereby allowing the subsequent stages of modeling and interpretation.

Interconnection with Subsequent Research Phases:

The methodologies developed in this manuscript provide a foundational tool for the entire analysis workflow outlined in the thesis. By successfully identifying key variables through `fastHDMI`, researchers can ensure that the modeling phase, discussed in subsequent manuscripts, is based on the most pertinent data, thereby enhancing the efficacy and computational efficiency of the models. This initial screening is particularly vital given the nonlinear associations often present in biological data, which traditional linear screening methods might miss.

Enhancement of Neuroimaging Data Analysis:

The utilization of the preprocessed Autism Brain Imaging Data Exchange (ABIDE) dataset to confirm the efficiency and computational efficiency of these screening techniques underlines the practical relevance of `fastHDMI`. Through a thorough evaluation of the various mutual information estimation techniques included in the package, the manuscript demonstrates its suitability for the analysis of real-world neuroimaging data.

Contribution to the Broader Research Goals:

The findings from Manuscript 1 significantly contribute to the overall objective of the thesis by enhancing our understanding of how to efficiently perform a screening of variables that are robust to nonlinear associations. This step is essential for the efficient processing and analysis of large datasets prevalent in biostatistics and underpins the subsequent methodological advances explored in Manuscripts 2 and 3. By establishing a robust and computationally efficient approach to variable screening, this manuscript ensures that the data fed into more complicated statistical models at the later stage is of the highest relevance and quality, thereby facilitating more robust and insightful analyses.

Transition to Manuscript 2:

Building on the computational efficiency achieved in Manuscript 1, Manuscript 2 expands these concepts into the realm of sparse estimation using nonconvex penalties. The ability to screen variables effectively sets the stage for these advanced computational techniques, which are designed to handle the challenges in statistical computing posed by the high-dimensional data structures. This natural progression underscores the interconnectedness of the manuscripts, as each builds upon the previous findings to enhance the overall efficacy of biostatistical data analyses.

**fastHDMI: Fast Mutual Information Estimation for
High-Dimensional Data**

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Abstract

In this paper, we introduce `fastHDMI`, a Python package for the efficient execution of variable screening for high-dimensional datasets, including neuroimaging datasets. This study marks the inaugural application of three distinct mutual information estimation methodologies for variable selection in the context of neuroimaging analysis, a novel contribution implemented through `fastHDMI`. Such advancements are critical for dissecting the complex architectures inherent in neuroimaging datasets, offering refined mechanisms for variable selection against the backdrop of high dimensionality. Employing the preprocessed Autism Brain Imaging Data Exchange (ABIDE) dataset [Cameron et al., 2013, Barry et al., 2020] as a foundation, we assess the efficacy of these variable screening methodologies through extensive simulation studies. These evaluations encompass a diverse set of conditions, including linear and nonlinear associations, alongside continuous and binary outcomes. The results delineate the *Fast Fourier Transform Kernel Density Estimation (FFTKDE)*-based mutual information estimation approach as preeminent for feature screening with continuous nonlinear outcomes, while the binning-based methodology is identified as superior for binary outcomes contingent on nonlinear underlying probability preimage. For linear simulations, a parity in performance is observed for continuous outcomes between the absolute Pearson correlation and FFTKDE-based mutual information estimation, with the former also exhibiting dominance in binary outcomes predicated on linear underlying probability preimage. A comprehensive case analysis utilizing the preprocessed Autism Brain Imaging Data Exchange (ABIDE) dataset further illuminates the applicative potential of `fastHDMI`, demonstrating the predictive capabilities of models constructed from variables selected through our implemented screening methods. This research not only substantiates the computational prowess and methodological robustness of `fastHDMI`, but also contributes significantly to the arsenal of analytical tools available for neuroimaging research.

3.1 Introduction

The question of how to best select a subset of variables from a large set is a commonly investigated topic in high-dimensional model fitting [Chandrashekar and Sahin, 2014]. This topic is often called “variable selection” in statistics, or “feature selection” in the machine learning world. Feature selection may be necessary either to fit a particular statistical model or, in some situations, because the data are too large for memory. Neuroimaging data provide a good example of such challenges. For example, Magnetic Resonance Images (MRI) result in measurements at millions of voxels [Bell and Drew, 2018, Liang et al., 2022, Linn et al., 2016, Fan and Chou, 2016], and the development of multiple imaging modalities is leading to multiple high-dimensional sets of features, each capturing a different aspect of brain function, that can show widespread correlation patterns within and between each modality. These high dimensions in neuroimaging data have stimulated the development of variable selection methods; indeed, there has been a recent surge in publications: see, for example, [Adeli et al., 2017, Fan and Chou, 2016, Febles et al., 2022, Gómez-Verdejo et al., 2019, Hao et al., 2020, He et al., 2018, Hunt et al., 2014, Ivanoska et al., 2021, Mohr et al., 2006, Martino et al., 2008, Pereda et al., 2018, Roy, 2021, Schlögl et al., 2002, Sofer et al., 2014, Suresh et al., 2022]. These papers take a wide variety of strategies ranging from univariate to multivariate selection. Among these, Fan and Chou [2016], Schlögl et al. [2002] considered absolute correlation or mutual information with respect to the outcome as a conventional univariate approach; selection based on sparse-inducing penalties on multivariable models were proposed on the data [Fan and Chou, 2016, Hao et al., 2020, Hunt et al., 2014, Roy, 2021] or transformed data [Adeli et al., 2017]. Multivariate selection based on random forest variable importance [Febles et al., 2022, Hao et al., 2020] or sign consistency from the support vector machine [Gómez-Verdejo et al., 2019] has also been applied previously. A “potential support vector machine” was applied by Mohr et al. [2006], an idea that rests on exchanging the roles of data points and features. Another approach can be seen in [Martino et al., 2008], where they selected features recursively based on multivariate

model fitting. Evidently, these papers take a wide variety of strategies ranging from simple methods like analyzing the direct absolute correlation between outcomes and features, to more complex approaches involving the use of univariate regression coefficients, univariate copulas, and techniques that leverage variable importance measures or sparse penalties in multivariate model fitting. Variable selection under a multivariable model generally requires certain assumptions, often including the assumption of linearity, which is not robust to misspecification. Furthermore, variable selection based on marginal associations demands less computational power and memory and can easily adapt to data inflow. Additionally, variable selection within a joint model framework allows for variable screening conditioned on other covariates, such as confounders.

Although Pearson correlation is frequently used to measure the association between covariates and the outcome, in situations where nonlinearity may be present, a variety of strategies have been introduced to examine the relationship between the outcome and the covariates [Rényi, 1959, Reshef et al., 2011, Speed, 2011]. These methods, when utilized for feature screening, effectively equate to screening via mutual information, as they are all deterministic monotonically increasing functions of mutual information. Among the strategies for feature selection, an entropy-based method, *mutual information* has two appealing characteristics. As defined in (3.3), mutual information is defined as the Kullback–Leibler divergence (KL divergence) between the joint distribution of two variables and their outer product distribution, effectively quantifying their dependency. This method can carry out model-independent feature selection, and is robust to non-linearity between the outcome and the features. For these reasons, mutual information has already been a popular choice for neuroimaging data. Ince et al. [2016] proposed to estimate mutual information based on the Gaussian Copula for continuous data, which works well for approximately Gaussian data, such as local field potentials and M/EEG data [Magri et al., 2009]. Nemirovsky et al. [2023] advanced the analysis of functional MRI data by implementing integrated information theory, which is calculated based on the mutual information between the state of the conscious system over

time and across the conscious system’s partitions. Tsai et al. [1999] used mutual information to analyze functional MRI data to compute an activation map. Schlögl et al. [2002] used mutual information to study the EEG-based brain-computer interface. Chai et al. [2009] and Li [2022] employed multivariate mutual information to study functional connectivity between brain regions in functional MRI data. Combrisson et al. [2022] proposed a nonparametric permutation-based framework for neurophysiological data to analyze cognitive brain networks.

While mutual information estimation for discrete random variables is trivial, the estimation of mutual information for continuous random variables can be done using a few different approaches. One fundamental method is to estimate mutual information based on the binning of continuous variables to treat them as discrete variables. Steuer et al. [2002] reported improved performance using Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) based methods. KDE-based methods numerically calculate the mutual information estimation based on the estimated kernel density functions [Moon et al., 1995]. The k -Nearest Neighbors (k NN) approach was previously adapted to estimate mutual information [Faivishevsky and Goldberger, 2008, Kraskov et al., 2004, Victor, 2002, Pál et al., 2010, Lord et al., 2018, Gao et al., 2015]. Khan et al. [2007] compared the performance of mutual information estimators based on k NN and KDE and concluded that KDE-based mutual information estimators outperform k NN-based estimators for small samples with a high noise level. Gao et al. [2015] argued that accurate estimation of mutual information of two strongly dependent variables using k NN-based methods requires a prohibitively large sample size. As shown later in our simulation studies in Section 3.3.1, our KDE-based mutual information screening method also outperforms the k NN-based counterpart. Since kernel density estimation on large volume of data is a computationally challenging approach and that neuroimaging data is usually of large volume, variable screening based on mutual information has never been implemented for neuroimaging data to the best of our knowledge. In this paper, we implement variable screening methods using a few different approaches and carried out comprehensive simula-

tion and real case studies using the preprocessed ABIDE data [Cameron et al., 2013, Barry et al., 2020]. The variable screening functionality is encapsulated within our Python package, `fastHDMI`, an acronym for *Fast high-dimensional Mutual Information estimation*. This package is specifically designed to facilitate the effective processing and analysis of substantial volumes of neuroimaging data using a few different computationally efficient estimation methods.

In Section 3.2, we will explore the concept of mutual information and provide an overview of the estimation methods. Subsequently, Section 3.3 assesses the efficacy of variable selection and the computational speed of the variable selection methods implemented in our `fastHDMI` package. These methods encompass *Fast Fourier Transform-based Kernel Density Estimation (FFTKDE)* mutual information estimation, mutual information estimation based on binning of continuous variables with the number of bins determined using the results of a previous study [Birgé and Rozenholc, 2006] utilizing bounds on the risk of penalized maximum likelihood estimators due to Castellán [Castellán, 2000], k NN-based mutual information estimation, and Pearson correlation. The k NN-based mutual information estimation utilized in our work is adapted from the `scikit-learn` library. We will begin by examining these variable screening methods within our `fastHDMI` package through simulations in Section 3.3.1, then proceed to compare their computing speeds. Finally, in Section 3.3.2, the performance of the predictive models created with the variables selected using our four implemented methods will be demonstrated.

3.2 Estimation of Mutual Information

The entropy-based screening methods are based on Shannon’s entropy [Shannon, 1948]. Let $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ denote a random variable residing in a probability space with probability mass or

density function $p(\mathbf{X})$. Shannon’s entropy is defined as

$$H(\mathbf{X}) := \mathbb{E}[-\log p(\mathbf{X})]. \quad (3.1)$$

Furthermore, Lebesgue’s decomposition theorem expands the above definition for all other random variables. Relative entropy, also known as the *KL divergence*, is a specific case of Bregman divergence applied to $-H$, the negative of Shannons entropy, which is a strictly convex functional:

$$D_{KL}(\mathbf{X}_1 \parallel \mathbf{X}_2) := \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}_1} \left[-\log \frac{p(\mathbf{X}_2)}{p(\mathbf{X}_1)} \right]. \quad (3.2)$$

Moreover, mutual information is defined as the KL divergence from the joint distribution (\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}) to the outer product distribution $\mathbf{X} \otimes \mathbf{Y}$, hence symmetric. For random variables \mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y} , the mutual information

$$I(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}) := D_{KL}((\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}) \parallel \mathbf{X} \otimes \mathbf{Y}). \quad (3.3)$$

\mathbf{X} and \mathbf{Y} in (3.3) are typically univariate for variable screenings. The implementation of KDE-based mutual information estimation uses Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) based KDE methods from the Python package KDEpy [Odland, 2018]. FFT-based KDE was initially proposed by Silverman [1982] on Gaussian kernels with much faster computing speed and much lower numerical errors. As shown in the paper, such an approach significantly solves the computational speed challenges that KDE usually faces [Silverman, 1982]. The performance of KDE usually depends on the bandwidth and kernel selection. While we leave it for users to choose kernel and bandwidth, the default arguments are set to be the state-of-the-art *Improved Sheather-Jones* bandwidth [Botev et al., 2010] with Epanechnikov kernel [Epanechnikov, 1969]. For a detailed explanation of the FFTKDE method for mutual information estimation, see Appendix A.1.

At the same time, mutual information estimation using the k NN method leverages the k NN

algorithm for entropy estimation, a technique introduced by [L. F. Kozachenko \[1987\]](#). This method estimates Shannon entropy, as detailed in equation (5.2), with the sample mean, alongside a trinomial distribution to estimate $\widehat{p}(x_j)$. The binning approach for mutual information estimation converts continuous variables into discrete variables through binning, with the optimal number of bins guided by findings from a previous study by [Birgé and Rozenholc \[2006\]](#), which derived the optimal number of bins based on the bounds on the risk of penalized maximum likelihood estimators due to [Castellan \[2000\]](#). Pearson correlation is calculated through the standardized inner product of outcomes and variables. Additionally, to drastically improve the processing speed for large-scale datasets, our package incorporates multiprocessing capabilities, enabling parallel processing across all employed methods. This adaptation to parallel computing significantly enhances the utility of our package, especially for extensive neuroimaging data analyses.

Previous studies demonstrated that the three density estimation methods discussed in this paper, KDE, k NN, and histogram-based methods, are consistent estimators under suitable conditions. The Lebesgue integral, as a linear operator, has its boundedness equivalent to continuity in a normed linear space. Since expectation is a linear operator, it is continuous under appropriate norms when it is bounded. By the continuous mapping Theorem, the mutual information estimated using these three density estimators is consistent, as the mutual information functional is continuous with respect to the joint likelihood, and continuity is preserved under finite composition.

Furthermore, since mutual information is continuous with respect to the joint density, sufficiently small numerical errors will not significantly perturb the mutual information estimation. The numerical error associated with the FFT procedure arises from multiple sources beyond numerical precision, including errors from using a finite number of Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) terms — such as discretization, truncation of frequencies, and aliasing; and errors from applying FFT to a non-periodic function, including boundary effects, zero-

padding, and interpolation. Notably, Fourier's theorem implies that the error from FFT for *periodic* functions vanishes asymptotically with respect to the number of DFT terms. With a computational complexity of $O(n \log n)$, utilizing a sufficiently fine grid can mitigate these errors while maintaining high computational efficiency. Moreover, KDE is inherently non-periodic. Consequently, errors due to boundary effects, zeropadding, and interpolation are influenced by the chosen interval for KDE and will not asymptotically vanish with respect to the number of DFT terms. The error due to the chosen bounded interval in which the data points reside presents a general challenge when evaluating mutual information numerically, not limited to the FFT approach. Additionally, it is important to note that numerical errors, though generally insignificant when using a large number of DFT terms, will not vanish asymptotically with respect to the number of data points in the dataset. In summary, FFT is an efficient tool to perform KDE while maintaining high computational efficiency, as evidenced by previous studies [Silverman, 1982].

3.3 Simulation and Case Studies

Autism Brain Imaging Data Exchange (ABIDE) preprocessed Data consists of preprocessed functional MRI brain imaging data from 539 individuals suffering from ASD and 573 typical controls [Cameron et al., 2013]. In this paper, we used the preprocessed ABIDE data consisting of 149955 brain imaging variables, together with age, biological sex, and diagnosis of autism for 508 cases and 542 controls [Cameron et al., 2013, Barry et al., 2020]. The preprocessing was carried out exactly the same manner as the preprocessing performed earlier by Barry et al. [2020] (see also [Fischl, 2012, Dale et al., 1999]): the T1-weighted Magnetic Resonance scans were processed through the FreeSurfer 6.0 pipeline [Fischl, 2012] on the CBrain computing facility [Sherif et al., 2014]. This pipeline delineates the cortical surface from magnetic resonance scans, allowing the quantification of the cortical thickness across the brain hemispheres [Fischl, 2012, Dale et al., 1999]. The process involves several

steps: affine registration to MNI305 space [Collins et al., 1994], bias field correction, removal of non-cortical regions, and the estimation of white matter and pial surfaces from intensity gradients, which are used to estimate cortical thickness. These cortical surfaces are projected into a common space (fsaverage) for comparison across individuals.

Brain MRI data has been used to predict age to study the brain aging process linked to diseases such as Alzheimers disease and Parkinsons disease [Jonsson et al., 2019, Jiang et al., 2020, Cole et al., 2017, Franke et al., 2010, Liem et al., 2017]. For the case studies based on the preprocessed ABIDE data [Cameron et al., 2013, Barry et al., 2020] in Section 3.3.2, we choose age at the MRI scan as the continuous outcome and autism diagnosis as the binary outcome. When using age at the MRI scan as the outcome, we adjust for sex and autism diagnosis; we using autism diagnosis as the outcome, we adjust for age and sex. We compare the few screening methods in our Python package `fastHDMI`, including mutual information estimation using the FFTKDE and k NN originally implemented in the `scikit-learn` library, as well as Pearson correlation.

3.3.1 Simulation based on the preprocessed ABIDE data [Cameron et al., 2013, Barry et al., 2020]

We decided to simulate outcomes based on the preprocessed ABIDE MRI features in order to preserve the distribution patterns and the correlation structure in this high-dimensional dataset. Therefore, we simulated both nonlinear and linear outcomes from the preprocessed ABIDE data [Cameron et al., 2013, Barry et al., 2020]. Let $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times p}$ denote the design matrix; i.e., all the MRI brain imaging variables from the entire preprocessed ABIDE dataset. The simulation of the *nonlinear* outcomes proceeds in this manner – the nonlinearity for continuous outcomes comes from the quadratic manipulation, i.e., step 4:

1. Pick the number of “true” covariates p_{true} , choose p_{true} uniformly randomly from the full feature set; let $\mathbf{X}_{\text{true}} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times p_{\text{true}}}$ denote the corresponding design sub-matrix.
2. Simulate the corresponding “true” coefficients $\boldsymbol{\beta}_{\text{true}} \in \mathbb{R}^{p_{\text{true}}}$ with $\boldsymbol{\beta}_{\text{true}} \sim N_{p_{\text{true}}}(1, \Sigma_{\boldsymbol{\beta}_{\text{true}}})$ and $\Sigma_{\boldsymbol{\beta}_{\text{true}}}$ being a 0.6 Toeplitz matrix. The correlation design aims to replicate the phenomenon of correlated brain signals.
3. Standardize the design sub-matrix for the true features \mathbf{X}_{true} , to obtain $\mathbf{X}_{\text{true},1}$.
4. For nonlinear simulations only: take the element-wise square of $\mathbf{X}_{\text{true},1}$ and then standardize the matrix again to obtain $\mathbf{X}_{\text{true},2}$; the standardization here is to ensure that each feature impacts the simulated outcome proportionally.
5. The continuous and binary outcomes are then simulated in this manner:
 - (a) To simulate continuous outcomes:
 - i. Pick $\text{SNR} = 3$; calculate $\sigma_{\text{true}} = \sqrt{\frac{\boldsymbol{\beta}_{\text{true}}^T \mathbf{X}_{\text{true},2}^T \mathbf{X}_{\text{true},2} \boldsymbol{\beta}_{\text{true}}}{\text{SNR}}}$;
 - ii. Simulate the error $\varepsilon_j \stackrel{i.i.d.}{\sim} N(0, \sigma_{\text{true}}^2)$;
 - iii. The outcome is simulated as $\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{X}_{\text{true},2} \boldsymbol{\beta}_{\text{true}} + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$.
 - (b) To simulate binary outcomes:
 - i. Calculate $\boldsymbol{\tau} = \mathbf{X}_{\text{true},2} \boldsymbol{\beta}_{\text{true}}$;
 - ii. Standardize $\boldsymbol{\tau}$, obtain $\boldsymbol{\tau}'$ – this is to avoid the data being too centered, which will cause all simulated binary outcomes in the same class;
 - iii. Take $\boldsymbol{\tau}'' = \boldsymbol{\tau}' + \text{arctanh}\sqrt{\frac{1}{3}}$ for *translated* binary outcome simulations, or $\boldsymbol{\tau}'' = \boldsymbol{\tau}'$ for *original* binary outcome simulations. The translated binary outcome simulation is to make the logistic transformation of centered data in the next step as nonlinear as possible, as $\pm \text{arctanh}\sqrt{\frac{1}{3}}$ is the location for the logistic transformation to achieve the greatest absolute curvature value;
 - iv. The binary outcome is then simulated as $y_j \stackrel{\text{indep.}}{\sim} \text{Bern}(\text{logistic}(\tau_j''))$.

For linear simulations, we omit step 4 and take $\mathbf{X}_{\text{true},2} := \mathbf{X}_{\text{true},1}$ thereafter.

The screening of features with respect to the simulated continuous and binary outcomes \mathbf{y} are then carried out using the original entire design matrix \mathbf{X} . Variable selection performance

is measured by *Variable Selection Area under Receiver Operating Curve (AUROC)*, which is the AUROC calculated with the true labels taking value 1 for the simulated true coefficients and 0 for other coefficients, and the ranking of the coefficients follows the absolute value of the three association measures, respectively; i.e., \widehat{MI} based on FFTKDE and k NN, as well as Pearson correlation. The top p_{true} of the most associated covariates are then taken as selected covariates, which will take value 1, and the others will take value 0. Variable Selection AUROC therefore measures the matching between the selected covariates and the simulated “true” covariates. Such measures can differentiate distinct methods when the traditional measures such as classification rate or adjusted Rand Index can not – a scenario frequently occurs to variable selection for ultra-high-dimensional data.

We evaluate the efficacy of our implemented variable screening methods in `fastHDMI` package, including: 1) Mutual information estimation using FFTKDE, 2) Mutual information estimation using k NN, 3) Mutual information estimation through binning, and 4) absolute Pearson correlation. Our findings, illustrated in Figures 3.1 and 3.2, reveal that for continuous outcomes, the FFTKDE-based mutual information estimator outperforms its counterparts. In scenarios with linear relationships, FFTKDE-based mutual information estimator and absolute Pearson correlation are jointly the most effective. Conversely, for binary outcomes, the binning-based mutual information estimator excels in capturing nonlinear associations, whereas other methodologies display substantially overlapping confidence intervals. In linear association contexts, Pearson correlation emerges as the most effective method for binary outcomes. Interestingly, Pearson correlation, particularly when employed with a balanced number of cases and controls, inherently correlates to a two-sample testing approach, which explains its superior performance for binary outcomes with linearly simulated underlying probability pre-image.

All discussed variable screening methods were conducted concurrently on 16-core CPUs on Compute Canada. The fast Fourier transform (FFT) algorithm is leveraged to significantly

enhance the efficiency of the KDE estimation process, traditionally viewed as computationally intensive. As depicted in Figure 3.3, the execution times to complete the screenings with all the methods implemented in our `fastHDMI` package are assessed. Notably, the KDE-based mutual information estimation, often anticipated to be slower, exhibited competitive speed akin to alternative methods, courtesy of the FFT algorithm’s effectiveness. This computational efficiency was achieved with the same CPU configuration, while intentionally avoiding multiple data duplications in memory during multiprocessing. Given the substantial size of high-dimensional datasets, duplicating such datasets in memory is generally impractical.

3.3.2 Pre-processed ABIDE data case studies [Cameron et al., 2013, Barry et al., 2020] – predict age and diagnosis

In this subsection, we evaluate the performance of various variable screening techniques implemented in the `fastHDMI` package using preprocessed ABIDE data [Cameron et al., 2013, Barry et al., 2020]. Initially, we deploy the four variable screening methods to identify the features most associated with the outcome. Since we are fitting multiple penalized models, standardization of the selected variables is carried out to achieve a sample mean of 0 and a standard deviation of 1. This step is crucial for ensuring consistent penalization across all coefficients of the penalized covariates.

Subsequently, we divide the dataset, stratified by the outcome, into a training set comprising 80% of the observations and a testing set with the remaining 20%. This stratification ensures a balanced representation of the outcomes in both sets. For the continuous outcome, age, we employ binning to categorize observations into 30 bins based on their outcome values, followed by stratification based on the bin labels. This approach allows for the division of the dataset into training and testing sets with similar outcome means, an important factor for reliable prediction performance comparison.

For the continuous outcome variable, age at MRI scan, we fit several models: elastic net, least-angle regression (LARS), least absolute shrinkage and selection operator (LASSO), LASSO-LARS, linear model, Random Forest regressor, and ridge regression. Except for the Random Forest regressor, which utilizes the out-of-bag error scored by R^2 for model averaging, all models are tuned using 5-fold cross-validation with validation set R^2 as the scoring function for penalty hyperparameters.

For binary outcomes, diagnosis of autism disorder, we fit both unpenalized and penalized logistic regressions (using ℓ_1 , ℓ_2 , and elastic net penalties), as well as the Random Forest classifier. All models, with the exception of the Random Forest classifier, which uses out-of-bag error scored by Gini impurity for model averaging, are tuned using 5-fold cross-validation, scored by mean accuracy for the penalty hyperparameters.

Unlike simulation studies in Section 3.3.1, where “true” signals are known, case studies lack such definitive benchmarks, necessitating reliance on model-based performance metrics. Hence, we use testing set R^2 for continuous outcomes and testing set Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic (AUROC) for binary outcomes to evaluate model performance.

Figure 3.4 illustrates that in predicting the continuous outcome, age at MRI scan, linear models utilizing brain imaging variables selected using mutual information estimations via FFKDE or k NN emerge as the best-performing. Conversely, models built using variables selected by mutual information estimations based on binning exhibit the least predictive capability. However, within the context of random forest regression, models built using variables chosen through mutual information estimation by k NN outperform the rest. Figure 3.5 indicates that for the binary outcome of autism diagnosis, models constructed with variables selected via absolute Pearson correlation yield superior predictive performance. This phenomenon could stem from multiple factors, including the linear nature of the assessment model, which favors linear association measures, or a linear relationship between age at MRI

scan, the probability of autism diagnosis, and the brain imaging covariates.

3.4 Conclusion and Discussion

In this paper, we introduce the Python package `fastHDMI`, designed to streamline variable screening through three distinct mutual information estimation methods along with absolute Pearson correlation. Our evaluations, conducted on the large, high-dimensional preprocessed ABIDE data [Cameron et al., 2013, Barry et al., 2020], affirm `fastHDMI`'s computational efficiency and robustness. Through extensive simulation studies, which encompass both simulations for linear and nonlinear associations, as well as continuous and binary simulated outcomes, we evaluated the performance of each implemented variable screening method. Our findings reveal that for simulated continuous nonlinear outcomes, the FFTKDE-based mutual information estimation method excels in variable selection. Similarly, for simulated binary outcomes with a nonlinear underlying probability preimage, the binning-based mutual information estimation stands out. In the cases of simulated continuous linear outcomes, both absolute Pearson correlation and FFTKDE-based mutual information estimation share the top performance. Furthermore, absolute Pearson correlation is superior for binary outcomes simulated with linear underlying probability preimage. Complementing our simulations, a comprehensive case study on the preprocessed ABIDE data [Cameron et al., 2013, Barry et al., 2020] showcased the predictive capabilities of models crafted from the most relevant covariates identified by our methods. By pioneering sophisticated variable selection techniques in the domain of high-dimensional neuroimaging data, our work stands as a critical advancement, fostering novel pathways for research exploration and analytical insight within the scientific community. A promising avenue for future research could be to explore variable screening based on non-parametric copula models [Rabhi and Bouezmarni, 2019].

3.5 Disclaimer

All codes to reproduce the simulation and case study results of this paper and outputs from Calcul Quebec/Compute Canada can be found on the following GitHub repository:

<https://github.com/Kaiyangshi-Ito/fastHDMI>

Figure 3.1: Variable selection AUROC on the simulated *nonlinear* continuous and original/-translated binary outcomes; the horizontal axis is the number of “true” covariates used in the outcome simulation. Means with their 95% confidence intervals were plotted for 100 simulation replications.

Figure 3.2: Variable selection AUROC on the simulated *linear* continuous and original/-translated binary outcomes; the horizontal axis is the number of “true” covariates used in the outcome simulation. Means with their 95% confidence intervals were plotted for 100 simulation replications.

Figure 3.3: Running speeds of variable screening for continuous (age) and binary (diagnosis) outcomes utilizing the methods under study. The horizontal axis represents the proportion of features introduced into the screening phase, while the vertical axis measures the time in seconds to complete the screening. The plot displays the mean running times and their corresponding 95% confidence intervals (C.I.), derived from 5 simulation replications.

Figure 3.4: Testing Set R^2 for age at the scan outcome v.s. the number of most associated brain imaging covariates based on the association measure rankings. Means with their 95% confidence intervals were plotted for 20 simulation replications.

Figure 3.5: Testing Set AUROC for autism diagnosis outcome v.s. the number of most associated brain imaging covariates based on the association measure rankings. Means with their 95% confidence intervals were plotted for 20 simulation replications.

Chapter 4

Accelerated Gradient Methods for Sparse Statistical Learning with Nonconvex Penalties

Preamble to Manuscript 2.

Introduction to the Study and Its Place in the Workflow:

Manuscript 2 advances the computational frontier by delving into the optimization challenges associated with nonconvex oracle penalties, a critical area when dealing with the complexities of sparse learning of high-dimensional data that follow the initial variable screening. The manuscript adapts Nesterovs Accelerated Gradient (AG) method, traditionally used for convex objective functions, to handle nonconvexity induced by oracle penalties such as SCAD.

Building on Foundations Established in Manuscript 1:

The integration of nonconvex optimization techniques is a direct progression from the efficient variable screening method introduced in Manuscript 1. With the relevant variables identified using `fastHDMI`, the need for efficient optimization techniques that can manage the intricacies of the high-dimensional dataset composed of these selected variables becomes apparent. Manuscript 2 addresses this by enhancing the capability of statistical computing methods to converge faster, even when nonconvex penalties are involved, thereby ensuring the computational efficiency of sparse learning.

Innovation and Contribution to Statistical Computing:

The manuscript's development of a optimization hyperparameter setting based on the complexity upper bound to accelerate convergence represents a significant contribution in statistical computing. By establishing a rate of convergence and providing a new bound for the optimal damping sequence, this study not only enhances the understanding of nonconvex optimization algorithms but also improves the practical application of these methods in high-dimensional settings.

Enhancing Model Performance and Reliability:

The proposed adaptations allow faster convergence compared to traditional methods, such as the proximal gradient algorithm. This improvement is crucial for handling sophisticated models that emerge from the high-dimensional large datasets prevalent in biostatistics, particularly those involving sparse learning problems. The ability to recover signals more effectively further underscores the practical value of the advances made in this manuscript.

On the Lipschitz–Smooth Constant and More Clarifications:

Depending on the optimization problem, L_Ψ often has a closed form in a context of statistical sparse learning. For example, in the case of a penalized linear model, it is given by $\frac{1}{n} \|X^T X\|_2 + L_{\text{SCAD/MCP}}$. In the discussed statistical sparse learning context, nonconvexity arises from the nonconvex penalties. As illustrated in the manuscript, nonconvex penalties typically decompose into a difference of convex form: a convex ℓ_1 component to induce sparsity and a concave component. As discussed in the manuscript, the concave component has a Lipschitz–smooth constant of $L_{\text{SCAD}} = \frac{1}{a-1}$ for SCAD and $L_{\text{MCP}} = \frac{1}{\gamma}$ for MCP, which is often negligible compared to the Lipschitz-smooth constant for the convex smooth component. Previous literature indicates that the greatest eigenvalue of random matrices tend to grow with the number of dimensions. Specifically, studies on the spectral properties of random matrices have shown that the greatest eigenvalue often scales with the dimension of the matrix [Wigner, 1955,9, Marčenko and Pastur, 1967, Mehta, 2004, Bai and Silverstein, 2010]. This implies that the Lipschitz–smooth constant for the nonconvex smooth component is often negligible compared to that of the convex smooth component in the context of high-dimensional data, where the operator norm of the Hessian typically grows with the greatest eigenvalue of the design matrix.

Global convergence refers to the property of an algorithm in which, starting from any point in the feasible set, the algorithm will converge to a stationary point.

The dynamical system interpretation of the momentum methods reveals that the trajectory of the algorithm describes *Newtonian particles moving through a viscous medium in a conservative force field* [Qian, 1999, Su et al., 2014, Shi et al., 2018, Attouch et al., 2020]. Hence, in the context of statistical computing, when applied to a proper objective function, the trajectory of the optimization algorithm for parameter estimation is bounded, which serves as the rationale behind the boundedness assumption.

Transition to Manuscript 3:

Having established an efficient framework for optimizing high-dimensional statistical models under nonconvex conditions, Manuscript 3 takes the next logical step by addressing another layer of complexity: robust statistical modeling of correlated observations. The introduction of the q Gaussian linear mixed-effects model in Manuscript 3 builds directly on the optimization techniques refined in Manuscript 2, adapting them to models that must also account for correlation among observations. This advancement guarantees that the formulated methods are not just computationally efficient, but also robust to underlying normality assumptions and heavy tails while accounting for correlated observations, assisting in managing the intricacies of biostatistical data.

Accelerated Gradient Methods for Sparse Statistical Learning with Nonconvex Penalties

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Abstract

Nesterov’s accelerated gradient (AG) is a popular technique to optimize objective functions comprising two components: a convex loss and a penalty function. While AG methods perform well for convex penalties, such as the LASSO, convergence issues may arise when it is applied to nonconvex penalties, such as SCAD. A recent proposal generalizes Nesterov’s AG method to the nonconvex setting. The proposed algorithm requires specification of several hyperparameters for its practical application. Aside from some general conditions, there is no explicit rule for selecting the hyperparameters, and how different selection can affect convergence of the algorithm. In this article, we propose a hyperparameter setting based on the complexity upper bound to accelerate convergence, and consider the application of this nonconvex AG algorithm to high-dimensional linear and logistic sparse learning problems. We further establish the rate of convergence and present a simple and useful bound to characterize our proposed optimal damping sequence. Simulation studies show that convergence can be made, on average, considerably faster than that of the conventional proximal gradient algorithm. Our experiments also show that the proposed method generally outperforms the current state-of-the-art methods in terms of signal recovery.

4.1 Introduction

Sparse learning is an important component of modern data science and is an essential tool for the statistical analysis of high-dimensional data, with significant applications in signal processing and statistical genetics, among others. Penalization is commonly used to achieve sparsity in parameter estimation. The prototypical optimization problem for obtaining penalized estimators is

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}} \in \arg \min_{\boldsymbol{\beta} \in \mathbb{R}^{q+1}} \left[f(\boldsymbol{\beta}) + \sum_{j=1}^q p_{\lambda}(\beta_j) \right],$$

where $f : \mathbb{R}^{q+1} \mapsto \mathbb{R}$ is a convex loss function, $p_{\lambda} : \mathbb{R} \mapsto \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ constitutes the penalty term, and $\lambda > 0$ is the tuning parameter for the penalty. Commonly used penalization methods for sparse learning include: LASSO (Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator) [Tibshirani, 1996], Elastic Net [Zou and Hastie, 2005], SCAD (Smoothly Clipped Absolute Deviation) [Fan and Li, 2001] and MCP (Minimax Concave Penalty) [Zhang et al., 2010]. Among these penalties, parameter estimation with SCAD and MCP leads to a nonconvex objective function. The nonconvexity poses a challenge in statistical computing, as most methods developed for convex objective functions might not converge when applied to the nonconvex counterpart.

Various approaches have been proposed to carry out parameter estimation with SCAD or MCP penalties. Zou and Li [Zou and Li, 2008] proposed a local linear approximation, which yields a first-order majorization-minimization (MM) algorithm. Kim et al. [Kim et al., 2008] discussed a difference-of-convex programming (DCP) method for ordinary least square estimators penalized by the SCAD penalty, which was later generalized by Wang et al. [Wang et al., 2013] to a general class of nonconvex penalties to produce a first-order algorithm. These first-order methods belong to the class of proximal gradient descent methods, which are usually inefficient as relaxation is often expensive [Nesterov, 2004b]. The objective function is often ill-conditioned for sparse learning problems, and gradient descent with constant step size is especially inefficient for high-dimensional problems. Indeed, previous studies

have suggested that the condition number of a square random matrix grows linearly with respect to its dimension [Edelman, 1988]. Therefore, high-dimensional problems have a large condition number with high probability. Specific to gradient descent with constant step size, the trajectory will oscillate in the directions with a large eigenvalue, moving very slowly toward the directions with a small eigenvalue, making the algorithm inefficient. Lee et al. [Lee et al., 2016] developed a modified second-order method originally designed for the ordinary least square loss function penalized by LASSO with extensions to SCAD and MCP; this attempt was later extended to generalized linear models, such as logistic and Poisson regression, and Cox’s proportional hazard model. Quasi-Newton methods, or a mixture of first and second-order descent methods, have also been applied on nonconvex penalties [Ibrahim et al., 2012, Ghosh and Thoresen, 2016]. However, for high-dimensional problems, these second-order methods are slow due to the computational cost of evaluating the secant condition. Concurrently, most first and second-order methods discussed above require a line-search procedure at each step to ensure global convergence, which is prohibitive when the number of parameters to estimate grows large. Breheny and Huang [Breheny and Huang, 2011] implemented a coordinate descent method in the `ncvreg` R package to carry out estimation for linear models with least squares loss or logistic regression, penalized by SCAD and MCP. Mazumder et al. [Mazumder et al., 2011] also implemented a coordinate descent method in the `sparsenet` R package, which carries out a closed-form root-finding update in a coordinate-wise manner for penalized linear regression. Similar to how ill-conditioning makes gradient descent inefficient, coordinate descent methods are generally inefficient when the covariate correlations are high [Friedman et al., 2007]. Previous studies have also found that coordinate-wise minimization might not converge for some nonsmooth objective functions [Spall, 2012]. Furthermore, it is naturally challenging to run coordinate-wise minimization in parallel, as the algorithm must run in a sequential coordinate manner.

Due to the low computational cost and adequate memory requirement per iteration, first-order methods without a line search procedure have become the primary approach for high-

dimensional problems arising from various areas [Beck, 2017]. For smooth convex objective functions, Nesterov proposed the *accelerated gradient method* (AG) to improve the rate of convergence from $O(1/N)$ for gradient descent to $O(1/N^2)$ while achieving global convergence [Nesterov, 1983]. Subsequently, Nesterov extended AG to composite convex problems [Nesterov, 2012], whereas the objective is the sum of a smooth convex function and a simple nonsmooth convex function. With proper step-size choices, Nesterov’s AG was later shown optimal to solve both smooth and nonsmooth convex programming problems [Lan, 2011].

Given that sparse learning problems are often high-dimensional, Nesterov’s AG has been frequently used for *convex* problems in statistical machine learning (e.g., [Simon et al., 2013, Yang and Zou, 2014, Yu et al., 2015, Akyildiz and Míguez, 2021]). However, convergence is questionable if the convexity assumption is violated. Recently, Ghadimi and Lan [Ghadimi and Lan, 2015] generalized the AG method to nonconvex objective functions, hereafter referred to as the nonconvex AG method, and derived the rates of convergence for both smooth and composite objective functions. While this method can be applied to nonconvex sparse learning problems, several hyperparameters must be set prior to running the algorithm and can be difficult to choose in practice. Indeed, the nonconvex AG method has never been applied in the context of sparse statistical learning problems with nonconvex penalties, such as SCAD and MCP.

This manuscript presents a detailed analysis of the complexity upper bound of the nonconvex AG algorithm and proposes a hyperparameter setting to accelerate convergence (Theorem 1). We further establish the rate of convergence (Theorem 2) and present a simple and useful bound to characterize our proposed optimal damping sequence (Theorem 3 and Corollary 4). Our simulation studies on penalized linear and logistic models show that the nonconvex AG method with the proposed hyperparameter selector converges considerably faster than other first-order methods. We also compare the signal recovery performance of the algorithm to

that of `ncvreg`, the state-of-the-art method based on coordinate descent, showing that the proposed method outperforms the state-of-the-art coordinate descent method.

The rest of this manuscript is organised as follows. In Sections 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, we will present an analysis of the nonconvex AG algorithm by Ghadimi and Lan [2015] to illustrate the algorithm as a generalization of Nesterov’s AG. We also present formal results about the effect of hyperparameter settings on the complexity upper bound. Section 4.5 will include simulation studies for linear and logistic models penalized by SCAD and MCP penalties. The simulation studies show that i) The AG method using our proposed hyperparameter settings converges faster than commonly used first-order methods for data with various q/n and covariate correlation settings; and ii) our method outperforms the current state-of-the-art method, i.e. `ncvreg`, in terms of signal recovery performance, especially when the signal-to-noise ratios are low. The proofs for the theorems are included in the Appendix B.1.

4.2 Motivation and Setup

Having built on Nesterov’s seminal work, Ghadimi and Lan [Ghadimi and Lan, 2015] considered the following composite optimization problem:

$$\min_{x \in \mathbb{R}^{q+1}} \Psi(x) + \chi(x), \quad \Psi(x) := f(x) + h(x), \quad (\mathcal{P})$$

where $f \in \mathcal{C}_{L_f}^{1,1}(\mathbb{R}^{q+1}, \mathbb{R})$ is convex, $h \in \mathcal{C}_{L_h}^{1,1}(\mathbb{R}^{q+1}, \mathbb{R})$ is possibly nonconvex, and χ is a convex function over a bounded domain, and $\mathcal{C}_L^{1,1}$ denotes the class of first-order Lipschitz smooth functions with L being the Lipschitz constant. They devised Algorithm 2 discussed in details in next section, and presented a theoretical analysis of their algorithm.

Some commonly used nonconvex penalties, such as SCAD and MCP, have a form that can naturally be decomposed into summation of a convex and a nonconvex function satisfying

the conditions required by Ghadimi and Lan [Ghadimi and Lan, 2015]. When such penalties are added to a smooth convex deviance measure, such as negative of typical log-likelihoods, the resulting optimization problem follows the form of optimization problem \mathcal{P} . As we show below this is, in particular, the case when the deviance measure is a quadratic loss and the penalty is either SCAD or MCP. The quadratic loss plays the role of f . The other two functions, i.e. h and χ are specified for both SCAD and MCP penalties. Define

$$p_{\lambda,a,\text{SCAD}}(\boldsymbol{\beta}) = \chi(\boldsymbol{\beta}) + h_{\text{SCAD}}(\boldsymbol{\beta}), \quad (4.1)$$

$$p_{\lambda,\gamma,\text{MCP}}(\boldsymbol{\beta}) = \chi(\boldsymbol{\beta}) + h_{\text{MCP}}(\boldsymbol{\beta}); \quad (4.2)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\beta} := [\beta_0, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_q]^T$, $\chi(\boldsymbol{\beta}) = \sum_{j=1}^q \lambda |\beta_j|$, and

$$h_{\text{SCAD}}(\boldsymbol{\beta}) = \sum_{j=1}^q \begin{cases} 0; & |\beta_j| \leq \lambda \\ \frac{2\lambda|\beta_j| - \beta_j^2 - \lambda^2}{2(a-1)}; & \lambda < |\beta_j| < a\lambda \in \mathcal{C}_{L_{\text{SCAD}}}^{1,1} \\ \frac{1}{2}(a+1)\lambda^2 - \lambda|\beta_j|; & |\beta_j| \geq a\lambda \end{cases} \quad (4.3)$$

$$h_{\text{MCP}}(\boldsymbol{\beta}) = \sum_{j=1}^q \begin{cases} -\frac{\beta_j^2}{2\gamma}; & |\beta_j| < \gamma\lambda \in \mathcal{C}_{L_{\text{MCP}}}^{1,1} \\ \frac{1}{2}\gamma\lambda^2 - \lambda|\beta_j|; & |\beta_j| \geq \gamma\lambda \end{cases} \quad (4.4)$$

In the above equations, $\lambda > 0, a > 2, \gamma > 1$ are the penalty tuning parameters. It is trivial that, in (4.1) and (4.2), $\chi(\boldsymbol{\beta})$ is convex and the remaining term is a first-order smooth concave function. In view of the optimization problem \mathcal{P} , when applying SCAD/MCP on a convex $\mathcal{C}_{L_\ell}^{1,1}$ statistical learning objective function, $f = -2\ell$ will be the convex component; $h_{\text{SCAD}}, h_{\text{MCP}}$ will be the smooth nonconvex component with $L_{\text{SCAD}} = \frac{1}{a-1}$ and $L_{\text{MCP}} = \frac{1}{\gamma}$; and $\chi = \sum_{j=1}^q \lambda |\beta_j|$ will be the nonsmooth convex component. For high-dimensional statistical learning problems, the L-smoothness constant for the smooth nonconvex component, L_{SCAD} and L_{MCP} , are often negligible when compared to the greatest singular value of

the design matrix [Meckes, 2021]. In statistical learning applications, most unconstrained problems can, in fact, be reduced to problems over a bounded domain, as information often suggests the boundedness of the variables.

4.3 The Accelerated Gradient Algorithm

This Section comprises two subsections. Subsection 4.3.1 includes an algorithm proposed by Ghadimi and Lan [Ghadimi and Lan, 2015] for solving the composite optimization problem \mathcal{P} . In Subsection 4.3.2 we propose an approach for selecting the hyperparameters of the algorithm by minimizing the complexity upper bound (4.10)

4.3.1 Nonconvex Accelerated Gradient Method

Building on Nesterov’s AG algorithm, Ghadimi and Lan [Ghadimi and Lan, 2015] proposed the following algorithm for solving the composite optimization problem \mathcal{P} .

Algorithm 2 Accelerated Gradient Algorithm

Input: starting point $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{q+1}$, $\{\alpha_k\}$ s.t. $\alpha_1 = 1$ and $\forall k \geq 2, 0 < \alpha_k < 1, \{\omega_k > 0\}$, and $\{\delta_k > 0\}$

Output: Minimizer x_N^{md}

0. Set $x_0^{ag} = x_0$ and $k = 1$

1. Set

$$x_k^{md} = \alpha_k x_{k-1}^{ag} + (1 - \alpha_k) x_{k-1} \quad (4.5)$$

2. Compute $\nabla\Psi(x_k^{md})$ and set

$$x_k = \begin{cases} x_{k-1} - \delta_k \nabla\Psi(x_k^{md}) & \text{(smooth)} \\ \mathcal{P}(x_{k-1}, \nabla\Psi(x_k^{md}), \delta_k) & \text{(composite)} \end{cases} \quad (4.6)$$

$$x_k^{ag} = \begin{cases} x_k^{md} - \omega_k \nabla\Psi(x_k^{md}) & \text{(smooth)} \\ \mathcal{P}(x_k^{md}, \nabla\Psi(x_k^{md}), \omega_k) & \text{(composite)} \end{cases} \quad (4.7)$$

3. Set $k = k + 1$ and go to step 1

In Algorithm 2, “smooth” represents the updating formulas for smooth problems, and “composite” represents the update formulas for composite problems, and \mathcal{P} is the proximal oper-

ator defined as:

$$\mathcal{P}(x, y, c) := \arg \min_{u \in \mathbb{R}^{q+1}} \left\{ \langle y, u \rangle + \frac{1}{2c} \|u - x\|^2 + \chi(u) \right\}.$$

It is evident that the composite counter-part of the algorithm is the Moreau envelope smoothing of the simple nonconvex function; for this reason, in later analysis of the algorithm, we will use smooth updating formulas for the sake of parsimony. As an interpretation of the algorithm, $\{\alpha_k\}$ controls the damping of the system, and ω_k controls the step size for the “gradient correction” update for momentum method. In what follows, Γ_k is defined recursively as:

$$\Gamma_k := \begin{cases} 1, & k = 1; \\ (1 - \alpha_k) \Gamma_{k-1}, & k \geq 2. \end{cases}$$

Ghadimi and Lan [Ghadimi and Lan, 2015] proved that under the following conditions:

$$\alpha_k \delta_k \leq \omega_k < \frac{1}{L_\Psi}, \quad \forall k = 1, 2, \dots, N-1 \text{ and} \quad (4.8)$$

$$\frac{\alpha_1}{\delta_1 \Gamma_1} \geq \frac{\alpha_2}{\delta_2 \Gamma_2} \geq \dots \geq \frac{\alpha_N}{\delta_N \Gamma_N}, \quad (4.9)$$

the rate of convergence for composite optimization problems can be illustrated by the following complexity upper bound:

$$\begin{aligned} & \min_{k=1, \dots, N} \left\| \mathcal{G}(x_k^{md}, \nabla \Psi(x_k^{md}), \omega_k) \right\|^2 \\ & \leq \left[\sum_{k=1}^N \Gamma_k^{-1} \omega_k (1 - L_\Psi \omega_k) \right]^{-1} \left[\frac{\|x_0 - x^*\|^2}{\delta_1} + \frac{2L_h}{\Gamma_N} (\|x^*\|^2 + M^2) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (4.10)$$

In the above inequality, $\mathcal{G}(x_k^{md}, \nabla \Psi(x_k^{md}), \omega_k)$ is the analogue to the gradient for smooth functions defined by:

$$\mathcal{G}(x, y, c) := \frac{1}{c} [x - \mathcal{P}(x, y, c)].$$

In accelerated gradient settings, x corresponds to the past iteration, y corresponds to the smooth gradient at x , and c corresponds to the step size taken.

4.3.2 Hyperparameters for Nonconvex Accelerated Gradient Method

Here we discuss how hyperparameters, α_k , ω_k and δ_k can be selected to accelerate convergence of Algorithm 2 by minimizing the complexity upper bound. From Lemma 19, it is clear that the conditions (4.8) and (4.9) merely present a lower bound for the vanishing rate of $\{\alpha_k\}$. We also observe that the right-hand side of (B.1) is monotonically increasing with respect to α_k ; thus, to obtain the maximum values for $\{\alpha_k\}$, it is sufficient to maximize α_k recursively.

Using (4.5), (4.6), and (4.7), we have

$$\frac{x_{k+1}^{md} - (1 - \alpha_{k+1})x_k^{ag}}{\alpha_{k+1}} = \frac{x_k^{md} - (1 - \alpha_k)x_{k-1}^{ag}}{\alpha_k} - \delta_k \nabla \Psi(x_k^{md}) \quad \text{and}$$

$$x_k^{ag} = x_k^{md} - \omega_k \nabla \Psi(x_k^{md}).$$

By sorting out the terms in the above equations, we obtain the following updating formulas:

$$x_k^{ag} = x_k^{md} - \omega_k \nabla \Psi(x_k^{md}) \tag{4.11}$$

$$x_{k+1}^{md} = x_k^{ag} + \alpha_{k+1} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_k} - \frac{\delta_k}{\omega_k} \right) \cdot (\omega_k \nabla \Psi(x_k^{md})) + \alpha_{k+1} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_k} - 1 \right) (x_k^{ag} - x_{k-1}^{ag}) \tag{4.12}$$

Compared to Nesterov’s AG, the AG method proposed by Ghadimi and Lan differs by the convergence conditions (4.8) and (4.9), and the inclusion of the term $\alpha_{k+1} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_k} - \frac{\delta_k}{\omega_k} \right) \cdot (\omega_k \nabla \Psi(x_k^{md}))$ in (4.12). Since $\alpha_{k+1} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_k} - \frac{\delta_k}{\omega_k} \right) \geq 0$ is implied by convergence condition (4.8), this added term functions as a step to reduce the magnitude of “gradient correction” presented in (4.11): the resulting framework will keep the same momentum compared to Nesterov’s AG, but the momentum step update will occur at a midpoint between x_k^{ag} and

x_k^{md} to yield x_{k+1}^{md} . Such a framework suggests that the proposed algorithm is merely a midpoint generalization in the gradient correction step of Nesterov’s AG. Therefore, *the acceleration occurs to the convex component f of the objective function Ψ* . Following this intuition, we proceed to investigate the optimization hyperparameter settings for the most accelerating effect in Theorem 1 based on the idea of minimizing the complexity upper bound (4.10) when the objective function is convex; i.e., when $h \equiv 0$.

It can be deduced from (B.1) that an increasing sequence of $\{\delta_k\}$ allows a slower vanishing rate for $\{\alpha_k\}$. Specifically, the existence of δ_1 in (4.10) can be explained as the following: the momentum initialization step in Algorithm 2 indicates that $x_1^{md} = x_0^{ag} = x_0$. We also have $x_1^{ag} = x_1^{md} - \omega_1 \nabla \Psi(x_1^{md}) = x_0^{ag} - \omega_1 \nabla \Psi(x_0)$ for smooth problems or $x_1^{ag} = \mathcal{P}(x_1^{md}, \nabla \Psi(x_1^{md}), \omega_1) = \mathcal{P}(x_0^{ag}, \nabla \Psi(x_0), \omega_1)$ for composite problems. In view of (4.12), the momentum initializes as $x_1^{ag} - x_0^{ag} = -\omega_1 \nabla \Psi(x_0)$ for smooth problems. Thus, should $\delta_1 < \omega_1$ take a smaller value, $\alpha_2 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_1} - \frac{\delta_1}{\omega_1}\right) > 0$; i.e., x_2^{md} is a convex combination of x_1^{ag} and the initial point x_0 , and the smaller δ_1 is, the closer x_2^{md} is to x_0 . Meanwhile, a smaller δ_1 allows a faster increasing sequence $\{\delta_k\}$; hence a slower-vanishing sequence $\{\alpha_k\}$ can be achieved to incorporate more momentum. This process can be interpreted as follows: when x_2^{md} does not retain the full step update from the initial point x_0 , more initial momentum will be allowed to accumulate, as the initial momentum is in the same direction as the update. We therefore choose $\delta_1 = \omega_1$; i.e., to let x_2^{md} retain fully the update from x_0 in the direction of $-\omega_1 \nabla \Psi(x_0)$, such that no *excess* initial momentum will be needed to account for initial update deficiency in this direction.

4.4 Theoretical Analysis of the Algorithm

For gradient methods without a line-search procedure, the step size for the gradient correction is usually set to be a constant. Based on this convention, we assume $\omega_k = \beta$ for $k = 1, 2, \dots, N$. Theorem 1 below presents the optimal choice of hyperparameters under mild

conditions.

THEOREM 1. Assume conditions (4.8) and (4.9) hold. Let $\delta_1 = \omega_k = \omega$ and $h = 0$. Then the complexity upper bound (4.10) is minimized by:

$$\bar{\alpha}_{k+1} = \frac{2}{1 + \sqrt{1 + \frac{4}{\bar{\alpha}_k^2}}}, \quad \bar{\alpha}_1 = 1, \quad (4.13)$$

$$\bar{\delta}_{k+1} = \frac{\bar{\omega}}{\bar{\alpha}_{k+1}}, \quad (4.14)$$

$$\bar{\omega} = \frac{2}{3L_\Psi}. \quad (4.15)$$

Proof. See Appendix B.1.1. □

As illustrated by the proof of the above theorem, the optimization hyperparameter settings (4.13), (4.14), and (4.15) allow for the greatest values of $\{\alpha_k\}$ under the constant gradient-correction step size and maximum initial update assumptions; i.e., condition 1. Such settings allow the most acceleration for the convex component. Although a greater momentum will result in a much faster convergence at the initial stage of the algorithm, it will also result in oscillations of larger magnitudes near the minimizer. Therefore, in the following theorem, we will show that the complexity upper bound will always maintain $O(1/N)$ rate of convergence. This observation implies that the accelerated gradient method’s worst-case scenario is at least as good as $O(1/N)$ for gradient descent in terms of the rate of convergence.

THEOREM 2. Assume conditions (4.8) and (4.9) hold. Then under the assumptions of Theorem 1, the complexity upper bound is $O(1/N)$.

Proof. See Appendix B.1.2. □

The recursive formula for optimal momentum hyperparameter, $\{\alpha_k\}$, as presented in (4.13), is of a rather complicated structure. The next theorem illustrates the vanishing rate of $\{\alpha_k\}$.

THEOREM 3. Let $\bar{\alpha}_1 = 1$ and (4.13) holds. Then

$$\frac{2}{(1 + a \cdot k^{-b})k + 1} < \bar{\alpha}_k \leq \frac{2}{k + 1}, \quad k = 1, \dots, N, \quad (4.16)$$

for any $a > 0$, $0 < b < 1$, such that

$$a(1 - b) \cdot 2^{2-b} - ab(1 - b) \cdot 2^{-b} - 1 \geq 0. \quad (4.17)$$

Proof. See Appendix B.1.3. □

The following corollary establishes a tight bound for the damping sequence, hence providing the speed of convergence of our proposed optimal damping sequence $\{\bar{\alpha}_k\}$ to $\frac{2}{k+1}$.

COROLLARY 4. The lower bound in (4.16) is maximized at

$$\bar{a}_k = \frac{2^{\bar{b}_k}}{(1 - \bar{b}_k)(4 - \bar{b}_k)} \quad \text{and} \quad \bar{b}_k = \frac{2 + 5 \left(\log \frac{2}{k}\right) + \sqrt{9 \left(\log \frac{2}{k}\right)^2 + 4}}{2 \left(\log \frac{2}{k}\right)} \quad \text{for } k \geq 8.$$

The lower bound in (4.16) therefore becomes

$$\frac{k + 1}{2} - \bar{\alpha}_k^{-1} = O(\log k) \quad (4.18)$$

Proof. See Appendix B.1.4. □

To better illustrate Corollary 4, we plot the value of $\log(\bar{a}_k k^{-b})$ v.s. (k, b) in Figure 4.1. The plot shows that as k grows large, the optimizer \bar{b}_k converges to 1 at a very slow rate. It also reflects on the speed of $1 + \bar{a}_k \cdot k^{-\bar{b}_k}$, the coefficient of k in the denominator of the lower bound in (4.16), goes to 1 as k increases.

Figure 4.1: Numerical plots for Corollary 4. The figure plots $\log(\bar{a}_k k^{-b})$ v.s. k and b ; the red line plots its minimizer $\bar{b}_k = \frac{2+5(\log \frac{2}{k})+\sqrt{9(\log \frac{2}{k})^2+4}}{2(\log \frac{2}{k})}$ for each k . The plot reflects on the speed for the coefficient of k in the denominator of the lower bound in (4.16) converges to 1. The red line shows that \bar{b}_k converges to 1 at an extremely slow rate.

4.5 Simulation Studies

In this section, we conduct two sets of simulation studies for nonconvex penalized linear and logistic models. We first visualize the convergence rates and signal recovery performance for each set of simulation studies using a single simulation replicate. Second, we compare the convergence rates across the first-order methods with varying q/n ratios and covariate correlations for 100 simulation replications. Lastly, we compare the signal recovery performance using our method to the state-of-the-art method, `ncvreg` [Breheny and Huang,

2011], with varying covariate correlations and Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) for 100 simulation replications. Since the iterative complexity differs for the first-order methods and coordinate descent methods, the convergence rates in terms of the number of iterations are not directly comparable. Thus, we choose to compare the computing time between AG, proximal gradient descent, and coordinate descent.

4.5.1 Simulation Setup

Linear models with the OLS loss function is a popular method for modelling a continuous response. We aim to achieve signal recovery by solving the following problem for penalized linear models:

$$\arg \min_{\boldsymbol{\beta} \in \mathbb{R}^{q+1}} \frac{1}{2n} \|\mathbf{X}\boldsymbol{\beta} - \mathbf{y}\|_2^2 + \sum_{j=1}^q p_\lambda(\beta_j),$$

where $p_\lambda : \mathbb{R} \mapsto \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ is the SCAD or MCP penalty function. To compare the convergence rates across the first-order methods, we choose different q/n ratios and the strength of correlation, τ , between the covariates. These two parameters are most likely to impact the convergence rates. Median and corresponding 95% bootstrap confidence intervals from 1000 bootstrap replications for the number of iterations required for the iterative objective values to make a fixed amount of descent are reported. To compare the signal recovery performance between our AG method and the state-of-the-art package `ncvreg`, we performed 100 simulation replications with varying SNRs and covariate correlations, as they directly impact the signal recovery performance. The simulation studies we performed adapt the following setups:

- The total number of observations $n = 1000$ for visualization plots and signal recovery performance comparison, and $n = 200, 500, 1000, 3000$ for convergence rate and computing time comparisons.
- For visualization purposes, we perform one simulation replicate with the number of covariates $q = 2004$, with 4 nonzero signals being 2, -2, 8, -8. We perform 100 simula-

tion replications with the number of covariates $q = 2050$, with 5 blocks of true signals equal-spaced with 500 zeros in-between for convergence rate and computing time comparison, as well as signal recovery performance comparison. For each simulation replicate, the blocks of the “true” signals are simulated from $N_{10}(0.5, 1)$, $N_{10}(5, 2)$, $N_{10}(10, 3)$, $N_{10}(20, 4)$, $N_{10}(50, 5)$, respectively.

- The design matrix, \mathbf{X} , is simulated from a multivariate Gaussian distribution with mean 0. The covariance matrix Σ is a τ -Toeplitz matrix, where $\tau = 0.5$ for the visualization plots and $\tau = 0.1, 0.5, 0.9$ for the convergence rate and computing time comparison, as well as signal recovery performance comparison. All covariates are standardized; i.e., centered by the sample mean and scaled by the sample standard deviation.
- The signal-to-noise ratio is set as $\text{SNR} = \frac{\sqrt{\beta_{\text{true}}^T \Sigma \beta_{\text{true}}}}{\sigma}$, where β_{true} are the “true” coefficient values, and σ is used as the residual standard deviation. $\text{SNR} = 5$ for visualization plots, $\text{SNR} = 3$ for convergence rate comparison, and $\text{SNR} = 1, 3, 7, 10$ for signal recovery performance comparison.
- For visualization plots, convergence rate and computing time comparisons, we take $\lambda = 0.5, a = 3.7$ for SCAD and $\lambda = 0.5, \gamma = 3$ for MCP, unless otherwise specified. For signal recovery rate comparison, λ sequence consists of 50 values equal-spaced from λ_{\max}^1 to 0. The tuning parameter λ is chosen to minimize the (non-penalized) loss function value on a validation set of the same size as the training set.
- For signal recovery performance comparison, we use the same objective function as `ncvreg` to ensure that the same value of penalty tuning parameters results in the same degree of penalization. We also adapt the same strong rule setup as `ncvreg` [Lee and Breheny, 2015].

To compare the gradient-based methods and the coordinate descent method, we compare

¹ λ_{\max} is the minimal value for λ such that all penalized coefficients are estimated as 0.

the computing time when both coded in Python/CuPy. The coordinate descent method was coded based on the state-of-the-art pseudo-code [Breheny and Huang, 2011]. All of the computing was carried out on a NVIDIA A100 GPU with CUDA compute capability of 8.0 on the Narval computing cluster from Calcul Quèbec/Compute Canada. Furthermore, we also excluded the computation of the L-smoothness parameter for the coordinate descent method in our simulations.

The simulation setups for penalized logistic models are similar to those above for penalized linear models, except that the active coefficients are set differently to account for the exponential scale inherent to the logistic regression. For the single-replicate visualization simulations, we let the 4 nonzero signals be 0.5, -0.5 , 0.8, -0.8 . For the simulations with 100 replications to compare the convergence rate and signal recovery performance, we simulate the 5 blocks of the “true” signals from $N_{10}(0.5, 1)$, $N_{10}(0.5, 1)$, $N_{10}(-0.5, 1)$, $N_{10}(-0.5, 1)$, $N_{10}(1, 1)$, respectively. The SNR for logistic regression has the same definition as linear models, with Gaussian noise added to the generated continuous predictor $\mathbf{X}\boldsymbol{\beta}_{true}$. The binary outcomes are independent Bernoulli realizations, with probabilities being the logistic transforms of the continuous response.

4.5.2 Simulation Results

Penalized Linear Regression

Figure 4.2 shows the log differences of iterative objective values for a single replicate. This figure visualizes the accelerating effect of the AG method using our proposed hyperparameter settings. Median with the corresponding 95% bootstrap CI of the number of iterations required for the iterative objective function values to make a fixed amount of descent for 100 simulation replications are reported in Figures B.1, B.2 in Appendix B.2.1. The lack of bars in the reported barplots indicates that the median of 100 replications breaks down; i.e., the corresponding proximal gradient algorithm fails to converge to the minimizer found by the

Figure 4.2: Convergence rate performance of first-order methods on SCAD (left) and MCP (right) penalized linear model for a single simulation replicate. k represents the number of iterations, g_k represents the iterative objective function value, and g^* represents the minimum found by the three methods considered.

three algorithms within 2000 iterations. The AG method using our hyperparameter settings converges much faster than proximal gradient and AG using the original hyperparameter settings proposed by Ghadimi and Lan for both SCAD and MCP-penalized models discussed here, as reflected in Figures 4.2, B.1, B.2. It can also be observed that momentum methods such as AG are much less likely to be stuck at saddle points or local minimizers than proximal gradient – this property is consistent with previous findings [Jin et al., 2017]. Since the proposed AG methods belong to the class of momentum methods, the AG algorithms do not possess a descent property. As suggested by a previous study [Su et al., 2014], oscillation will occur at the end of the trajectory; the descent property will therefore vanish. This is also reflected in Figures 4.2, 4.5 – as the trajectory moves close to the optimizer, the oscillation will start to occur for the AG methods. Among all the first-order methods, the AG method with our proposed hyperparameter settings tends to converge the fastest in all scenarios considered, as illustrated by Figures B.1, B.2 in Appendix B.2.1. The observed standard errors among 100 simulation replications are rather small, suggesting that the halting time retains predictable for high-dimensional models, which agrees with the recent findings [Paquette et al., 2020].

Figures B.3, B.4 report median with the corresponding 95% bootstrap CI of the computing time (in seconds) required for the infinity norm of the two consecutive iterations $\|\beta^{(k+1)} - \beta^{(k)}\|_\infty$ to fall below 10^{-4} for 100 simulation replications. It can be observed that the computing time for AG with suggested settings is much shorter than the computing time for coordinate descent.

Figure 4.3: Solution paths obtained using the proposed AG method for MCP-penalized linear model with different values of γ for a single simulation replicate. The behaviors of the solution path match the expected from the MCP penalized problems. The solution path behaves similarly to hard-thresholding for a small γ . As γ increases, the solution path will behave more similarly to soft-thresholding.

To visualize the signal recovery performance using our proposed method, Figure 4.3 plots the solution paths for the MCP-penalized linear model with different values of γ . The grey lines in Figure 4.3 represent the recovered values for the noise variables. AG method performs very well when applied to signal recovery problems for nonconvex-penalized linear models. Figure 4.3 serves as an arbitrary instance that the recovered signals using our method exhibit the expected pattern with MCP – as λ decreases, the degree of penalization

decreases, and more false-positive signals will be selected. The stable solution path for the recovered signals suggests that the algorithm does not converge to a point far away from the “true” coefficients.

Figure 4.4: Sample means for Positive/Negative Predictive Values (PPV, NPV) of signal detection across different values of covariates correlation (τ) and SNRs for AG with our proposed hyperparameter settings and `ncvreg` on SCAD-penalized linear model over 100 simulation replications. The error bars represent the standard errors.

To further illustrate the signal recovery performance, the means and standard errors for the scaled estimation error $\frac{\|\beta_{\text{true}} - \hat{\beta}\|_2^2}{\|\beta_{\text{true}}\|_2^2}$, positive/negative predictive values (PPV, NPV), and active set cardinality across 100 replications are reported in Tables B.1 and B.2 in Appendix B.2.1. In what follows, \mathcal{A} denotes the set of nonzero “true” coefficients and $\hat{\mathcal{A}}$ denotes the set of nonzero coefficients selected by the model. PPV and NPV use the following definitions:

$$\text{PPV} := \frac{|\mathcal{A} \cap \hat{\mathcal{A}}|}{|\hat{\mathcal{A}}|}, \quad \text{NPV} := \frac{|\mathcal{A}^c \cap \hat{\mathcal{A}}^c|}{|\hat{\mathcal{A}}^c|}.$$

Sample means and standard errors for PPV and NPV from Table B.1 are further visualized in

Figure 4.4. When applied to sparse learning problems, the signal recovery performance of our proposed method often outperforms `ncvreg`, the current state-of-the-art method [Breheny and Huang, 2011], particularly in terms of the positive predictive values (PPV). This can be observed from Figure 4.4 and Tables B.1, B.2 from Appendix B.2.1. This observation is especially evident when the signal-to-noise ratios are low. At the same time, $\|\beta_{\text{true}} - \hat{\beta}\|_2^2 / \|\beta_{\text{true}}\|_2^2$ for both methods are close. As the SNR increases, the validation set becomes more similar to the training set, causing the chosen model to have a smaller λ . The model size will therefore increase, which will decrease the value of PPV.

Penalized Logistic Regression

Figure 4.5: Convergence rate performance of first-order methods on SCAD (left) and MCP (right) penalized logistic regression for a single simulation replicate. k represents the number of iterations, g_k represents the iterative objective function value, and g^* represent the minimum found by the three methods considered.

The simulation results reflected in Figures 4.5, 4.6, as well as Figures B.5, B.6 and Tables B.3, B.4 in Appendix B.2.2 suggest similar findings for penalized logistic models to our findings for penalized linear models as discussed in Section 4.5.2. We further note that when applied to penalized logistic models, the coordinate descent method often fails to converge, resulting in overall poor performance in positive predictive values as reflected in Figure 4.7 and Tables B.3, B.4 in Appendix B.2.2. When it does converge, the coordinate descent method does so at a very slow rate. In comparison, our proposed method has a convergence guarantee

Figure 4.6: Solution paths obtained using the proposed AG method for MCP-penalized logistic regression with different values of γ for a single simulation replicate. The behaviors of the solution path match the expected from the MCP penalized problems. The solution path behaves similarly to hard-thresholding for a small γ . As γ increases, the solution path will behave more similarly to soft-thresholding.

in theory and converges within a reasonable number of iterations in our simulation studies, as shown in Figures B.1, B.2 in Appendix B.2.2. In our computing time comparison, we used identical simulation setups and convergence standard for both the AG method and coordinate descent method, running both on a NVIDIA A100 GPU with CUDA compute capability of 8.0 from Compute Canada; the submitted simulation job finished well within 20 minutes for both SCAD and MCP-penalized logistic models when using the AG method, but exceeded the 7-day computing time limit imposed on the Narval cluster when using the coordinate descent method.

Figure 4.7: Sample means for Positive/Negative Predictive Values (PPV, NPV) of signal detection across different values of covariates correlation (τ) and SNRs for AG with our proposed hyperparameter settings and `ncvreg` on SCAD-penalized logistic model over 100 simulation replications. The error bars represent the standard error.

4.6 Discussion

We considered a recently developed generalization of Nesterov’s accelerated gradient method for nonconvex optimization, and we have discussed its potential in sparse statistical learning with nonconvex penalties. An important issue concerning this algorithm is the selection of its sequences of hyperparameters. We present an explicit solution to this problem by minimizing the algorithm’s complexity upper bound, hence accelerating convergence of the algorithm. Our simulation studies indicate that among first-order methods, the AG method using our proposed hyperparameter settings achieves a convergence rate considerably faster than other first-order methods such as the AG method using the original proposed hyperparameter settings or proximal gradient. Our simulations also show that signal recovery using our proposed method generally outperforms `ncvreg`, the current state-of-the-art method. This

performance gain is much more pronounced for penalized linear models when the signal-to-noise ratios are low. For penalized logistic regression, the performance gain observed is consistent across various covariates correlation and signal-to-noise ratio settings. Compared to coordinate-wise minimization methods, our proposed method is less challenged by low signal-to-noise ratios and is feasible to implement in parallel. Given today’s computing facilities, parallel computing is particularly meaningful for large datasets [Parnell et al., 2020]. We also show this gain in parallel computing performance by comparing computing time on a GPU. Furthermore, our proposed method has weaker convergence conditions and can be applied to a class of problems that do not have an explicit solution to the coordinate-wise objective function. For example, linear mixed models for grouped or longitudinal data involve the inverse of a large covariance matrix. Decomposition of this covariance matrix is necessary to apply the coordinate descent method. However, such decomposition can be computationally costly and numerically unstable [Quarteroni et al., 2007]. On the other hand, matrix decomposition is not needed for first-order methods, as numerically stable yet computationally efficient approaches such as conjugate gradient can be adapted when applying our proposed method. The proposed nonconvex AG method can be applied to a wide range of statistical learning problems, opening various future research opportunities in statistical machine learning and statistical genetics.

4.7 Disclaimer

All codes to reproduce the simulation results of this paper and outputs from Calcul Québec/Compute Canada can be found on the following GitHub repository:

<https://github.com/Kaiyangshi-Ito/nonconvexAG>

Chapter 5

Tsallis Entropy Maximizing Distributions for Robust and Efficient Sparse Learning on Correlated Data

Preamble to Manuscript 3.

Introduction to the Study and Its Place in the Workflow:

Manuscript 3 explores the critical limitations of Gaussian assumptions often made in statistical models, particularly those used to analyze correlated and heterogeneous data typical in biostatistical applications. By proposing the use of the q Gaussian distribution, derived from Tsallis entropy maximization, this manuscript introduces a robust alternative capable of accommodating the correlated observations often inherent in biostatistical data, such as genetic and longitudinal studies. This novel approach significantly enhances the flexibility and robustness of statistical models, making it an invaluable addition to the techniques

developed in the previous manuscripts.

Building on Optimization and Computational Advances:

This manuscript extends the efficient computational methodologies refined in Manuscripts 1 and 2 by integrating them into a broader modeling context that includes correlated observations. After establishing efficient variable screening and optimization techniques for sparse learning, the introduction of a new modeling framework that can effectively handle correlations and heterogeneities addresses the next layer of complexity in the analysis of high-dimensional data. The q Gaussian model not only offers a solution to the robustness issues posed by the underlying distributional assumptions and heavy tails, but also fits within the computational framework previously developed.

Innovation in Statistical Modeling and Optimization:

The framework for adapting numerical methods originally designed to find equilibria in flows to tackle composite optimization problems presents a novel approach to address the challenges of statistical computing in sparse learning. This methodology ensures that the models developed are not only theoretically sound but also practically applicable.

Enhancing Data Analysis in Biostatistics:

By applying the innovative framework mentioned above to the Hager–Zhang conjugate gradient algorithm, Manuscript 3 develops a numerically stable and computationally efficient algorithm for sparse statistical learning. This advancement is crucial for efficiently processing high-dimensional large datasets that biostatistics often deals with. The robustness offered by the q Gaussian distribution transforms the landscape of statistical machine learning, making it more robust, hence better suited to the nuanced challenges posed by high-dimensional biostatistical data with correlated observations.

Integration with Previous Manuscripts:

Manuscript 3 synthesizes and builds on the computational and methodological foundations laid in the first two manuscripts. The variable screening from Manuscript 1 ensures that the most relevant variables are identified for robust modeling, while the optimization techniques from Manuscript 2 provide an efficient optimization algorithm to handle the statistical computing challenges introduced by the q Gaussian modeling of high-dimensional data. Together, these manuscripts create a comprehensive workflow for handling high-dimensional biostatistical data, from initial robust screening and modeling of complex data structures to efficient statistical computing algorithms.

Tsallis Entropy Maximizing Distributions for Robust and Efficient Sparse Learning on Correlated Data

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Abstract

This paper addresses the limitations of Gaussian distribution assumptions in statistical sparse learning, particularly in modeling correlated and heterogeneous data. Conventional Gaussian models often lack robustness towards outliers and underlying distribution assumptions. To overcome these limitations, we propose the use of the q Gaussian distribution, derived from Tsallis entropy maximization, as a robust alternative. This is notably relevant in biostatistics, where the presence of correlated observations and heterogeneity, such as in genetic and longitudinal studies, is prevalent. Our contributions include modeling of correlated data through the re-derived multivariate probability density function from Tsallis entropy maximization, thereby addressing the limitations inherent in conventional Gaussian models. Furthermore, we introduce a novel framework that adapts numerical methods designed for finding equilibria in flows to tackle composite optimization problems prevalent in statistical sparse learning. Applying this framework to the Hager-Zhang conjugate gradient algorithm [Hager and Zhang, 2005], we develop a numerically stable and efficient algorithm for sparse statistical learning. The q Gaussian distribution, informed by the principle of maximizing Tsallis entropy, presents a viable and flexible alternative to Gaussian-based methods, potentially transforming the landscape of statistical machine learning. This paper not only contributes to the theoretical understanding of statistical distributions and optimization techniques, but also paves the way for practical data analysis in biostatistics and related fields.

5.1 Introduction

In the realm of statistical sparse learning, the pursuit of robust and efficient methodologies remains paramount, especially when confronted with the complexities of correlated data. The principle of maximizing Shannon’s entropy stands as a pivotal framework that has led to the derivation of nearly all frequently utilized statistical distributions to date [Cover and Thomas, 2006]. This principle’s application has notably revealed that the multivariate Gaussian distribution maximizes Shannon’s entropy under first moment and second central moment constraints, significantly influencing the landscape of statistical sparse learning. The Gaussian assumption has become a fundamental cornerstone of numerous statistical sparse learning problem formulations, and its core assumptions are rarely re-examined or challenged.

However, the Gaussian distribution’s features, particularly its exponential tail decay and the absence of a shape parameter, can present substantial limitations. Specifically, the lack of robustness towards outliers and a limited capacity to accurately represent the distribution’s shape results in violations of the Gaussian assumption in statistical modeling. Such violations have many practical repercussions, including the potential for erroneous Type I error rates and the lack of robustness towards distribution shape when estimating the dispersion parameter, motivating the development of alternative approaches.

Dispersion or volatility parameters encapsulate critical and often decisive information about distributions. Their estimations, specifically in transformations of predicted outcomes, are often indispensable. For instance, in the context of log-normal distributions, the mean is directly influenced by the volatility parameter derived from the underlying Gaussian distribution. Likewise, principles like the Law of the Unconscious Statistician (LOTUS), which rely on accurate estimation of volatility and precise understanding of the distribution’s shape, highlight the importance of determining this parameter for dependable prediction and statistical modeling.

Volatility estimation is of great importance in finance. Specifically, Itos lemma, often used in stochastic calculus for option pricing, explicitly highlights the importance of volatility’s contribution. Delving into the realm of stochastic calculus, Ito’s lemma provides a mathematical framework that elegantly captures volatility’s impact on dynamic systems. Ito’s lemma states that for a twice-differentiable function f ,

$$df(t, X_t) = \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial t} + \mu \frac{\partial f}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial x^2} \right) dt + \sigma \frac{\partial f}{\partial x} dW_t, \quad (5.1)$$

where the term $\sigma^2 \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial x^2}$ specifically denotes the contribution of volatility to changes in the function f . This mathematical representation is pivotal in finance, where the phenomenon, termed *volatility smile*, challenges the foundational assumptions of the Black–Scholes–Merton (BSM) model, signaling empirical deviations from expected normality in option pricing models. These deviations have propelled the exploration of alternative distributions capable of more accurately reflecting market realities [Peña et al., 1999].

In response to these limitations of Gaussian distributions, the q Gaussian distribution, derived from maximizing Tsallis entropy, emerges as a compelling alternative. The q Gaussian distribution is celebrated for its flexibility in modeling the diverse shapes of bell-curved distributions, including the ability to account for heavy-tailed distributions — a feature crucial for the robust modeling of financial returns. It provides a more accurate representation of financial returns on platforms such as the *New York Stock Exchange (NYSE)* and *National Association of Securities Dealers Automated Quotations (NSDAQ)* [Borland, 2002a,0, Domingo et al., 2017]. Despite its proven advantages in finance, the incorporation of Tsallis entropy-maximizing distributions within the domain of statistical sparse learning and biostatistics remains limited. To the best of our knowledge, this paper represents the initial endeavor to apply Tsallis entropy-maximizing distributions for biostatistical data modeling. Correlated observations, frequently encountered in genetic and longitudinal studies [Garcia and Marder, 2017, Runcie and Crawford, 2019, Dandine-Roulland and Perdry, 2015], as

well as heterogeneity of the variance, will be specifically addressed by our proposed Tsallis entropy-maximizing model for correlated data.

Hence, this paper advocates for the application of the q Gaussian distribution in modeling correlated data within sparse statistical learning frameworks. Our approach relaxes the conventional reliance on normality assumptions; We aim to demonstrate that the intricate characteristics of q Gaussian distributions can profoundly enhance the modeling of correlated data, offering a robust and versatile alternative to conventional Gaussian-based methods.

Maximum likelihood estimation is one of the most commonly used estimation techniques. However, the estimation process encounters notable computational obstacles when dealing with high-dimensional and extra-large datasets. Oracle penalties, favored for their efficacy in facilitating variable selection, present an attractive yet complex solution to sparse learning problems. However, oracle penalties are notable for their nonconvex and nonsmooth nature [Nikolova, 2000], which lead to considerable optimization challenges. Recently, proximal methods have demonstrated an unmatched speed of convergence, thereby surpassing most other approaches in efficiently handling estimation in nonsmooth problems [Hoheisel et al., 2020]. Simultaneously, the Krylov subspace method, recognized among the top ten algorithms for computing in science and engineering of the twentieth century, lays a solid foundation for numerical analysis. The conjugate gradient method, a prominent member of the Krylov subspace methods, has been applied extensively in various areas and is a fundamental numerical tool in solving partial differential equations [Nocedal et al., 2000]. While the nonlinear conjugate gradient performs exceptionally well in terms of its convergence speed and numerical stability, much better than accelerated gradient or gradient descent, its global convergence depends on the line-search step, whereas the accelerated gradient and gradient descent methods do not necessarily require the line search step to achieve global convergence [Ghadimi and Lan, 2015, Yang et al., 2024]. Motivated by these methodologies,

our paper introduces a proximal conjugate gradient method that can be applied to solve q Gaussian sparse learning problems. This method aims to effectively combine the theoretical strengths of both proximal methods and Krylov subspace techniques. Additionally, our paper addresses the line search step needed for the proximal nonlinear conjugate gradient method to establish global convergence.

We re-derive the probability density function for the multivariate q Gaussian distribution from a Tsallis entropy maximizing perspective in Lemma 5. This derivation allows for a nuanced understanding and application of this model in statistical analysis. Furthermore, *our contributions in this paper are as following:*

1. *We apply the derived density to model correlated and heterogeneous data effectively, while carrying out the sparse statistical learning at the same time.*
2. *Sparse statistical learning involves minimizing a composite optimization problem, aimed at minimizing a composite objective function composed of a globally Lipschitz-smooth term, which may be nonconvex, and a convex nonsmooth term. A variety of numerical methods are available to find equilibrium points for globally Lipschitz flows. By employing the Moreau envelope and linearizing the smooth term, we develop a framework that allows any numerical method designed for finding equilibrium points in globally Lipschitz flows to be adapted into a numerical optimization algorithm for minimizing the composite objective function.*
3. *Leveraging the framework introduced above, we implement it with the state-of-the-art Hager-Zhang conjugate gradient method [Hager and Zhang, 2005]. This implementation yields a proximal conjugate gradient algorithm that is not only computationally efficient but also numerically stable, suitable for a wide range of statistical sparse learning challenges. This includes the robust sparse learning approach we devised based on the concept of maximizing the Tsallis entropy distribution.*

The structure of the paper is organized as follows:

Section 5.2 delves into the foundational properties of Tsallis entropy, drawing upon previous literature to establish a comprehensive background. Following this, Section 5.3 introduces the concept of q -moments. This section then elaborates on employing Tsallis entropy maximizing distribution to effectively model the q -correlation structure. In Section 5.3, we also re-derive the probability density function maximizing Tsallis entropy under the first and second central q -moment constraints, incorporating all relevant parameters for a likelihood-based approach to statistical analysis.

Our discussion transitions to the challenges and strategies of optimization in Section 5.4. This section is twofold; initially, in Section 5.4.1, we present essential background knowledge from variational and nonsmooth analysis. This foundation is critical for our novel contribution: the development of a proximal framework to transform any first-order numerical optimization algorithm to a proximal counterpart by leveraging the properties of the Moreau envelope, detailed in Section 5.4.2. In Section 5.4.3, we apply this innovative framework to the state-of-the-art Hager-Zhang conjugate gradient algorithm. This adaptation produces a proximal version for tackling sparse statistical learning challenges. The efficacy of this method is further showcased in Section 5.5, where we outline the application of our proximal Hager-Zhang conjugate gradient algorithm to optimize a penalized q Gaussian likelihood function. This section also lays out a map from problem formulation to the practical aspects of prediction using models trained with our approach. Finally, Section 5.6 synthesizes our contributions, offering a reflective conclusion and proposing avenues for future research.

5.2 Tsallis Entropy

For an arbitrary random variable X , Shannon’s Entropy [Shannon, 1948] poses the definition

$$H(X) := -\mathbb{E} \log(p(X)) = - \int \log(p(x)) d\mu_X, \quad (5.2)$$

where p is the likelihood function for X . Over a given (likelihood) function space

$$\mathcal{P} := \left\{ p(x) \mid \forall x \in \mathcal{X}, p(x) \geq 0, |\mathbb{E} \log(p(X))| < \infty \text{ and } \int_{\mathcal{X}} 1 d\mu_X = 1 \right\},$$

the Shannon's entropy is a *strictly concave* function, which implies uniqueness of the maximizer. Many commonly-used distributions have been shown to maximize Shannon's entropy under certain given constraints [Cover and Thomas, 2006]. For example, uniform distribution, whether in discrete or continuous case, are to maximize (5.2) over a compact support, with open sets defined by discrete or Euclidean topology, respectively. The exponential distribution is defined as maximizing (5.2) over $\mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ and with a constraint that the first moment is a constant, $\frac{1}{\lambda}$; where λ later turns out to be the scale parameter. And the Gaussian distribution maximizes (5.2) over \mathbb{R} with given mean and variance. More examples can be given. For example, the constraint to obtain a Laplace distribution is a given mean absolute deviation, etc.

Additivity is a key element of Shannon's entropy. That is, let A_1, A_2 be two independent event sets, then the information of the intersection $I(\mathbb{P}(A_1 \cap A_2)) = I(\mathbb{P}(A_1) \cdot \mathbb{P}(A_2)) = I(\mathbb{P}(A_1)) + I(\mathbb{P}(A_2))$ — such homomorphism was considered particularly useful in Shannon's view [Shannon, 1948]. Later in the 1980s, Tsallis [1988] constructed an entropy similar to Shannon's entropy but without the additivity property. To see how Tsallis' entropy was developed, first we look at Tsallis' q -exponential function, which is defined as $\exp_q : \mathbb{R} \mapsto \mathbb{R}$, given by

$$\exp_q x := \begin{cases} ((1 + (1 - q)x))^{\frac{1}{1-q}}; & 1 + (1 - q)x > 0 \\ 0; & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (5.3)$$

For $q > 1$, \exp_q is bijective over $(0, \frac{1}{q-1})$. The inverse function, called the q -logarithmic function, is given by

$$\ln_q x := \frac{x^{1-q} - 1}{1 - q}. \quad (5.4)$$

Based on this deformed q -exponential function, Tsallis [1988] developed *Tsallis entropy* by replacing the log function in 5.2 with q -log function (5.4) and replacing the expectation with q -expectation operator [Tsallis, 1988]:

$$S_q(X) = - \int_{\mathcal{X}} p^q(x) \ln_q p(x) dx =: -\mathbb{E}_q \ln_q p(X) \quad (5.5)$$

$$= \frac{1}{q-1} \left(1 - \int_{\mathcal{X}} p^q(x) dx \right) \quad (5.6)$$

where $q \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{1\}$ is a constant, and $\mathbb{E}_q f(X) := \int_{\mathcal{X}} f(x) \cdot p^q(x) dx = \langle f(x), (d\mu_X)^q \rangle$ is referred to as the q -expectation operator. Tsallis entropy is also known as *non-extensive* entropy; namely for arbitrary independent two random variable X_1, X_2 :

$$S_q(X_1, X_2) = S_q(X_1) \oplus_q S_q(X_2), \quad (5.7)$$

where " \oplus_q " is defined as $\forall a, b \in \mathbb{R}$,

$$a \oplus_q b := a + b + (1 - q) ab. \quad (5.8)$$

Expectation has been used to characterize statistical distributions. However, one significant drawback of the expectation (linear) operator is the lack of continuity for some distributions; such as the Cauchy distribution. Therefore, the q -expectation operator, \mathbb{E}_q , provides robustness when characterizing the distributions in the real domain. If the tail of the function vanishes at a rate of $O((\log x)^{-1})$, the function will not have a proper integral if the support is unbounded. Thus, for any distribution whose likelihood function is bounded in uniform norm, $\exists q \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ such that \mathbb{E}_q is continuous at the likelihood function in the function space we are considering.

5.3 Tsallis Entropy Maximizing Distribution to Accommodate the q -Correlation Structure

The Gaussian distribution maximizes the Shannon's entropy in the following problem:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \max_{\phi \in \mathcal{P}} & - \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \phi(x) \log(\phi(x)) dx \\
 \text{s.t. } & \phi \geq 0; \\
 & \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \phi(x) dx = 1; \\
 & \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} x \cdot \phi(x) dx = 0; \\
 & \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} xx^T \cdot \phi(x) dx = \Sigma;
 \end{aligned} \tag{5.9}$$

for some $n \in \mathbb{N}_+$ and $\Sigma \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $\Sigma \succ 0$. For the sake of parsimony, in (5.9) we assume that the distribution is centered. To set the central trend parameter, or the mean parameter in the specific case of the Gaussian distribution, the likelihood function ϕ can be simply translated $x \mapsto x - \mu$ to incorporate the parameter μ for the central trend. Entropy functions are invariant under translation.

Similarly to how the multivariate Gaussian distribution maximizes Shannon's entropy in a Euclidean space, the multivariate q Gaussian distribution maximizes Tsallis entropy in a Euclidean space. Specifically, the optimization problem is formulated as:

$$\max_{\phi \in L^q(\mathbb{R}^n)} - \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \phi^q(x) dx \tag{5.10}$$

$$\text{s.t. } \phi \geq 0;$$

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \phi(x) dx = 1; \tag{5.11}$$

$$\frac{\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} x \cdot \phi^q(x) dx}{\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \phi^q(x) dx} = 0; \tag{5.12}$$

$$\frac{\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} xx^T \cdot \phi^q(x) dx}{\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \phi^q(x) dx} = \Sigma, \tag{5.13}$$

where $q > 1$. The feasible set of Lebesgue space $L^q(\mathbb{R}^n)$ is to ensure the well-definedness of Tsallis entropy. The normalization constraint (5.11) implies that $\phi \in L^1$; however, $\phi \in L^1$ does not imply $\phi \in L^q$, as the embedding property $L^1 \subseteq L^q$ fails to hold for Lebesgue measure on \mathbb{R}^n . As an example, consider the one-dimensional example of the probability density function

$$\tilde{\phi}(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{4} |x|^{-\frac{1}{2}} & \text{for } x \in (-1, 1) \setminus \{0\}; \\ 0 & \text{else.} \end{cases} \quad (5.14)$$

Clearly, $\tilde{\phi} \in L^1$ but $\tilde{\phi} \notin L^2$. Note that (5.12) and (5.13) are the first and second moment constraints using the q -expectation operator \mathbb{E}_q . As noted by M. Tsukada [2005], maximizing any member of the generalized class of power-law entropies, including Renyi entropy, Havrda and Charvat entropy, Arimoto entropy, and Tsallis entropy, all yield the identical power-law objective function (5.10). Regarding the constraints, $\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \phi^q(x) dx$ is the normalization factor for the q -expectation. M. Tsukada [2005] further noted that optimizing the problem formulated above is equivalent to the following problem:

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{\varphi \in L^s(\mathbb{R}^n)} & \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \varphi^s(x) dx & (5.15) \\ \text{s.t. } & \varphi \geq 0; \\ & \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \varphi(x) dx = 1; \\ & \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} x \cdot \varphi(x) dx = 0; \\ & \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} xx^T \cdot \varphi(x) dx = \Sigma. \end{aligned}$$

In (5.15), $s := q^{-1} \in (0, 1)$, thus $L^s(\mathbb{R}^n)$ is a quasi-normed space; $\varphi(x) := \frac{\phi^q(x)}{\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \phi^q(x) dx}$. If the maximizer of (5.15) is φ , then the maximizer of (5.10), ϕ , will be normalized

$$\phi(x) \propto \varphi^{1/q}. \quad (5.16)$$

Several important properties were proposed previously regarding the q Gaussian distributions in previous studies [Vignat et al., 2004, Costa et al., 2003]. Notably,

1. Using Bregman information divergence, Problem (5.15) has a unique maximizer of the form

$$\varphi(x; s) = A_s (1 - (s - 1) \beta' \langle x, \Sigma^{-1} x \rangle)_+^{\frac{1}{s-1}} \quad (5.17)$$

for some $s \in (\frac{n}{n+2}, \infty) \setminus \{1\}$, normalization constant A_s , and some dispersion parameter β' .

2. If $X \sim q\text{Gaussian}(q, \Sigma)$, $H \in \mathbb{R}^{\tilde{n} \times n}$ and $\text{rank}(H) = \tilde{n}$. Then $\tilde{X} \sim q\text{Gaussian}(\tilde{q}, H\Sigma H^T)$ with

$$\frac{2}{1 - \tilde{q}^{-1}} - \tilde{n} = \frac{2}{1 - q^{-1}} - n. \quad (5.18)$$

3. If X_1, X_2 are both q Gaussian random vectors but independent, a linear combination of $H_1 X_1 + H_2 X_2$ is not q Gaussian.
4. The duality property: if $X \sim q\text{Gaussian}(q, \Sigma)$ with $1 < q < 1 + \frac{2}{n}$, let the degree of freedom for X be $m := \frac{2}{q-1} - n$ and $\Lambda := m\Sigma$, then

$$\frac{X}{\sqrt{1 - \langle X, \Lambda^{-1} X \rangle}} \sim q\text{Gaussian}\left(\tilde{q}, \frac{m}{m+4} \Sigma\right)$$

with $\frac{1}{\tilde{q}^{-1} - 1} = \frac{1}{1 - q^{-1}} - \frac{n}{2} - 1,$

and $0 < \tilde{q} < 1$.

Property 1 will be used in our Lemma 5. Property 2 implies that any components of a q Gaussian random vector are also q Gaussian, while Property 3 implies that two independent q Gaussian vectors are not jointly q Gaussian.

By the equivalence of problems (5.10) and (5.15) discussed before, (5.17) can be rewritten

as

$$\phi(x; q, \Sigma) = (\alpha - \beta \langle x, \Sigma^{-1} x \rangle)_+^{\frac{1}{1-q}} \quad (5.19)$$

for some constant (parameter) $\alpha, \beta, q \in (0, 1 + \frac{2}{n}) \setminus \{1\}$; $x_+ := \max(0, x)$. As shown later in the proof of Lemma 5, the dimension-related upper bound $1 + \frac{2}{n}$ is due to the normalization constraint (5.11). When $0 < q < 1$, the density represents a distribution with bounded support; when $q > 1$, the density is a generalization of the bell curve distributions, and with $q \searrow 1$ the Gaussian distribution is recovered. A higher value of q corresponds to heavier tails in shape. The duality between the q Gaussian random vectors with $0 < q < 1$ and $1 < q < 1 + \frac{2}{n}$ was given by Vignat et al. [2004], which we discussed in Property 4 in Section 5.3. Distributions with bounded support correspond to $0 < q < 1$, and distributions with heavy tails correspond to $1 < q < 1 + \frac{2}{n}$. For the scope of this paper, we will focus only on the heavy-tail distributions; i.e., the case when $q > 1$. Vignat and Plastino [2009] derived the q Gaussian probability density function for $1 < q < \frac{n+4}{n+2}$, when the multivariate q Gaussian density becomes the scaled density of the multivariate student's t distribution. To incorporate the case of $q \in [1 + \frac{2}{n+2}, 1 + \frac{2}{n})$, when the variance does not exist but the q -variance can be used to capture the volatility/dispersion of the data, Vignat and Plastino [2007] also derived the resulting density; however, since a typo was found in that paper, we re-derive the density in Lemma 5. The parameters presented in the density formula (5.20) are of particular interest to statisticians, as parameter inference is the key to statistical analysis and prediction. The case of $q \in [1 + \frac{2}{n+2}, 1 + \frac{2}{n})$ will allow the resulting q Gaussian distribution to incorporate the wider class of distributions without finite moments but finite q -moments; such as the Cauchy distribution. Therefore, modeling using the q Gaussian distribution with q allowed to take the value in $[1 + \frac{2}{n+2}, 1 + \frac{2}{n})$ will be more robust.

Lemma 5. When $q \in (1, 1 + \frac{2}{n})$, the unique solution to (5.10) is:

$$p(x; q, \Sigma) = \frac{1}{|\pi\Sigma|^{1/2}} \cdot \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2}\right)} \cdot \left(\frac{2}{q-1} - n\right)^{-\frac{n}{2}} \cdot \left(1 + \left(\frac{2}{q-1} - n\right)^{-1} \cdot \langle x, \Sigma^{-1}x \rangle\right)^{\frac{1}{1-q}}. \quad (5.20)$$

Proof. By (5.17) and the equivalence of the problems (5.10) and (5.15), let the solution to (5.10) be denoted by

$$p(x; q, \Sigma) = \frac{1}{Z} (\gamma + \langle x, \Sigma^{-1}x \rangle)^{\frac{1}{1-q}} \quad (5.21)$$

for some $Z, \gamma > 0$. Feasibility for problem 5.10 when $q \in (1, 1 + \frac{2}{n})$ was given in [Vignat et al., 2004]. Hence, the strictly concavity of the objective function 5.10 implies that the optimal solution is unique. The symmetry of $p(x; q, \Sigma)$ is implied by (5.21); thus, we reformulate the problem (5.10) as the following equivalent problem:

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{p \in L^q(\mathbb{R}^n)} & - \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} (p(x; q, \Sigma))^q dx \\ \text{s.t. } & p(x; q, \Sigma) \geq 0; \\ & \int_{\mathbb{R}_{>0}^n} p(x; q, \Sigma) dx = 2^{-n}; \\ & \frac{\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} x \cdot p^q(x; q, \Sigma) dx}{\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} p^q(x; q, \Sigma) dx} = 0; \\ & \frac{\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} xx^T \cdot p^q(x; q, \Sigma) dx}{\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} p^q(x; q, \Sigma) dx} = \Sigma. \end{aligned} \quad (5.22)$$

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} Z &= 2^n \int_{\mathbb{R}_{>0}^n} (\gamma + \langle x, \Sigma^{-1}x \rangle)^{\frac{1}{1-q}} dx \\ &= 2^n |\Sigma^{1/2}| \int_{\mathbb{R}_{>0}^n} (\gamma + \langle x, x \rangle)^{\frac{1}{1-q}} dx \\ &= 2^n |\Sigma|^{1/2} \int_0^\infty r^{n-1} (\gamma + r^2)^{\frac{1}{1-q}} \left(\prod_{i=1}^{n-2} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \sin^{n-1-i}(\theta_i) d\theta_i \cdot \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} 1 d\theta \right) dr \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= 2^n |\Sigma|^{1/2} \cdot \left(\prod_{i=1}^{n-2} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \sin^{n-1-i}(\theta_i) d\theta_i \cdot \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} 1 d\theta \right) \cdot \int_0^\infty r^{n-1} (\gamma + r^2)^{\frac{1}{1-q}} dr \\
&= \pi 2^{n-1} |\Sigma|^{1/2} \cdot \left(\prod_{i=1}^{n-2} \frac{1}{2} \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{n-i}{2}\right) \sqrt{\pi}}{\Gamma\left(\frac{n-i+1}{2}\right)} \right) \cdot \int_0^\infty r^{n-1} (\gamma + r^2)^{\frac{1}{1-q}} dr \\
&= 2\pi^{\frac{n}{2}} |\Sigma|^{1/2} \cdot \left(\Gamma\left(\frac{n}{2}\right) \right)^{-1} \cdot \int_0^\infty r^{n-1} (\gamma + r^2)^{\frac{1}{1-q}} dr \\
&= 2\pi^{\frac{n}{2}} |\Sigma|^{1/2} \cdot \left(\Gamma\left(\frac{n}{2}\right) \right)^{-1} \cdot \int_0^\infty \gamma^{\frac{n-1}{2} + \frac{1}{1-q}} \left(\frac{r}{\sqrt{\gamma}} \right)^{n-1} \left(1 + \left(\frac{r}{\sqrt{\gamma}} \right)^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{1-q}} dr \\
&= 2\pi^{\frac{n}{2}} |\Sigma|^{1/2} \cdot \left(\Gamma\left(\frac{n}{2}\right) \right)^{-1} \cdot \gamma^{\frac{n}{2} + \frac{1}{1-q}} \cdot \int_0^\infty (r')^{n-1} \left(1 + (r')^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{1-q}} dr' \\
&= 2\pi^{\frac{n}{2}} |\Sigma|^{1/2} \cdot \left(\Gamma\left(\frac{n}{2}\right) \right)^{-1} \cdot \gamma^{\frac{n}{2} + \frac{1}{1-q}} \cdot \int_0^\infty \left((r')^{1-n} \left(1 + (r')^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{q-1}} \right)^{-1} dr' \\
&= 2\pi^{\frac{n}{2}} |\Sigma|^{1/2} \cdot \left(\Gamma\left(\frac{n}{2}\right) \right)^{-1} \cdot \gamma^{\frac{n}{2} + \frac{1}{1-q}} \cdot \frac{1}{2} B\left(\frac{1}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2}, \frac{n}{2}\right) \\
&= \pi^{\frac{n}{2}} |\Sigma|^{1/2} \cdot \left(\Gamma\left(\frac{n}{2}\right) \right)^{-1} \cdot \gamma^{\frac{n}{2} + \frac{1}{1-q}} \cdot \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2}\right) \Gamma\left(\frac{n}{2}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1}\right)} \\
&= \pi^{\frac{n}{2}} |\Sigma|^{1/2} \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1}\right)} \cdot \gamma^{\frac{n}{2} + \frac{1}{1-q}}.
\end{aligned} \tag{5.23}$$

In step (5.23), we use the following formula for Beta function [M. Tsukada, 2005]:

$$\int_0^\infty \left(x^\alpha (1 + x^\lambda)^\beta \right)^{-1} dx = \frac{1}{\lambda} B\left(\beta - \frac{1-\alpha}{\lambda}, \frac{1-\alpha}{\lambda}\right), \tag{5.24}$$

where $\alpha < 1$, $\lambda > 0$, $\beta > 0$, $\lambda\beta > 1 - \alpha$. Well-definedness of Z and (5.23) implies that $\frac{1}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2} > 0$; i.e., $q < 1 + \frac{2}{n}$, which is the reason for the upper bound for the choice of q .

(5.22) implies that

$$\text{tr} \left(\Sigma^{-1} \frac{\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} x x^T \cdot p^q(x) dx}{\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} p^q(x) dx} \right) = \text{tr}(\Sigma^{-1} \Sigma) = n. \tag{5.25}$$

Hence, since $p(x)$ is symmetric,

$$\begin{aligned}
& \operatorname{tr} \left(\Sigma^{-1} \frac{\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} x x^T \cdot p^q(x; q, \Sigma) dx}{\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} p^q(x; q, \Sigma) dx} \right) & (5.26) \\
&= \operatorname{tr} \left(\Sigma^{-1} \frac{\int_{\mathbb{R}_{>0}^n} x x^T \cdot p^q(x; q, \Sigma) dx}{\int_{\mathbb{R}_{>0}^n} p^q(x; q, \Sigma) dx} \right) \\
&= \frac{\operatorname{tr} \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}_{>0}^n} \Sigma^{-1} x x^T \cdot p^q(x; q, \Sigma) dx \right)}{\int_{\mathbb{R}_{>0}^n} p^q(x; q, \Sigma) dx} \\
&= \frac{\int_{\mathbb{R}_{>0}^n} \operatorname{tr} (\Sigma^{-1} x x^T \cdot p^q(x; q, \Sigma)) dx}{\int_{\mathbb{R}_{>0}^n} p^q(x; q, \Sigma) dx} \\
&= \frac{\int_{\mathbb{R}_{>0}^n} \operatorname{tr} (x^T \Sigma^{-1} x) \cdot p^q(x; q, \Sigma) dx}{\int_{\mathbb{R}_{>0}^n} p^q(x; q, \Sigma) dx} \\
&= \frac{\int_{\mathbb{R}_{>0}^n} \langle x, \Sigma^{-1} x \rangle \cdot \left(\frac{1}{Z} (\gamma + \langle x, \Sigma^{-1} x \rangle)^{\frac{1}{1-q}} \right)^q dx}{\int_{\mathbb{R}_{>0}^n} \left(\frac{1}{Z} (\gamma + \langle x, \Sigma^{-1} x \rangle)^{\frac{1}{1-q}} \right)^q dx} \\
&= \frac{\int_{\mathbb{R}_{>0}^n} \langle x, \Sigma^{-1} x \rangle \cdot (\gamma + \langle x, \Sigma^{-1} x \rangle)^{\frac{q}{1-q}} dx}{\int_{\mathbb{R}_{>0}^n} (\gamma + \langle x, \Sigma^{-1} x \rangle)^{\frac{q}{1-q}} dx} \\
&= \frac{\int_{\mathbb{R}_{>0}^n} |\Sigma|^{1/2} \langle x, x \rangle \cdot (\gamma + \langle x, x \rangle)^{\frac{q}{1-q}} dx}{\int_{\mathbb{R}_{>0}^n} |\Sigma|^{1/2} (\gamma + \langle x, x \rangle)^{\frac{q}{1-q}} dx} \\
&= \frac{\int_{\mathbb{R}_{>0}^n} \langle x, x \rangle \cdot (\gamma + \langle x, x \rangle)^{\frac{q}{1-q}} dx}{\int_{\mathbb{R}_{>0}^n} (\gamma + \langle x, x \rangle)^{\frac{q}{1-q}} dx} \\
&= \frac{\int_0^\infty r^{n-1} \cdot r^2 \cdot (\gamma + r^2)^{\frac{q}{1-q}} \cdot \left(\prod_{i=1}^{n-2} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \sin^{n-1-i}(\theta_i) d\theta_i \cdot \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} 1 d\theta \right) dr}{\int_0^\infty r^{n-1} \cdot (\gamma + r^2)^{\frac{q}{1-q}} \cdot \left(\prod_{i=1}^{n-2} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \sin^{n-1-i}(\theta_i) d\theta_i \cdot \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} 1 d\theta \right) dr} \\
&= \frac{\int_0^\infty r^{n+1} \cdot (\gamma + r^2)^{\frac{q}{1-q}} dr}{\int_0^\infty r^{n-1} \cdot (\gamma + r^2)^{\frac{q}{1-q}} dr} \\
&= \frac{\gamma \int_0^\infty \left((r')^{-n-1} \cdot (1 + (r')^2)^{\frac{q}{q-1}} \right)^{-1} dr'}{\int_0^\infty \left((r')^{1-n} \cdot (1 + (r')^2)^{\frac{q}{q-1}} \right)^{-1} dr'} \\
&= \frac{\gamma B \left(\frac{q}{q-1} - \frac{n+2}{2}, \frac{n+2}{2} \right)}{B \left(\frac{q}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2}, \frac{n}{2} \right)} & (5.27)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \gamma \cdot \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{q}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2} - 1\right) \Gamma\left(\frac{n+2}{2}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{q}{q-1}\right)} / \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{q}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2}\right) \Gamma\left(\frac{n}{2}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{q}{q-1}\right)} \\
&= \gamma \cdot \frac{n}{2} \cdot \left(\frac{q}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2} - 1\right)^{-1}.
\end{aligned} \tag{5.28}$$

In step (5.27), we used (5.24). Combining (5.25) and (5.28), we have

$$\gamma \cdot \frac{n}{2} \cdot \left(\frac{q}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2} - 1\right)^{-1} = n, \tag{5.29}$$

which gives that

$$\gamma = \frac{2q}{q-1} - n - 2 = \frac{2}{q-1} - n. \tag{5.30}$$

Thus, the probability density function that maximizes problem (5.10) is:

$$\begin{aligned}
p(x; q, \Sigma) &= \left(\pi^{\frac{n}{2}} |\Sigma|^{1/2} \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1}\right)} \cdot \left(\frac{2}{q-1} - n\right)^{\frac{n}{2} + \frac{1}{1-q}} \right)^{-1} \left(\left(\frac{2}{q-1} - n\right) + \langle x, \Sigma^{-1}x \rangle \right)^{\frac{1}{1-q}} \\
&= \left(\pi^{\frac{n}{2}} |\Sigma|^{1/2} \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1}\right)} \cdot \left(\frac{2}{q-1} - n\right)^{\frac{n}{2}} \right)^{-1} \left(1 + \left(\frac{2}{q-1} - n\right)^{-1} \langle x, \Sigma^{-1}x \rangle \right)^{\frac{1}{1-q}} \\
&= \frac{1}{|\pi \Sigma|^{1/2}} \cdot \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2}\right)} \cdot \left(\frac{2}{q-1} - n\right)^{-\frac{n}{2}} \cdot \left(1 + \left(\frac{2}{q-1} - n\right)^{-1} \langle x, \Sigma^{-1}x \rangle \right)^{\frac{1}{1-q}}.
\end{aligned}$$

□

When $q \geq 1 + \frac{2}{n}$, the solution to problem (5.10) does not exist, due to property 1 and discussions in the proof. In Lemma 5, the presented density (5.20) outlines a formula for multivariate bell-curve distributions dependent on the value of q . As q shifts from values approaching 1 from above to values approaching $1 + \frac{2}{n}$ from below, the resulting density transitions from Gaussian through a scaled version of the multivariate t -distribution to Cauchy and beyond. This density explicitly details all parameters, enabling the application of the maximum likelihood principle and facilitating the use of maximum likelihood estimation

in modeling correlated data performed in Section 5.5.

In the context of (5.20), the *characterization matrix* [Costa et al., 2003], denoted by Σ , can undergo modifications to include the degree of freedom parameter $m := \frac{2}{q-1} - n$ [Vignat and Plastino, 2005]; specifically,

$$p(x; q, \Lambda) = \frac{1}{|\pi\Lambda|^{1/2}} \cdot \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{m}{2} + \frac{n}{2}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{m}{2}\right)} \cdot \left(1 + \langle x, \Lambda^{-1}x \rangle\right)^{\frac{1}{1-q}}, \quad (5.31)$$

where $\Lambda := m\Sigma$.

$$\text{and } m := \frac{2}{q-1} - n$$

Below are a few useful remarks related to the q Gaussian distribution and other bell-curve distributions.

Remark 6. To incorporate the location parameter μ , (5.20) and (5.31) become

$$\begin{aligned} p(x; \mu, q, \Sigma) &= \frac{1}{|\pi\Sigma|^{1/2}} \cdot \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2}\right)} \cdot \left(\frac{2}{q-1} - n\right)^{-\frac{n}{2}} \\ &\quad \cdot \left(1 + \left(\frac{2}{q-1} - n\right)^{-1} \cdot \langle x - \mu, \Sigma^{-1}(x - \mu) \rangle\right)^{\frac{1}{1-q}}; \\ p(x; \mu, q, \Lambda) &= \frac{1}{|\pi\Lambda|^{1/2}} \cdot \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{m}{2} + \frac{n}{2}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{m}{2}\right)} \cdot \left(1 + \langle x - \mu, \Lambda^{-1}(x - \mu) \rangle\right)^{\frac{1}{1-q}}. \end{aligned}$$

Remark 7. For random vector $X \sim q$ Gaussian(q, Σ), its q -covariance is

$$\mathbb{E}_q [XX^T] = \left(\frac{1}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2}\right)^{\frac{1-q}{2}} |\pi\Sigma|^{\frac{1-q}{2}} \cdot \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{q}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2}\right) / \left(\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2}\right)\right)^q}{\Gamma\left(\frac{q}{q-1}\right) / \left(\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1}\right)\right)^q} \cdot \Sigma. \quad (5.32)$$

Proof. We note that

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} p^q(x; q, \Sigma) dx = \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \left(\frac{1}{|\pi\Lambda|^{1/2}} \cdot \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2}\right)} \cdot \left(1 + \langle x, \Lambda^{-1}x \rangle\right)^{\frac{1}{1-q}} \right)^q dx$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \left(\frac{1}{|\pi\Lambda|^{1/2}} \cdot \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2}\right)} \right)^q \cdot \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \left((1 + \langle x, \Lambda^{-1}x \rangle)^{\frac{1}{1-q}} \right)^q dx \\
&= \left(\frac{1}{|\pi\Lambda|^{1/2}} \cdot \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2}\right)} \right)^q \cdot \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} (1 + \langle x, \Lambda^{-1}x \rangle)^{\frac{q}{1-q}} dx \\
&= \left(\frac{1}{|\pi\Lambda|^{1/2}} \cdot \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2}\right)} \right)^q |\Lambda|^{1/2} \cdot \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} (1 + \langle x, x \rangle)^{\frac{q}{1-q}} dx \\
&= 2^n \left(\frac{1}{|\pi\Lambda|^{1/2}} \cdot \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2}\right)} \right)^q |\Lambda|^{1/2} \cdot \int_{\mathbb{R}_{>0}^n} (1 + \langle x, x \rangle)^{\frac{q}{1-q}} dx \\
&= 2^n \left(\frac{1}{|\pi\Lambda|^{1/2}} \cdot \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2}\right)} \right)^q |\Lambda|^{1/2} \cdot \int_0^\infty r^{n-1} (1 + r^2)^{\frac{q}{1-q}} \\
&\quad \cdot \left(\prod_{i=1}^{n-2} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \sin^{n-1-i}(\theta_i) d\theta_i \cdot \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} 1 d\theta \right) dr \\
&= \pi 2^{n-1} \left(\frac{1}{|\pi\Lambda|^{1/2}} \cdot \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2}\right)} \right)^q |\Lambda|^{1/2} \cdot \left(\prod_{i=1}^{n-2} \frac{1}{2} \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{n-i}{2}\right) \sqrt{\pi}}{\Gamma\left(\frac{n-i+1}{2}\right)} \right) \\
&\quad \cdot \int_0^\infty r^{n-1} (1 + r^2)^{\frac{q}{1-q}} dr \\
&= 2\pi^{\frac{n}{2}} \left(\frac{1}{|\pi\Lambda|^{1/2}} \cdot \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2}\right)} \right)^q |\Lambda|^{1/2} \cdot \left(\Gamma\left(\frac{n}{2}\right) \right)^{-1} \cdot \int_0^\infty \left(r^{1-n} (1 + r^2)^{\frac{q}{q-1}} \right)^{-1} dr \\
&= 2\pi^{\frac{n}{2}} \left(\frac{1}{|\pi\Lambda|^{1/2}} \cdot \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2}\right)} \right)^q |\Lambda|^{1/2} \cdot \left(\Gamma\left(\frac{n}{2}\right) \right)^{-1} \cdot \frac{1}{2} B\left(\frac{q}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2}, \frac{n}{2}\right) \\
&= \pi^{\frac{n}{2}} \left(\frac{1}{|\pi\Lambda|^{1/2}} \cdot \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2}\right)} \right)^q |\Lambda|^{1/2} \cdot \left(\Gamma\left(\frac{n}{2}\right) \right)^{-1} \cdot \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{q}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2}\right) \Gamma\left(\frac{n}{2}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{q}{q-1}\right)} \\
&= \left(\frac{1}{|\pi\Lambda|^{1/2}} \cdot \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2}\right)} \right)^q |\pi\Lambda|^{1/2} \cdot \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{q}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{q}{q-1}\right)} \\
&= |\pi\Lambda|^{\frac{1-q}{2}} \cdot \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{q}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2}\right) / \left(\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2}\right)\right)^q}{\Gamma\left(\frac{q}{q-1}\right) / \left(\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1}\right)\right)^q}.
\end{aligned}$$

From (5.13), we then have the following expression for the q -variance-covariance matrix

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{E}_q [XX^T] &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} xx^T \cdot p^q(x; q, \Sigma) dx \\
&= \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} p^q(x; q, \Sigma) dx \cdot \Sigma \\
&= |\pi\Lambda|^{\frac{1-q}{2}} \cdot \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{q}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2}\right) / \left(\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2}\right)\right)^q}{\Gamma\left(\frac{q}{q-1}\right) / \left(\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1}\right)\right)^q} \cdot \Sigma \\
&= m^{\frac{1-q}{2}} |\pi\Sigma|^{\frac{1-q}{2}} \cdot \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{q}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2}\right) / \left(\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2}\right)\right)^q}{\Gamma\left(\frac{q}{q-1}\right) / \left(\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1}\right)\right)^q} \cdot \Sigma \\
&= \left(\frac{1}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2}\right)^{\frac{1-q}{2}} |\pi\Sigma|^{\frac{1-q}{2}} \Sigma \cdot \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{q}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2}\right) / \left(\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1} - \frac{n}{2}\right)\right)^q}{\Gamma\left(\frac{q}{q-1}\right) / \left(\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1}\right)\right)^q}. \tag{5.33}
\end{aligned}$$

□

Remark 8. Multivariate t distributions with degree of freedom of $\frac{2}{q-1} - n$ and the scale matrix of Σ are q Gaussian with shape parameter q and scale matrix Σ .

Remark 9. The multivariate Cauchy distributions [Lee et al., 2014] in \mathbb{R}^n with scale matrix $\frac{1}{2}\Sigma$ are q Gaussian with shape parameter $q = 1 + \frac{2}{n+1}$ and scale matrix Σ .

Remark 10. For a random vector $X \sim q$ Gaussian (q, Σ) , the variance-covariance matrix exists if and only if $q < 1 + \frac{2}{n+2}$; following the same procedure to derive the variance-covariance matrix for multivariate t distribution yields that, *if existing*,

$$\mathbb{E} [XX^T] = \frac{m}{m-2} \Sigma, \tag{5.34}$$

where $m = \frac{2}{q-1} - n$.

The remarks above on q Gaussian distributions reveal their flexibility in incorporating a location parameter, μ , and adapting to multivariate contexts through detailed formulas. Remarkably, these distributions bridge with the class of multivariate bell curve distributions including Gaussian, scaled t , and Cauchy distributions under certain conditions on the

shape parameter q . The elaboration of q -correlation and the q -variable-covariance matrix underscores the capability of these distributions to model and understand the intricacies of correlated data effectively.

5.4 Proximal Conjugate Gradient Algorithm

As delineated in Section 5.5.3, our optimization scenario is predominantly quadratic in nature; therefore, the conjugate gradient approach has potential for fast convergence and numerical stability. This insight forms the basis for our introduction of a proximal conjugate gradient algorithm framework, tailored to navigate the complexities introduced by the non-convex penalized q Gaussian likelihood function for sparse statistical learning. To lay the groundwork for this discussion, we begin with an overview of relevant concepts in variational and nonsmooth analysis, presented in Section 5.4.1. The results presented in Section 5.4.1 can be found in recent textbooks on variational and nonsmooth analysis, such as [Rockafellar and Wets, 2010, Clarke, 1990, Morduchovič, 2018, Mordukhovich, 2006a,0, Bauschke and Combettes, 2011].

5.4.1 A Review on Variational and Nonsmooth Analysis

Let \mathcal{C}^{k,α_H} with $k \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 0}$ and $\alpha_H \in [0, 1]$ denote the function space such that $\forall F \in \mathcal{C}^{k,\alpha_H}$, F is k th continuously differentiable, and $D^k F$ is globally Hölder continuous with exponent α_H ; clearly, when $\alpha_H = 1$, $D^k F$ is globally Lipschitz continuous. In this subsection, we will state the results from variational and nonsmooth analysis related to the following optimization problem:

$$\min_{x \in \mathbb{R}^{p+1}} f(x) := g(x) + h(x), \quad (5.35)$$

where $f \in \mathcal{C}^{0,0}(\mathbb{R}^{p+1}, \mathbb{R})$ is a locally-Lipschitz proper function, $g \in \mathcal{C}^{1,1}(\mathbb{R}^{p+1}, \mathbb{R})$ is globally $L_{\nabla g}$ -smooth and possibly nonconvex, and $h \in \mathcal{C}^{0,0}(\mathbb{R}^{p+1}, \mathbb{R})$ is a convex locally-Lipschitz function, possibly nonsmooth. The globally Lipschitz property of ∇g can be alternatively

addressed by carrying out the optimization over a compact set. In such scenarios, given that ∇g is locally Lipschitz, it inherently becomes globally Lipschitz when restricted to a compact set.

Results from convex analysis suggest that g, h are Clarke regular; thus, f is Clarke regular. The Clarke's directional derivative, defined by

$$\begin{aligned} f^\circ(x; d) &:= \limsup_{y \rightarrow x, t \searrow 0} \frac{f(y + td) - f(y)}{t} \\ &= \inf_{\delta > 0} \sup_{\|y - x\| \leq \delta, 0 < t < \delta} \frac{f(y + td) - f(y)}{t}, \end{aligned}$$

exists for all $x \in \mathbb{R}^{p+1}$ since f is Clarke regular. The Clarke subdifferential, denoted by $\partial_\circ f$, is a set-valued mapping defined by

$$\partial_\circ f(x) := \{ \phi \in \mathbb{R}^{p+1} \mid \forall d \in \mathbb{R}^{p+1}, \langle \phi, d \rangle \leq f^\circ(x; d) \}. \quad (5.36)$$

Since f is a locally Lipschitz function, $\forall x \in \mathbb{R}^{p+1}$, $\partial_\circ f(x) \neq \emptyset$. Fundamental convex analysis results show that $\forall x \in \mathbb{R}^{p+1}$, $\partial_\circ f(x)$ is compact, convex, and upper-semicontinuous. $\forall x, d \in \mathbb{R}^{p+1}$, and we also have

$$f^\circ(x; d) = \max_{u \in \partial_\circ f(x)} \left\langle u, \frac{d}{\|d\|} \right\rangle. \quad (5.37)$$

Furthermore, (5.37) is upper-semicontinuous with respect to x . Simple convex geometry results conclude that

$$\{(v, -1) \mid v \in \partial_\circ f(x)\} = N_{\text{epi } f}(x, f(x)), \quad (5.38)$$

where $N_{\text{epi } f}(x, f(x))$ denotes the *normal cone* to $\text{epi } f$ at the point $(x, f(x))$.

Since g is smooth, $\partial_\circ g(x) = \{\nabla g(x)\}$ is a singleton. Then $\partial_\circ f(x) = \partial_\circ g(x) + \partial_\circ h(x)$,

and

$$\begin{aligned}
f^\circ(x; d) &= \max_{u \in \partial_\circ f(x)} \left\langle u, \frac{d}{\|d\|} \right\rangle \\
&= \max_{u \in (\nabla g(x) + \partial_\circ h(x))} \left\langle u, \frac{d}{\|d\|} \right\rangle \\
&= \left\langle \nabla g(x), \frac{d}{\|d\|} \right\rangle + \max_{v \in \partial_\circ h(x)} \left\langle v, \frac{d}{\|d\|} \right\rangle \\
&= g^\circ(x; d) + h^\circ(x; d).
\end{aligned} \tag{5.39}$$

Let

$$M_\rho t(x) := \left(t \square \left(\frac{1}{2\rho} \|\cdot\|^2 \right) \right) (x) = \inf_{y \in \mathbb{R}^{p+1}} t(y) + \frac{1}{2\rho} \|y - x\|^2 \tag{5.40}$$

denote the Moreau envelope operator parameterized by $\rho \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ applied on an arbitrary proper, lower semi-continuous, locally Lipschitz function $t \in \mathcal{C}^{0,0}(\mathbb{R}^{p+1}, \mathbb{R})$, where “ \square ” denotes the infimal convolution operator. We have that the Moreau envelope is a smoothing operator, specifically,

$$\text{epi } t + \text{epi } \frac{1}{2\rho} \|\cdot\|^2 \subseteq \text{epi } M_\rho t, \tag{5.41}$$

where “epi” denotes the epigraph. Clearly, $M_\rho t(x) \leq t(x)$, since $(0, 0) \in \text{epi } \frac{1}{2\rho} \|\cdot\|^2$ implies that $\text{epi } t = \text{epi } t + (0, 0) \subseteq \text{epi } t + \text{epi } \frac{1}{2\rho} \|\cdot\|^2 \subseteq \text{epi } M_\rho t$. When t is convex, (5.41) takes the equal sign; i.e., the infimal convolution becomes the exact infimal convolution.

Consider the affine function

$$A(x) := \langle a, x \rangle + b, \tag{5.42}$$

simple algebra shows that the Moreau envelope applied on A is

$$M_\rho A(x) = \langle a, x \rangle + b + \frac{\rho}{2} \|a\|^2 = A(x) + \frac{\rho}{2} \|a\|^2 \tag{5.43}$$

for some $a, b \in \mathbb{R}^{p+1}$. Moreover, the following affine addition property is often used in proximal algorithms, mainly due to the fact that the epigraph of an affine function is a

half-space that the Moreau envelope applied on:

$$M_\rho(t + A)(x) = M_\rho t(x - \rho a) + \langle a, x \rangle + b - \frac{\rho}{2} \|a\|^2 \quad (5.44)$$

Let

$$\text{prox}_{\rho t}(x) := \arg M_\rho t(x) = \underset{y \in \mathbb{R}^{p+1}}{\text{arg min}} t(y) + \frac{1}{2\rho} \|y - x\|^2 \quad (5.45)$$

denote the proximal operator, a set-valued mapping; we have

$$\text{prox}_{\rho t} = (I + \rho \partial_\circ t)^{-1} \quad (5.46)$$

is the resolvent of the Clarke's subdifferential operator $\rho \partial_\circ t$.

For nonsmooth problems, proximal methods are often used. Fundamental convex analysis results show that:

1. the Moreau envelope $M_\rho t(x)$ is twice differentiable; thus, its gradient $\nabla M_\rho t(x)$ is well-defined.
2. If t is convex, $\text{prox}_{\rho t}(x)$ is a singleton. *For the sake of parsimony, with a slight abuse of notation, we use $\text{prox}_{\rho t}$ to represent a function in this case.* It follows that both $\text{prox}_{\rho t}$ and $\nabla M_\rho t$ are firmly non-expansive, and that

$$\nabla M_\rho t(x) = \rho^{-1} (x - \text{prox}_{\rho t}(x)). \quad (5.47)$$

The results from variational and nonsmooth analysis in this subsection have laid the foundation for proving the properties discussed in Section [5.4.2](#).

5.4.2 Proximal Conjugate Gradient Framework

Proximal methods are powerful optimization techniques and are particularly adept at handling problems characterized by sparsity, which usually leads to an optimization problem that is nonsmooth [Nikolova, 2000]. Proximal algorithm tends to outperform other methods by far for nonsmooth problems [Yu and Peng, 2017, Li et al., 2016]. On another ground, Krylov subspace methods represent a cornerstone of numerical analysis, providing a powerful framework for solving large-scale optimization problems efficiently [Saad, 2003]. Krylov subspace methods exhibit a remarkable property of convergence acceleration and vastly improved numerical stability, making them indispensable tools in the numerical analyst's toolkit.

Having reviewed the related results from variational and non-smooth analysis in Section 5.4.1, we are ready to introduce our main optimization framework to combine proximal methods and conjugate gradient together. The essence of proximal algorithms lies upon the Moreau envelope's smoothing on the objective function. Indeed, proximal methods minimize $M_\rho f$ instead of f , thus avoiding nonsmoothness since $M_\rho f$ is a smooth function. In this view, proximal algorithms are, in fact, minimizing the Moreau envelope of the objective function. Thus, a wide class of numerical optimization algorithms can easily have their proximal version. Among those, conjugate gradients, a type of Krylov subspace method, are the state-of-the-art methods in smooth optimization due to their computational and memory efficiency, scalability, and numerical stability.

Prior to introducing our proximal conjugate gradient update framework, we will first show the equivalency of the optimization problem to minimize (5.35) and its the Moreau envelope. In nonconvex optimization, the main task for numerical optimization is to find a Clarke stationary point of the objective function, for which we show in Theorem 11 that the set of Clarke stationary point of f is identical to that of $M_\rho f$ for $\rho \in (0, L_{\nabla g}^{-1})$.

Lemma 11. $\forall \bar{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{p+1}, \rho \in (0, L_{\nabla g}^{-1}),$

$$0 \in \partial_{\circ} f(\bar{x}) \Leftrightarrow \nabla M_{\rho} f(\bar{x}) = 0, \quad (5.48)$$

Proof. Consider arbitrary $x \in \mathbb{R}^{p+1}, \rho \in (0, L_{\nabla g}^{-1})$. As discussed previously, the gradient of the Moreau envelope $\nabla M_{\rho} f(x) = \rho^{-1}(x - \text{prox}_{\rho f}(x))$ implies that

$$\text{prox}_{\rho f}(x) = x - \rho \nabla M_{\rho} f(x), \quad (5.49)$$

which implies the following first-order (necessary) optimality condition for Clarke's stationary point:

$$0 \in \rho^{-1}(x - \rho \nabla M_{\rho} f(x) - x) + \partial_{\circ} f(x - \rho \nabla M_{\rho} f(x)). \quad (5.50)$$

The relation above is simplified to

$$\nabla M_{\rho} f(x) \in \partial_{\circ} f(x - \rho \nabla M_{\rho} f(x)) = \nabla g(x - \rho \nabla M_{\rho} f(x)) + \partial_{\circ} h(x - \rho \nabla M_{\rho} f(x)). \quad (5.51)$$

Consider arbitrary $\bar{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{p+1}, \rho \in (0, L_{\nabla g}^{-1})$.

“ \Rightarrow ” of (5.48):

Let $0 \in \partial_{\circ} f(\bar{x}) = \nabla g(\bar{x}) + \partial_{\circ} h(\bar{x})$; i.e., \bar{x} is a Clarke stationary point of f . Then $-\nabla g(\bar{x}) \in \partial_{\circ} h(\bar{x})$. Since h is convex, (5.51) implies that

$$\langle -\nabla g(\bar{x}) - (\nabla M_{\rho} f(\bar{x}) - \nabla g(\bar{x} - \rho \nabla M_{\rho} f(\bar{x}))), \rho \nabla M_{\rho} f(\bar{x}) \rangle \geq 0. \quad (5.52)$$

Simplification gives

$$\langle \nabla g(\bar{x} - \rho \nabla M_{\rho} f(\bar{x})) - \nabla g(\bar{x}), \nabla M_{\rho} f(\bar{x}) \rangle \geq \|\nabla M_{\rho} f(\bar{x})\|^2. \quad (5.53)$$

By Cauchy-Schwartz inequality,

$$\langle \nabla g(\bar{x} - \rho \nabla M_\rho f(\bar{x})) - \nabla g(\bar{x}), \nabla M_\rho f(\bar{x}) \rangle \leq L_{\nabla g} \cdot \rho \|\nabla M_\rho f(\bar{x})\|^2. \quad (5.54)$$

Since $\rho < L_{\nabla g}^{-1}$, (5.53) and (5.54) imply that

$$\|\nabla M_\rho f(\bar{x})\|^2 \leq \langle \nabla g(\bar{x} - \rho \nabla M_\rho f(\bar{x})) - \nabla g(\bar{x}), \nabla M_\rho f(\bar{x}) \rangle < \|\nabla M_\rho f(\bar{x})\|^2, \quad (5.55)$$

which implies that

$$\nabla M_\rho f(\bar{x}) = 0; \quad (5.56)$$

i.e., \bar{x} is the stationary point of $M_\rho f$, hence a Clarke's stationary point.

“ \Leftarrow ” of (5.48):

Let $\nabla f_\rho(\bar{x}) = 0$; i.e. \bar{x} is a stationary point of $M_\rho f$. It follows directly from (5.51) that

$$0 = \nabla M_\rho f(\bar{x}) \in \partial_\circ f(\bar{x} - \rho \nabla M_\rho f(\bar{x})) = \partial_\circ f(\bar{x}); \quad (5.57)$$

i.e., \bar{x} is a Clarke stationary point of f . □

The vast majority of optimization algorithms for smooth objective functions require Lipschitz continuity of the objective function. Thus, we are to propose the following Lemma to show the Lipschitz continuity of the gradient of the Moreau envelope of f .

Lemma 12. $\forall \rho \in (0, L_{\nabla g}^{-1}), \exists L_{\nabla M_\rho f} \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ such that

$$\forall x, y \in \mathbb{R}^{p+1}, \|\nabla M_\rho f(x) - \nabla M_\rho f(y)\| \leq L_{\nabla M_\rho f} \|x - y\|. \quad (5.58)$$

Proof. Consider arbitrary $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^{p+1}$. From (5.51), since h is convex,

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle \nabla M_\rho f(x) - \nabla g(x - \rho \nabla M_\rho f(x)) - (\nabla M_\rho f(y) - \nabla g(y - \rho \nabla M_\rho f(y))), x \\ & - \rho \nabla M_\rho f(x) - (y - \rho \nabla M_\rho f(y)) \rangle \geq 0. \end{aligned} \quad (5.59)$$

Simplification gives

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle \nabla M_\rho f(x) - \nabla M_\rho f(y) - (\nabla g(x - \rho \nabla M_\rho f(x)) - \nabla g(y - \rho \nabla M_\rho f(y))), x - y - \rho (\nabla M_\rho f(x) - \nabla M_\rho f(y)) \rangle \geq 0. \end{aligned} \quad (5.60)$$

Let $\delta_{\nabla M_\rho f} := \nabla M_\rho f(x) - \nabla M_\rho f(y)$, $\delta_{\nabla g} := \nabla g(x - \rho \nabla f_\rho(x)) - \nabla g(y - \rho \nabla f_\rho(y))$, and $\delta_{x,y} := x - y$, then

$$\begin{aligned} 0 & \leq \langle \delta_{\nabla M_\rho f} - \delta_{\nabla g}, \delta_{x,y} - \rho \delta_{\nabla M_\rho f} \rangle \\ & = -\rho \|\delta_{\nabla M_\rho f}\|^2 + \rho \langle \delta_{\nabla g}, \delta_{\nabla M_\rho f} \rangle + \langle \delta_{\nabla M_\rho f}, \delta_{x,y} \rangle - \langle \delta_{\nabla g}, \delta_{x,y} \rangle \\ & \leq -\rho \|\delta_{\nabla M_\rho f}\|^2 + \rho \|\delta_{\nabla g}\| \cdot \|\delta_{\nabla M_\rho f}\| + \|\delta_{\nabla M_\rho f}\| \cdot \|\delta_{x,y}\| + \|\delta_{\nabla g}\| \cdot \|\delta_{x,y}\| \\ & \leq -\rho \|\delta_{\nabla M_\rho f}\|^2 + \rho L_{\nabla g} (\|\delta_{x,y}\| + \rho \|\delta_{\nabla M_\rho f}\|) \cdot \|\delta_{\nabla M_\rho f}\| \\ & \quad + \|\delta_{\nabla M_\rho f}\| \cdot \|\delta_{x,y}\| + L_{\nabla g} (\|\delta_{x,y}\| + \rho \|\delta_{\nabla M_\rho f}\|) \cdot \|\delta_{x,y}\| \end{aligned}$$

Simplification of the above inequality gives

$$\|\delta_{\nabla M_\rho f}\| \leq \frac{2L_g\rho + 1 + \sqrt{8L_g\rho + 1}}{2\rho(1 - L_{\nabla g}\rho)} \|\delta_{x,y}\|; \quad (5.61)$$

i.e.,

$$\|\nabla M_\rho f(x) - \nabla M_\rho f(y)\| \leq L_{\nabla M_\rho f} \|x - y\|, \quad (5.62)$$

where

$$L_{\nabla M_\rho f} := \frac{2L_g\rho + 1 + \sqrt{8L_g\rho + 1}}{2\rho(1 - L_{\nabla g}\rho)} > 0. \quad (5.63)$$

Following this idea, we introduce our proximal conjugate gradient framework in Algorithm

3. □

Algorithm 3 Proximal Point Algorithm

- 1: Input: A fixed value of $\rho \in (0, \rho^{-1})$
 - 2: Calculate the gradient of the Moreau envelope: $s^{(k)} := \nabla M_\rho f(x^{(k)})$
 - 3: $d^{(k)} := -s^{(k)} + \beta^{(k)} \cdot d^{(k-1)}$
 - 4: Line search to find $\alpha^{(k)}$ for the update $x^{(k+1)} := x^{(k)} + \alpha^{(k)} d^{(k)}$
 - 5: Update $x^{(k+1)} := x^{(k)} + \alpha^{(k)} d^{(k)}$
-

In the above algorithm, $\beta^{(k)}$ is the conjugate parameter. The significant meaning of Algorithm 3 is that for any global convergent numerical method to find the equilibria of a globally Lipschitz flow, which generally include the global convergent first-order methods, Algorithm 3 can transform such a method to a proximal counterpart.

For some objective functions, the gradient of the Moreau envelope can be calculated directly. However, calculation for the Moreau envelope's gradient is not tractable for many objective functions whose smooth component g is of complicated form. Motivated by this, we further consider the following the Moreau envelope of the objective function with linearized g , such linearization step is frequently used in proximal algorithms for statistical sparse learning problems (e.g., [Nesterov, 2004b, Ghadimi and Lan, 2013, Yang et al., 2024]).

Consider the linearized surrogate of (5.35), the locally Lipschitz function $\tilde{f} \in \mathcal{C}^{0,0}(\mathbb{R}^{p+1}, \mathbb{R})$, defined by

$$\tilde{f}(x; u) := \langle u, x \rangle + h(x) \quad (5.64)$$

$$\text{prox}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(x; u) = \arg \min_{y \in \mathbb{R}^{p+1}} \left\{ \langle u, y \rangle + \frac{1}{2\rho} \|y - x\|^2 + h(y) \right\} \quad (5.65)$$

$$\nabla_x M_\rho \tilde{f}(x; u) = \rho^{-1} (x - \text{prox}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(x; u)) \quad (5.66)$$

$\text{prox}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(x; u)$ is the proximal operator applied on \tilde{f} , and $\nabla_x M_\rho \tilde{f}(x; u)$ is the gradient of the Moreau envelope of \tilde{f} . The linearization term $\langle u, x \rangle$ in (5.64) depends on u . Recognize that $\tilde{f}(x; u)$ is linearizing the nonconvex smooth component g in (5.101) when $u = \nabla g(x)$.

We establish several definitions for subsequent utilization. Define the mapping $\tilde{g}_\rho = I -$

$\rho \nabla g \in \mathcal{C}^{0,0}(\mathbb{R}^{p+1}, \mathbb{R}^{p+1})$ for some $\rho \in (0, L_{\nabla g}^{-1})$, the locally Lipschitz property of \tilde{g}_ρ follows from $g \in \mathcal{C}^{1,1}$; i.e., $\tilde{g}_\rho(x) := x - \rho \nabla g(x)$. The following Lemma identifies some fundamental property of \tilde{g}_ρ .

Lemma 13. *\tilde{g}_ρ is a bijective from \mathbb{R}^{p+1} to \mathbb{R}^{p+1} , and \tilde{g}_ρ^{-1} is globally Lipschitz with constant $(1 - \rho L_{\nabla g})^{-1}$.*

Proof. Injectivity proof:

Consider arbitrary $x_1, x_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{p+1}$. Since $\rho \in (0, L_{\nabla g}^{-1})$, $x_1 - \rho \nabla g(x_1) = x_2 - \rho \nabla g(x_2)$ implies that

$$\|x_1 - x_2\| = \rho \|\nabla g(x_1) - \nabla g(x_2)\| \leq \rho L_{\nabla g} \|x_1 - x_2\| < \|x_1 - x_2\|, \quad (5.67)$$

hence $x_1 = x_2$. This shows that \tilde{g}_ρ is an injective mapping.

Surjectivity proof:

Consider arbitrary $y_1, y_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{p+1}$. Consider arbitrary $z \in \mathbb{R}^{p+1}$. Define mapping $\mathcal{T}(y) := z + \rho \nabla g(y)$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \|\mathcal{T}(y_1) - \mathcal{T}(y_2)\| &= \|z + \rho \nabla g(y_1) - (z + \rho \nabla g(y_2))\| \\ &= \rho \|\nabla g(y_1) - \nabla g(y_2)\| \\ &\leq \rho L_{\nabla g} \|y_1 - y_2\| \\ &< \|y_1 - y_2\|. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, \mathcal{T} is a contraction mapping, since \mathbb{R}^{p+1} equipped with Euclidean topology is a Banach space, by Banach fixed point theorem, \mathcal{T} has a fixed point; i.e., $\exists y \in \mathbb{R}^{p+1}$ such that $y = z + \rho \nabla g(y)$, or equivalently, $\tilde{g}_\rho(y) = y - \rho \nabla g(y) = z$. Thus, $\mathbb{R}^{p+1} \subseteq \tilde{g}_\rho(\mathbb{R}^{p+1})$.

Globally Lipschitz constant derivation for inverse map:

Since ∇g is globally $L_{\nabla g}$ -Lipschitz,

$$\begin{aligned}
\|\tilde{g}_\rho(y_1) - \tilde{g}_\rho(y_2)\| &= \|y_1 - \rho\nabla g(y_1) - (y_2 - \rho\nabla g(y_2))\| \\
&= \|y_1 - y_2 - \rho(\nabla g(y_1) - \nabla g(y_2))\| \\
&\geq \| \|y_1 - y_2\| - \|\rho(\nabla g(y_1) - \nabla g(y_2))\| \| \\
&= \| \|y_1 - y_2\| - \rho\|\nabla g(y_1) - \nabla g(y_2)\| \| \\
&= \|y_1 - y_2\| - \rho\|\nabla g(y_1) - \nabla g(y_2)\| \\
&\geq (1 - \rho L_{\nabla g})\|y_1 - y_2\|
\end{aligned} \tag{5.68}$$

where (5.68) is due to the fact that

$$\rho\|\nabla g(y_1) - \nabla g(y_2)\| \leq \rho L_{\nabla g}\|y_1 - y_2\| < \|y_1 - y_2\|. \tag{5.69}$$

Since \tilde{g}_ρ is surjective, consider arbitrary $z_1, z_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{p+1}$ let $y_1 := \tilde{g}_\rho^{-1}(z_1)$ and $y_2 := \tilde{g}_\rho^{-1}(z_2)$, then

$$\|\tilde{g}_\rho^{-1}(z_1) - \tilde{g}_\rho^{-1}(z_2)\| \leq (1 - \rho L_{\nabla g})^{-1}\|z_1 - z_2\|. \tag{5.70}$$

□

Define

$$\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(x) := \nabla_x M_\rho \tilde{f}(x; u) \tag{5.71}$$

with $u = \nabla g(x)$; i.e., $\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(x)$ is the gradient of the Moreau envelope of \tilde{f} .

Similarly to Lemma 11 and 12, we are to prove that the set of Clarke's stationary of (5.101) is identical to the set $\{\bar{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{p+1} | \mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(\bar{x}) = 0\}$ in Lemma 14, and then we are to show that (5.71) is globally Lipschitz in Lemma 15.

Lemma 14. $\forall \bar{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{p+1}, \rho \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$,

$$0 \in \partial_\circ f(\bar{x}) \Leftrightarrow \mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(\bar{x}) = 0. \tag{5.72}$$

Proof. Consider arbitrary $x \in \mathbb{R}^{p+1}$. The \tilde{f} is convex since it is a sum of convex function h and a linear mapping of x , which is convex.

$$\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(x) = \rho^{-1}(x - \text{prox}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(x; \nabla g(x))) \quad (5.73)$$

$$= \rho^{-1}(x - \text{prox}_{\rho h}(x - \rho\nabla g(x))) \quad (5.74)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \nabla g(x) + \rho^{-1}(x - \rho\nabla g(x) - \text{prox}_{\rho h}(x - \rho\nabla g(x))) \\ &= \nabla g(x) + (\nabla M_{\rho}h) \circ \tilde{g}_{\rho}(x) \end{aligned} \quad (5.75)$$

(5.74) is due to the affine addition property of proximal mapping. From (5.64) and (5.73),

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(x) = \rho^{-1}(x - \text{prox}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(x, \nabla g(x))) \\ \implies &\text{prox}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(x, \nabla g(x)) = x - \rho \cdot \mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(x) \\ &\implies 0 \in \rho^{-1}(x - \rho \cdot \mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(x) - x) + \partial_{\circ}\tilde{f}(x - \rho \cdot \mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(x)) \\ &\implies 0 \in -\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(x) + \nabla g(x) + \partial_{\circ}h(x - \rho \cdot \mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(x)) \\ &\implies \mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(x) \in \nabla g(x) + \partial_{\circ}h(x - \rho \cdot \mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(x)) \\ \implies &\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(x) - \nabla g(x) \in \partial_{\circ}h(x - \rho \cdot \mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(x)). \end{aligned} \quad (5.76)$$

Thus, since h is convex, $\forall v \in \partial_{\circ}h(x)$,

$$\begin{aligned} &\langle \mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(x) - \nabla g(x) - v, x - \rho \cdot \mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(x) - x \rangle \geq 0 \\ \implies &\langle \mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(x) - \nabla g(x) - v, \mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(x) \rangle \leq 0 \\ &\implies \|\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(x)\|^2 \leq \langle \nabla g(x) + v, \mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(x) \rangle \end{aligned} \quad (5.77)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq \|\nabla g(x) + v\| \cdot \|\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(x)\| \\ \implies &\|\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(x)\| \leq \|\nabla g(x) + v\|, \end{aligned} \quad (5.78)$$

provided that $\|\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(x)\| \neq 0$. Basic results on the Moreau envelope shows that $\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(x) = 0$ implies that x is a Clarke stationary point of $\tilde{f}(x)$.

Now we are proceed to prove (5.72):

“ \Rightarrow ”:

Consider arbitrary $\bar{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{p+1}$ and $\rho \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$. Let $0 \in \partial_o f(\bar{x}) = \nabla g(\bar{x}) + \partial_o h(\bar{x})$; i.e., \bar{x} is a Clarke stationary point of f . Then $\exists v \in \partial_o h(\bar{x})$ such that $\nabla g(\bar{x}) + v = 0$. (5.78) implies that

$$\|\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(\bar{x})\| \leq \|\nabla g(\bar{x}) + v\| = 0. \quad (5.79)$$

Thus, $\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(\bar{x}) = 0$.

“ \Leftarrow ”:

Consider arbitrary $\bar{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{p+1}$. Let $\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(\bar{x}) = 0$; i.e., $\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(\bar{x}) = 0$ is stationary. (5.76) implies that

$$0 = \mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(\bar{x}) \in \nabla g(\bar{x}) + \partial_o h(\bar{x} - \rho \cdot \mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(\bar{x})) = \nabla g(\bar{x}) + \partial_o h(\bar{x}) = \partial_o f(\bar{x}). \quad (5.80)$$

Thus, \bar{x} is a Clarke stationary point of f . □

Lemma 15. $\forall \rho \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}, \exists L_{\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}} \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ such that

$$\forall x, y \in \mathbb{R}^{p+1}, \|\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(x) - \mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(y)\| \leq L_{\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}} \|x - y\|. \quad (5.81)$$

Proof. Consider arbitrary $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^{p+1}$ and $\rho \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$. Let $u := \nabla g(x)$ and $v := \nabla g(y)$,

$$\begin{aligned} \|\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(x) - \mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(y)\| &= \left\| \nabla_x M_\rho \tilde{f}(x; u) - \nabla_y M_\rho \tilde{f}(y; v) \right\| \\ &= \left\| \nabla_x M_\rho \tilde{f}(x; u) - \nabla_x M_\rho \tilde{f}(x; v) + \nabla_x M_\rho \tilde{f}(x; v) - \nabla_y M_\rho \tilde{f}(y; v) \right\| \\ &\leq \left\| \nabla_x M_\rho \tilde{f}(x; u) - \nabla_x M_\rho \tilde{f}(x; v) \right\| + \left\| \nabla_x M_\rho \tilde{f}(x; v) - \nabla_y M_\rho \tilde{f}(y; v) \right\| \\ &\leq \|u - v\| + \left\| \nabla_x M_\rho \tilde{f}(x; v) - \nabla_y M_\rho \tilde{f}(y; v) \right\| \end{aligned} \quad (5.82)$$

$$\leq \|u - v\| + \rho^{-1} \|x - y\| \quad (5.83)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&\leq L_{\nabla g} \|x - y\| + \rho^{-1} \|x - y\| \\
&= (L_{\nabla g} + \rho^{-1}) \|x - y\|
\end{aligned}$$

(5.82) is due to Lemma 4 in [Ghadimi and Lan, 2013], and (5.83) is due to $\tilde{f}(\cdot; v)$ is convex and the fact that the gradient of a convex function's Moreau envelope is ρ^{-1} -Lipschitz. Therefore, let

$$L_{\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}} := L_{\nabla g} + \rho^{-1} \quad (5.84)$$

and we have

$$\|\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(x) - \mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(y)\| \leq L_{\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}} \|x - y\|. \quad (5.85)$$

□

Furthermore, (5.75) suggests that

$$\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}} = \nabla g + (\nabla M_\rho h) \circ \tilde{g}_\rho = \nabla g + (\nabla M_\rho h) \circ (Id - \rho \nabla g). \quad (5.86)$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned}
Id - \rho \mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}} &= Id - \rho \nabla g - \rho (\nabla M_\rho h) \circ (Id - \rho \nabla g) \\
&= \tilde{g}_\rho - \rho (\nabla M_\rho h) \circ \tilde{g}_\rho \\
&= (Id - \rho (\nabla M_\rho h)) \circ \tilde{g}_\rho
\end{aligned} \quad (5.87)$$

$$= \tilde{g}_\rho^{-1} \circ (\tilde{g}_\rho \circ (Id - \rho (\nabla M_\rho h))) \circ \tilde{g}_\rho \quad (5.88)$$

shows that $\tilde{g}_\rho^{-1} \circ (\tilde{g}_\rho \circ (Id - \rho (\nabla M_\rho h))) \circ \tilde{g}_\rho : \mathbb{R}^{p+1} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^{p+1}$ equals to $Id - \rho \mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}} : \mathbb{R}^{p+1} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^{p+1}$.

Since \tilde{g}_ρ is bijective, and that \tilde{g}_ρ and \tilde{g}_ρ^{-1} are continuous due to the globally Lipschitz property from Lemma 13, \tilde{g}_ρ is a homeomorphism. Hence, $Id - \rho \mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}$ and $\tilde{g}_\rho \circ (Id - \rho (\nabla M_\rho h))$ are topologically equivalent mappings via the homeomorphism \tilde{g}_ρ . Lemma 15 implies that $\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}$ is globally Lipschitz, which sufficiently implies by the Cauchy-Lipschitz theorem that the

differential equation

$$\dot{x} := \frac{dx}{dt} = \mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(x) \quad (5.89)$$

has a unique solution for any given initial value condition. Thus, $\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}$ generates a unique flow under a given initial value condition.

The operator equations presented above can be understood as demonstrating how $\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}$ functions analogously to a gradient operator. Specifically, $Id - \rho\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}$ represents executing a descent operation in the $-\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}$ direction with a step size ρ . Similarly, $Id - \rho(\nabla M_\rho h)$ represents a single gradient descent step with ρ as the step size with objective function $M_\rho h$, the Moreau envelope of h ; while $\tilde{g}_\rho = Id - \rho\nabla g$ reflects a gradient descent step with objective function g , again with ρ as the step size. Equation (5.87) elucidates that a descent in the $-\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}$ direction is identical to first performing a one-step gradient descent on g , followed by $M_\rho h$; or performing gradient descents in a converse order yields a topological equivalence via the homeomorphism \tilde{g}_ρ , as shown in (5.88).

In short summary, the approach based on linearization of the smooth term and the Moreau envelope enables us to build equivalence between identifying Clarke stationary points of the original nonsmooth objective function (5.101) and finding equilibria of the (unique) flow generated by $\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}$, as demonstrated in Lemma 14. The task of finding equilibria within a globally Lipschitz continuous flow, such as the $\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}$ flow, is well explored within mathematics, particularly in the realms of dynamical systems and numerical analysis (see, for example, [Quarteroni et al., 2007, Atkinson, 1989, Lubich et al., 2006, Hubbard and West, 1995, Helmke, 1994]). Cauchy-Lipschitz theorem establishes the uniqueness of solutions to initial value problems for globally Lipschitz continuous flows; while the existence of equilibria is a direct result of Brouwer fixed-point theorem. Numerical methods for dynamical systems, including methods for finding equilibria of the flow, are largely based on this uniqueness result. This is one reason that the vast majority of numerical methods in the context of dynamical systems require the flow to be globally Lipschitz. It is important to note that

these numerical strategies, widely applied across dynamical systems, do not hinge on the flow being derived from a conservative field. As such, the process of formulating a potential function for $\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}$ is not a prerequisite for employing numerical techniques to determine its equilibria. This perspective underscores the versatility of numerical methods in dynamical systems in finding the equilibria of flows, regardless of the explicit existence of a potential function, a stance corroborated by various sources in the literature [Quarteroni et al., 2007, Atkinson, 1989, Lubich et al., 2006, Hubbard and West, 1995, Helmke, 1994, Ross, 2019, Riahi and Qattan, 2018]. In this view, the construction of a potential function for $\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}$ is generally not necessary when deploying numerical analysis methods to find its equilibria.

In the context of nonlinear conjugate gradient algorithms for optimization, achieving global convergence on nonconvex objective functions that are globally Lipschitz-smooth implies that such methods can reliably find equilibria within the corresponding flow dynamics [Ross, 2019, Riahi and Qattan, 2018]. These algorithms typically incorporate a line search step, which may use a surrogate objective function instead of the original. This surrogate can be a constructed potential, Lyapunov, or energy function, offering flexibility when finding the potential function for $\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}$ poses challenges [Ross, 2019, Clarke, 2004, Sontag, 1998].

When it is feasible to construct a potential function whose gradient with respect to x is $\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}$, the associated objective function and its gradient become more manageable, allowing for direct global convergence arguments. If constructing a potential function with respect to x for the $(\nabla M_\rho h) \circ \tilde{g}_\rho(x)$ term in (5.75) or $\nabla g \circ (Id - \rho(\nabla M_\rho h))$ in (5.88) is tractable, the objective function with gradient being (5.75) or $\tilde{g}_\rho \circ (Id - \rho(\nabla M_\rho h))$ can hence be easily constructed. Thus, arguments for global convergence for methods based on the objective function and its gradient directly follow to prove the global convergence of the numerical optimization algorithm when applied to the constructed potential function for $\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}$. We remark that $Id - \rho\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}$ and $\tilde{g}_\rho \circ (Id - \rho(\nabla M_\rho h))$ generate two topologically equivalent flows via homeomorphism \tilde{g}_ρ ; thus, their equilibria can be transformed by \tilde{g}_ρ and share the same

stability. In the context of numerical optimization, this implies that a fixed point \bar{x} for the mapping $Id - \rho\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}$ corresponds bijectively to a fixed point $\tilde{g}_\rho(\bar{x})$ for $\tilde{g}_\rho \circ (Id - \rho(\nabla M_\rho h))$. Characterized by the first-order optimality condition in optimization of smooth functions, or equivalently, the stationary condition in dynamical system,

$$\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(\bar{x}) = \nabla g(\bar{x}) + (\nabla M_\rho h) \circ \tilde{g}_\rho(\bar{x}) = 0 \Leftrightarrow \nabla M_\rho h(\tilde{g}_\rho(\bar{x})) + \nabla g(\tilde{g}_\rho(\bar{x}) - \rho\nabla M_\rho h(\tilde{g}_\rho(\bar{x}))) = 0. \quad (5.90)$$

This approach is practical because the literature on first-order numerical optimization techniques frequently includes proofs of global convergence for methods that depend on the objective function and its gradient (for example, see [Fletcher, 1964, Polak and Ribiere, 1969, Hestenes and Stiefel, 1952, Dai and Yuan, 1999, Hager and Zhang, 2005]). Alternatively, construction of a potential function for $\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}$ is often not necessary due to the fact that fixed-point methods finding equilibria for a flow mostly establish convergence properties based on Banach fixed point theorem. This theorem guarantees convergence through intrinsic flow properties, obviating the need for a potential function [Burden, 2016, Atkinson, 1989, Agarwal et al., 2009]. Conventionally, the use of line search based on the objective function and its gradient has been applied in some numerical methods to ensure global convergence. However, with the rapid growth of research in high-dimensional statistical machine learning and large-scale optimization, evaluations of the objective function often proven to be inefficient. Consequently, recent years have seen the exploration of two main alternatives. For instance, two different types of approaches for global convergent nonlinear conjugate gradient methods have been proposed without the conventional objective function-based line search procedure. One type of approach ensures global convergence by utilizing a line search mechanism that depends only on the nonlinear equation that generates the flow [Feng et al., 2017, Snyman, 1985, 2004, Kafka and Wilke, 2019]; that is, the gradient function for smooth optimization, or $\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}$ in our case. As an example, under the smoothness assumption, the first-order optimality condition for an exact line search often solves for α with the current value $x^{(k)}$ and the

search direction $d^{(k)}$ from $\langle \mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(x^{(k)} + \alpha \cdot d^{(k)}), d^{(k)} \rangle = 0$, an equation dependent only on $\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}$ but not any surrogate objective function. From a practical perspective, this one-dimensional root finding problem can be carried out efficiently using the Brent root finding algorithm [Brent, 1971]. The other approach suggests achieving global convergence either without the need for line search [Shi and Shen, 2005, Chen et al., 2018, Sun and Zhang, 2001, Wu, 2011, Wang, 2006, Zhou, 2009] or by meeting a condition related to the Zoutendijk condition to replace the Wolfe-Powell conditions of sufficient descent (Armijo) and curvature [Neumaier et al., 2024]. Additionally, in scenarios where the fulfillment of a sufficient descent (Armijo) condition is imperative, the formulation of a surrogate objective function becomes essential. Considering (5.75), where a surrogate objective is required for the line search phase, it could be formulated as:

$$\begin{aligned}
& g(x) + (M_\rho h) \circ \tilde{g}_\rho(x) \\
&= g(x) + (M_\rho h) \circ \tilde{g}_\rho(x) + \text{constant} \\
&= g(x) + \langle \nabla g(x), \text{prox}_{\rho h}(x - \rho \nabla g(x)) - x \rangle + \frac{1}{2\rho} \|\text{prox}_{\rho h}(x - \rho \nabla g(x)) - x\|^2 \quad (5.91) \\
&\quad + h(\text{prox}_{\rho h}(x - \rho \nabla g(x))) + \text{constant}
\end{aligned}$$

This formulation, denoted as (5.91), represents a quadratic approximation of g plus the nonsmooth term h , evaluated at $\text{prox}_{\rho h}(x - \rho \nabla g(x))$. This type of formulation has often been used for the line search step in previous studies [Beck and Teboulle, 2009, Kanzow and Lechner, 2020]. The addition of the term $-\langle \nabla g(x), x \rangle$ acts as a constant in (5.64), analogous to fixing the value of u as $\nabla g(x)$ for linearization. This constant term, $-\langle \nabla g(x), x \rangle$, doesn't alter the gradient of the Moreau envelope (5.66) or the proximal point (5.65), serving to frame the quadratic approximation of $g(\text{prox}_{\rho h}(x - \rho \nabla g(x)))$.

Evaluation of $\text{prox}_{\rho h}$ in (5.91) is tractable and efficient for many functions, such as the ℓ_1 norm commonly encountered in sparse statistical learning can be efficiently computed via the soft-thresholding function. Given that line search rules such as the Wolfe-Powell or Armijo-

Goldstein conditions require only the difference in the value of the objective function at two points to decide on the step size, the constant term in (5.91) can be disregarded. Subsequent global convergence arguments stem from the fixed-point theory analysis of the numerical methods deployed to find the equilibria of the $\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}$ flow. Another possible surrogate objective function inspired by the quadratic Lyapunov function for the $\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}$ flow could be $\frac{1}{2} \|\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}\|^2$, attains its minimal value 0 exactly at the $\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}$ flow's equilibria. This quadratic approach simplifies evaluation, but it may not offer insights into the potential function's landscape, potentially limiting the numerical algorithm's acceleration capabilities if such an algorithm uses the landscape information to ensure the sufficient descent (Armijo) condition. Therefore, formulating the surrogate objective function preserving the landscape of the original objective function as outlined in (5.91) is preferable.

Building on the above discussion, we introduce our practical proximal conjugate gradient framework in Algorithm 4.

Algorithm 4 Computationally Tractable Proximal Conjugate Gradient Update Scheme

- 1: Input: A fixed value of $\rho \in (0, \rho^{-1})$
 - 2: Calculate the proximal value $p^{(k)} := \text{prox}_{\rho^{-1}h}(x^{(k)} - \rho^{-1} \cdot \nabla g(x^{(k)}))$
 - 3: Calculate $\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(x^{(k)})$: $s^{(k)} := \rho(x^{(k)} - p^{(k)})$
 - 4: $d^{(k)} := -s^{(k)} + \beta^{(k)} \cdot d^{(k-1)}$
 - 5: Line search to find $\alpha^{(k)}$ for the update $x^{(k+1)} := x^{(k)} + \alpha^{(k)}d^{(k)}$, if needed.
 - 6: Update $x^{(k+1)} := x^{(k)} + \alpha^{(k)}d^{(k)}$
-

In Algorithm 4, $\beta^{(k)}$ functions as the conjugate parameter. Unlike Algorithm 3, Algorithm 4 facilitates the update process without the need to compute $\nabla M_{\rho}f(x^{(k)})$. This adaptation is significantly valuable in practical scenarios, especially in statistical sparse learning challenges characterized by a complicated smooth component g alongside a simple nonsmooth convex component h . In such cases, computing $\text{prox}_{\rho h}$ is markedly more tractable and efficient than $\text{prox}_{\rho f}$. This approach is particularly beneficial for sparse statistical learning issues, where sparsity is commonly induced by an ℓ_1 penalty term.

5.4.3 Proximal Hager-Zhang [Hager and Zhang, 2005] Conjugate Gradient

The nonlinear conjugate gradient method represents the pinnacle of first-order techniques for addressing smooth optimization challenges. Various versions of nonlinear conjugate gradient methods have been introduced, including the Fletcher-Reeves (FR) method [Fletcher, 1964], the modified Polak-Ribiere-Polyak (PRP+) method [Polak and Ribiere, 1969, Gilbert and Nocedal, 1992], the Hestenes-Stiefel (HS) method [Hestenes and Stiefel, 1952], the Dai-Yuan (DY) method [Dai and Yuan, 1999], and the Hager-Zhang (HZ) method [Hager and Zhang, 2005]. These versions have all demonstrated global convergence with nonconvex globally Lipschitz-smooth objective functions. Among these, the Hager-Zhang conjugate gradient method is notable for delivering the best numerical performance on large-scale datasets, as indicated in previous research [Hager and Zhang, 2006]. Building on this, having introduced our practical proximal conjugate gradient update mechanism in Algorithm 4, we aim to extend this approach by adapting the smooth Hager-Zhang nonlinear conjugate gradient method to its proximal version in Algorithm 5.

In Algorithm 5, Hager-Zhang’s conjugate parameter $\bar{\beta}^{(k)}$ is defined as [Hager and Zhang, 2005]:

$$\begin{aligned} y^{(k)} &:= s^{(k+1)} - s^{(k)} \\ \beta^{(k)} &:= \frac{1}{\langle d^{(k)}, y^{(k)} \rangle} \cdot \left\langle y^{(k)} - 2 \frac{\|y^{(k)}\|^2}{\langle d^{(k)}, y^{(k)} \rangle} d^{(k)}, s^{(k+1)} \right\rangle \\ \eta^{(k)} &:= -\frac{1}{\|d^{(k)}\| \min \{\eta, \|s^{(k)}\|\}} \\ \bar{\beta}^{(k)} &:= \max \{ \beta^{(k)}, \eta^{(k)} \} \end{aligned}$$

It was proven that if the line search step in Algorithm 5 satisfies Wolfe-Powell conditions and the gradient is globally Lipschitz, Hager-Zhang conjugate gradient achieves global conver-

Algorithm 5 Proximal Hager-Zhang [Hager and Zhang, 2005] Conjugate Gradient

- 1: **Input:** Initial point $x^{(0)}$; $g \in \mathcal{C}^{1,1}(\mathbb{R}^{p+1}, \mathbb{R})$; locally-Lipschitz, convex $h \in \mathcal{C}^{0,0}(\mathbb{R}^{p+1}, \mathbb{R})$;
the smoothing parameter for the Moreau envelope $\rho \in (0, \rho^{-1})$; $k := 0$
 - 2: **Output:** p
 - 3: $k+ = 1$
 - 4: Calculate the gradient for g : $g^{(0)} := \nabla g(x^{(0)})$
 - 5: Calculate the proximal value $p^{(0)} := \text{prox}_{\rho, h}(x^{(0)} - \rho \cdot g^{(0)})$
 - 6: Calculate the gradient analog: $s^{(0)} := x^{(0)} - p^{(0)}$
 - 7: $d^{(0)} := -s^{(0)}$
 - 8: Perform the line search with $d^{(0)}$ with step size $\alpha^{(0)}$
 - 9: Update $x_1 := x^{(0)} + \alpha^{(0)}d^{(0)}$
 - 10: **while** not converged **do**
 - 11: $k+ = 1$
 - 12: Calculate the gradient for g : $g^{(k)} := \nabla g(x^{(k)})$
 - 13: Calculate the proximal value $p^{(k)} := \text{prox}_{\rho, h}(x^{(k)} - \rho \cdot g^{(k)})$
 - 14: Calculate the gradient analog: $s^{(k)} := x^{(k)} - p^{(k)}$
 - 15: $d^{(k)} := -s^{(k)} + \bar{\beta}^{(k)} \cdot d^{(k-1)}$
 - 16: Perform the line search with $d^{(k)}$ with step size $\alpha^{(k)}$ based on Wolfe-Powell conditions
 - 17: Update $x^{(k+1)} := x^{(k)} + \alpha^{(k)}d^{(k)}$
 - 18: Check for convergence
 - 19: **return** $p^{(k)}$
-

gence finding a stationary point for a smooth nonconvex objective function. In a dynamical system view, this corresponds to the global attraction property of the trajectory of the numerical algorithm to find equilibria for globally Lipschitz flows. Lemma 15 implies that $\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}$, or $s^{(k)}$ in Algorithm 5, are globally Lipschitz. Thus, by Lemma 14, Algorithm 5 yields the Clarke stationary point of f . Based on the arguments in Section 5.4.2, if the potential function for $\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}$ is tractable to construct, the Wolfe-Powell line search in Algorithm 5 can be carried out using the potential function of $\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}$ as the surrogate objective function; alternatively, an exact line search can be carried out by finding α that satisfies $\langle \mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(x^{(k)} + \alpha \cdot d^{(k)}), d^{(k)} \rangle = 0$ — such an exact line search can usually be carried out efficiently using Brent’s method to find a root of a one-dimensional equation in $\mathbb{R}_{>0}$ [Brent, 1971]. Furthermore, the descent property of $d^{(k)}$ was shown by Hager and Zhang [2005] independent of the line searches, which guarantees that $\langle \mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(x^{(k)} + \alpha \cdot d^{(k)}), d^{(k)} \rangle = 0$ has a positive root. Moreover, another line search to ensure global convergence can be carried out by backtracking to find $\alpha^{(k)}$ satisfying

$$-\langle \mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}(x^{(k)} + c_1 \cdot \alpha^{(k)} d^{(k)}), d^{(k)} \rangle \geq c_1 c_2 \cdot \alpha^{(k)} \|d^{(k)}\|^2, \quad (5.92)$$

where $c_1, c_2 \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ are constant to be chosen. When $\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}$ is pseudo-monotone in the sense of Karamardian [Karamardian, 1976], since the global Lipschitz property was established for $\mathcal{G}_{\rho\tilde{f}}$ in Lemma 15, global convergence was proven for this backtracking line search method [Feng et al., 2017]. We conclude this section with the observation that certain conjugate gradient methods obviate the need for line search procedures by determining the step size directly from $s^{(k)}$ and $d^{(k)}$, as exemplified in [Chen et al., 2018].

5.5 Optimizing Algorithm and Prediction for Penalized q Gaussian Likelihood Problems

5.5.1 Problem Formulation

Using the q Gaussian distribution to model the data will undoubtedly enhance the robustness towards the underlying distributional assumption and outliers. However, unlike the Gaussian distribution, two independent q Gaussian random vectors are not jointly q Gaussian. Thus, we take the following approach to model the data. Let $\mathbf{X}_{\text{train}} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{\text{train}} \times (p+1)}$, $y_{\text{train}} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{\text{train}}}$ denote the training design matrix and outcome, $\mathbf{X}_{\text{val}} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{\text{val}} \times (p+1)}$, $y_{\text{val}} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{\text{val}}}$ denote the validation design matrix and outcome, and $\mathbf{X}_{\text{test}} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{\text{test}} \times (p+1)}$, $y_{\text{test}} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{\text{test}}}$ denote the testing design matrix and outcome. Let

$$\mathbf{X} := [\mathbf{X}_{\text{train}}^T, \mathbf{X}_{\text{val}}^T, \mathbf{X}_{\text{test}}^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times (p+1)} \quad (5.93)$$

denote the design matrix for the entire dataset, and let

$$y := [y_{\text{train}}^T, y_{\text{val}}^T, y_{\text{test}}^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^n \quad (5.94)$$

denote the outcome for the entire dataset. Instead of assuming the q Gaussian distribution for the training, validation and testing set separately, we assume that

$$y \sim q\text{Gaussian}(q, \mathbf{X}\theta, \Sigma), \quad (5.95)$$

where $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^{p+1}$ denotes the coefficients for regression, and Σ denotes the characteristic/scale matrix for the entire data. Clearly,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{X}_{\text{train}} &= [I_{n_{\text{train}} \times n_{\text{train}}}, 0_{n_{\text{train}} \times n_{\text{val}}}, 0_{n_{\text{train}} \times n_{\text{test}}}] \mathbf{X} \\ y_{\text{train}} &= [I_{n_{\text{train}} \times n_{\text{train}}}, 0_{n_{\text{train}} \times n_{\text{val}}}, 0_{n_{\text{train}} \times n_{\text{test}}}] y \end{aligned}$$

implies that

$$y_{\text{train}} \sim q\text{Gaussian}(q_{\text{train}}, \mathbf{X}_{\text{train}}\theta, \Sigma_{\text{train}}) \quad (5.96)$$

where by the linear mapping closeness property 2,

$$\Sigma_{\text{train}} = [I_{n_{\text{train}} \times n_{\text{train}}}, 0_{n_{\text{train}} \times n_{\text{val}}}, 0_{n_{\text{train}} \times n_{\text{test}}}] \Sigma [I_{n_{\text{train}} \times n_{\text{train}}}, 0_{n_{\text{train}} \times n_{\text{val}}}, 0_{n_{\text{train}} \times n_{\text{test}}}]^T \quad (5.97)$$

is the $n_{\text{train}} \times n_{\text{train}}$ block diagonal matrix of Σ corresponding to the training data. By (2),

$$\frac{2}{1 - q_{\text{train}}^{-1}} - n_{\text{train}} = \frac{2}{1 - q^{-1}} - n, \quad (5.98)$$

which implies that

$$\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} - n_{\text{train}} = \frac{1}{q - 1} - n. \quad (5.99)$$

(5.99) allows us to recover q from the training procedure. Above formulas for the training data and parameters can trivially be applied to the validation and the testing data and parameters; thus, validation and test can carried out easily from the model build from the training data.

For q -correlated data, often times, the q -correlation structure is inferred or given prior to the model fitting; thus, we assume that the q -correlation structure is given as Ψ and we estimate the volatility / dispersion / scale parameter $\sigma^2 > 0$ such that

$$\Sigma = \sigma^2 \Psi. \quad (5.100)$$

Trivially, Ψ_{train} is the block diagonal matrix of Ψ corresponding to the training data and $\Sigma_{\text{train}} = \sigma^2 \Psi_{\text{train}}$.

We are now ready to formulate our likelihood loss function. To utilize q Gaussian distribution to model the q -correlated observations, we estimate the value of q such that q is allowed to vary, and the model will thus be more robust towards a wide class of distributions. Therefore,

we choose to build the model using (5.20), since the dispersion matrix Λ (5.31) depends on q . We formulate our maximization of our log-likelihood function as the following from (5.96) and (5.20):

$$\begin{aligned} & \underset{q_{\text{train}} \in (1, 1 + \frac{2}{n_{\text{train}}}), \theta \in R^{p+1}, \sigma^2 \in R_{>0}}{\text{arg max}} \log \left(\frac{1}{|\sigma^2 \Psi_{\text{train}}|^{1/2}} \right) \\ & \cdot \frac{\Gamma \left(\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} \right)}{\Gamma \left(\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} - \frac{n_{\text{train}}}{2} \right)} \cdot \left(\frac{2}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} - n_{\text{train}} \right)^{-\frac{n_{\text{train}}}{2}} \\ & \cdot \left(1 + \left(\frac{2}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} - n_{\text{train}} \right)^{-1} \cdot \left\langle y_{\text{train}} - \mathbf{X}_{\text{train}} \theta, (\sigma^2 \Psi_{\text{train}})^{-1} (y_{\text{train}} - \mathbf{X}_{\text{train}} \theta) \right\rangle \right)^{\frac{1}{1 - q_{\text{train}}}}. \end{aligned}$$

To address the high-dimensional data concerns, Oracle penalties are incorporated to carry out variable selection. To penalize the log-likelihood loss function to achieve variable selection, we formulate the following problem:

$$\begin{aligned} & \underset{q_{\text{train}} \in (1, 1 + \frac{2}{n_{\text{train}}}), \theta \in R^{p+1}, \sigma^2 \in R_{>0}}{\text{arg min}} \\ & - \log \left(\frac{1}{|\sigma^2 \Psi_{\text{train}}|^{1/2}} \cdot \frac{\Gamma \left(\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} \right)}{\Gamma \left(\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} - \frac{n_{\text{train}}}{2} \right)} \cdot \left(\frac{2}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} - n_{\text{train}} \right)^{-\frac{n_{\text{train}}}{2}} \right. \\ & \cdot \left. \left(1 + \left(\frac{2}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} - n_{\text{train}} \right)^{-1} \cdot \sigma^{-2} \cdot \left(\left\langle y_{\text{train}} - \mathbf{X}_{\text{train}} \theta, \Psi_{\text{train}}^{-1} (y_{\text{train}} - \mathbf{X}_{\text{train}} \theta) \right\rangle + 2n_{\text{train}} \sum_{j=2}^{p+1} w(\theta_j) \right) \right) \right)^{\frac{1}{1 - q_{\text{train}}}} \\ & \Leftrightarrow \underset{q_{\text{train}} \in (1, 1 + \frac{2}{n_{\text{train}}}), \theta \in R^{p+1}, \sigma^2 \in R_{>0}}{\text{arg min}} \frac{n}{2} \log \sigma^2 - \log \Gamma \left(\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} \right) + \log \Gamma \left(\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} - \frac{n_{\text{train}}}{2} \right) \\ & + \frac{n_{\text{train}}}{2} \log \left(\frac{2}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} - n_{\text{train}} \right) + \frac{1}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} \log \left(1 + \left(\frac{2}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} - n_{\text{train}} \right)^{-1} \cdot \sigma^{-2} \right. \\ & \cdot \left. \left(\left\langle y_{\text{train}} - \mathbf{X}_{\text{train}} \theta, \Psi_{\text{train}}^{-1} (y_{\text{train}} - \mathbf{X}_{\text{train}} \theta) \right\rangle + 2n_{\text{train}} \sum_{j=2}^{p+1} w(\theta_j) \right) \right) \end{aligned} \quad (5.101)$$

In the above formulated problem, w is the Oracle penalty function, and we are not to penalize the intercept term. The $2n_{\text{train}}$ multiplier is to ensure that the penalization effect is consistent with the number of training observations. We choose to put the penalty term

together with the quadratic term without the variance scale parameter σ^2 for two reasons: first, the optimization problem is more tractable under such problem formulation; second, we do not wish to let the value of σ^2 perturb the degree of penalization. Comparing to penalized the log-likelihood directly, we choose to penalize the quadratic component directly as it is more tractable. It was shown that doing so will preserve Oracle properties [Nikolova, 2000] of penalized estimators.

For the optimization procedure, we will proceed in a blockwise manner; i.e., we will optimize $q_{\text{train}}, \theta, \sigma^2$ separately in each iteration. More details will be given in the following subsections.

5.5.2 Minimizing with respect to q_{train} and σ^2

With all the other parameters fixed, the sub-problem to minimize with respect to σ^2 is

$$\begin{aligned} \arg \min_{\sigma^2 \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}} \frac{n}{2} \log \sigma^2 + \frac{1}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} \log \left(1 + \left(\frac{2}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} - n_{\text{train}} \right)^{-1} \cdot \sigma^{-2} \right. \\ \left. \cdot \left(\langle y_{\text{train}} - \mathbf{X}_{\text{train}} \theta, \Psi_{\text{train}}^{-1} (y_{\text{train}} - \mathbf{X}_{\text{train}} \theta) \rangle + 2n_{\text{train}} \sum_{j=2}^{p+1} w(\theta_j) \right) \right) \end{aligned} \quad (5.102)$$

which has a smooth objective function with respect to σ^2 . The first-order optimality condition

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{n}{2} = \frac{1}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} \\ \cdot \frac{\left(\frac{2}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} - n_{\text{train}} \right)^{-1} \cdot \left(\langle y_{\text{train}} - \mathbf{X}_{\text{train}} \theta, \Psi_{\text{train}}^{-1} (y_{\text{train}} - \mathbf{X}_{\text{train}} \theta) \rangle + 2n_{\text{train}} \sum_{j=2}^{p+1} w(\theta_j) \right)}{\sigma^2 + \left(\frac{2}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} - n_{\text{train}} \right)^{-1} \cdot \left(\langle y_{\text{train}} - \mathbf{X}_{\text{train}} \theta, \Psi_{\text{train}}^{-1} (y_{\text{train}} - \mathbf{X}_{\text{train}} \theta) \rangle + 2n_{\text{train}} \sum_{j=2}^{p+1} w(\theta_j) \right)} \end{aligned}$$

implies that the optimal value for the subproblem (5.102) takes minimizer

$$\overline{\sigma^2} = \left(\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} / \frac{n}{2} - 1 \right) \cdot \left(\frac{2}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} - n_{\text{train}} \right)^{-1} \quad (5.103)$$

$$\cdot \left(\langle y_{\text{train}} - \mathbf{X}_{\text{train}}\theta, \Psi_{\text{train}}^{-1}(y_{\text{train}} - \mathbf{X}_{\text{train}}\theta) \rangle + 2n_{\text{train}} \sum_{j=2}^{p+1} w(\theta_j) \right) > 0,$$

which is feasible. The feasible set for q_{train} is $\left(1, 1 + \frac{2}{n_{\text{train}}}\right)$, in this view, when n_{train} is large, the numerical stability will be an issue if minimization is carried out with respect to q_{train} directly. Thus, we choose to minimize with respect to $\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}-1}} \in \left(\frac{n_{\text{train}}}{2}, \infty\right)$.

First of all, we are to prove that such minimization is feasible.

Lemma 16. *The objective function (5.101) has a local minimizer in $\left(\frac{n_{\text{train}}}{2}, \infty\right)$ with respect to $\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}-1}}$.*

Proof. Since the objective function (5.101) is continuous and smooth with respect to $\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}-1}}$, we only need to analyze the derivative when $\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}-1}} \searrow 0$ and $\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}-1}} \rightarrow \infty$.

$\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}-1}} \rightarrow \infty$:

Stirling's formula states that

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\Gamma(x)}{\sqrt{\frac{2\pi}{x}} \left(\frac{x}{e}\right)^x (1 + O(x^{-1}))} = 1. \quad (5.104)$$

Thus,

$$\lim_{\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}-1}} \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}-1}}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}-1}} - \frac{n_{\text{train}}}{2}\right)} \cdot \left(\frac{2}{q_{\text{train}-1}} - n_{\text{train}}\right)^{-\frac{n_{\text{train}}}{2}} = 1 \quad (5.105)$$

then

$$\lim_{\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}-1}} \rightarrow \infty} -\log \left(\frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}-1}}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}-1}} - \frac{n_{\text{train}}}{2}\right)} \cdot \left(\frac{2}{q_{\text{train}-1}} - n_{\text{train}}\right)^{-\frac{n_{\text{train}}}{2}} \right) = 0. \quad (5.106)$$

We also have

$$\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} \log \left(1 + \left(\frac{2}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} - n_{\text{train}}\right)^{-1} \cdot \sigma^{-2} \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \cdot \left(\left\langle y_{\text{train}} - \mathbf{X}_{\text{train}}\theta, \Psi_{\text{train}}^{-1}(y_{\text{train}} - \mathbf{X}_{\text{train}}\theta) \right\rangle + 2n_{\text{train}} \sum_{j=2}^{p+1} w(\theta_j) \right) \\
& = O \left(\left(\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} \right) / \log \left(\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} \right) \right),
\end{aligned}$$

which implies that this term will go to infinity as $\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} \rightarrow \infty$. Thus, the objective function (5.101) goes to infinity as $\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} \rightarrow \infty$.

$$\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} \searrow \frac{n_{\text{train}}}{2}:$$

Since $\Gamma \left(\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} - \frac{n_{\text{train}}}{2} \right) \rightarrow \infty$ as $\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} \searrow \frac{n_{\text{train}}}{2}$.

The penalized log-likelihood involving $\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}} - 1}$ can be simplified as

$$\begin{aligned}
& -\log \frac{\Gamma \left(\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} \right)}{\Gamma \left(\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} - \frac{n_{\text{train}}}{2} \right)} \cdot \left(\frac{2}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} - n_{\text{train}} \right) \\
& + \left\langle y_{\text{train}} - \mathbf{X}_{\text{train}}\theta, (\sigma^2 \Psi_{\text{train}})^{-1}(y_{\text{train}} - \mathbf{X}_{\text{train}}\theta) \right\rangle + 2n_{\text{train}} \sum_{j=2}^{p+1} w(\theta_j)^{\frac{1}{1 - q_{\text{train}}}} \rightarrow \infty
\end{aligned}$$

as $\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} \searrow \frac{n_{\text{train}}}{2}$. Thus, the subproblem to minimize with respect to $\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}} - 1}$ is coercive on $(\frac{n_{\text{train}}}{2}, \infty)$. Coercivity implies that any minimizing sequence $\left\{ \left(\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} \right)_j \right\}$ must be contained within a bounded subset of $(\frac{n_{\text{train}}}{2}, \infty)$. Thus, Bolzano–Weierstrass theorem implies the existence of a convergent subsequence. Let $\left\{ \left(\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} \right)_{j_k} \right\}$ be one such subsequence, and let $\overline{\left(\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} \right)}$ be its limit. Since the subproblem has a continuous objective function with respect to $\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}} - 1}$, the objective function is lower-semicontinuous and the value of the objective function at $\overline{\left(\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} \right)}$ is less than or equal to the value of the objective function at $\left(\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} \right)_{j_k}$ for all $k = 1, 2, \dots, \infty$. Thus, since $\left\{ \left(\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} \right)_j \right\}$ is a minimizing sequence, the value of the objective function at $\overline{\left(\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} \right)}$ is less than or equal to the infimum of the objective function on $(\frac{n_{\text{train}}}{2}, \infty)$. Hence, since the entire minimizing sequence is contained in $(\frac{n_{\text{train}}}{2}, \infty)$, $\overline{\left(\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} \right)} \in (\frac{n_{\text{train}}}{2}, \infty)$ solves the subproblem of minimizing with respect to $\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}} - 1}$.

Unlike σ^2 , the minimizer for $\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}}-1}$ is not in closed form, and the evaluation of the derivative with respect to $\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}}-1}$ can not be carried out efficiently. Thus, we apply Brent's line-search method to optimize the $\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}}-1}$ subproblem [Brent, 1971]. \square

5.5.3 Minimizing with respect to θ

Minimizing with respect to θ involves a nonconvex smooth function and a convex nonsmooth function, which is termed a composite problem. In Section 5.4.3, we developed a proximal conjugate gradient algorithm for such composite optimization.

In this part, we will establish an important remark regarding the Oracle penalty. The subproblem we are to minimize with respect to θ is

$$\begin{aligned}
& \arg \min_{\theta \in \mathbb{R}^{p+1}} \langle y_{\text{train}} - \mathbf{X}_{\text{train}}\theta, \Psi_{\text{train}}^{-1}(y_{\text{train}} - \mathbf{X}_{\text{train}}\theta) \rangle + 2n_{\text{train}} \sum_{j=2}^{p+1} w(\theta_j) \\
& \Leftrightarrow \arg \min_{\theta \in \mathbb{R}^{p+1}} \frac{1}{2n_{\text{train}}} \langle y_{\text{train}} - \mathbf{X}_{\text{train}}\theta, \Psi_{\text{train}}^{-1}(y_{\text{train}} - \mathbf{X}_{\text{train}}\theta) \rangle + \sum_{j=2}^{p+1} w(\theta_j) \\
& \Leftrightarrow \arg \min_{\theta \in \mathbb{R}^{p+1}} \frac{1}{2n_{\text{train}}} \langle \theta, \mathbf{X}_{\text{train}}^T \Psi_{\text{train}}^{-1} \mathbf{X}_{\text{train}} \theta \rangle - 2 \langle y_{\text{train}}, \Psi_{\text{train}}^{-1} \mathbf{X}_{\text{train}} \theta \rangle + \sum_{j=2}^{p+1} w(\theta_j) \quad (5.107)
\end{aligned}$$

w can be chosen as oracle penalties such as SCAD/MCP penalties. And it has been shown that both SCAD / MCP penalties admit a difference-of-convex decomposition to a first-order smooth concave term plus λ times ℓ_1 penalty. The quadratic loss function is clearly convex and smooth. This justifies our assumption for the objective function. To carry out the proximal Hager-Zhang conjugate gradient method proposed in Section 5.4.3, we need to calculate $L_{\nabla g}$, the L -smoothness constant for the smooth component. Previous work suggests $L_{\nabla g} = \max \left\{ \max \text{eigenvalue of } \frac{1}{n_{\text{train}}} \mathbf{X}_{\text{train}}^T \Psi_{\text{train}}^{-1} \mathbf{X}_{\text{train}}, c_{\text{penalty}} \right\}$, where c_{penalty} is the L -smoothness constant for the smooth component of the penalty, which will be $\frac{1}{a-1}$ for SCAD and $\frac{1}{\gamma}$ for MCP [Yang et al., 2024].

Remark 17. For high dimensional data, often times, the number of covariates exceeds the

number of observations; i.e, $\text{null}(\mathbf{X}_{\text{train}}) \neq \emptyset$. Both SCAD/MCP penalties take constant values in $B_\infty(0, c)$ ¹; where $c = a\lambda$ for SCAD and $c = \gamma\lambda$ for MCP. Given any stationary point $\bar{\theta}$ in the nonempty solution set defined by $\mathbf{X}_{\text{train}}^T \Psi_{\text{train}}^{-1} \mathbf{X}_{\text{train}} - \mathbf{X}_{\text{train}}^T y_{\text{train}} = 0$. For the set $\bar{\theta} + \text{null}(\mathbf{X}_{\text{train}}) \setminus B_\infty(0, c)$, each point in the relative interior (which is nonempty) of this set is a Clarke stationary point, which implies that any algorithm with a starting point in this set will converge in 0 steps. This might pose an issue for signal recovery, since $\text{null}(\mathbf{X}_{\text{train}})$ is a vector subspace and some points can be very far from the origin.

Remark 18. In view of the subproblem with respect to θ , it is trivial that the minimizer for (5.107) does not depend on the other parameters, which are q and σ^2 . Since the q Gaussian distribution is a generalization for all bell curve distributions, the estimation of the central trend using the maximum likelihood principle for bell curve distributions is equivalent to minimize a quadratic function, which has a breakdown point of 0.

Taking into account the optimization subproblem with respect to θ , it is evident that the solution to (5.107) remains unaffected by the other parameters, namely q and σ^2 . Given that the q Gaussian distribution extends the framework of bell curve distributions, the problem (5.107) implies that estimating the central trend through the maximum likelihood principle for all bell curve distributions is equivalent to minimizing a quadratic function of the central trend, therefore characterized by a breakdown point of 0.

5.5.4 Prediction for y_{test}

To show how prediction can be made, we will show the methods to predict y_{test} using the trained model in this subsection. The same method applies for validation when predictions on y_{val} are needed or to predict any new data based on the trained model. Since the data

¹ $B_\infty(0, c)$ denotes the open ball in uniform norm *in the corresponding space*, centered at the origin with radius c .

are mutually q Gaussian, (5.99) implies that

$$\frac{1}{q_{\text{train}} - 1} - n_{\text{train}} = \frac{1}{q_{\text{val}} - 1} - n_{\text{val}} = \frac{1}{q_{\text{test}} - 1} - n_{\text{test}} = \frac{1}{q - 1} - n, \quad (5.108)$$

which will be used to recover the value of the shape parameter $q_{\text{val}}, q_{\text{test}}$. Note that when n_{new} data points are introduced, the total number of observations n changes from $n_{\text{train}} + n_{\text{val}} + n_{\text{test}}$ to $n_{\text{train}} + n_{\text{val}} + n_{\text{test}} + n_{\text{new}}$, thus, the value of q will change for the entire dataset. However, q_{train} stays the same; thus, we suggest inferring the shape parameter for each data set based on q_{train} directly using the equation above. With q calculated, it is straightforward to estimate the q -variance-covariance matrix $\mathbb{E}_q \left[(y. - \mathbf{X}\theta) (y. - \mathbf{X}\theta)^T \right]$ based on (5.33); or, *if existing*, the variance-covariance matrix $\mathbb{E} \left[(y. - \mathbf{X}\theta) (y. - \mathbf{X}\theta)^T \right]$ based on (5.34).

5.6 Conclusion and Discussion

This paper explores the field of statistical sparse learning, focusing on modeling correlated data through the lens of maximizing Tsallis entropy. It addresses the limitations inherent in the conventional Gaussian distribution, notably its lack of robustness towards outliers and underlying shape assumptions, by advocating for the q Gaussian distribution. This distribution, derived from Tsallis entropy maximization, represents a novel approach to handling correlated data and heterogeneity — elements frequently encountered in biostatistical contexts involving genetic and longitudinal studies.

This paper encompasses a re-derived probability density function for the multivariate q Gaussian distribution based on Tsallis entropy maximization. Statistical modeling based on the derived density paves the way for the analysis of correlated data and heterogeneity and enables variable selection. Furthermore, we have developed an innovative framework capable of converting any numerical method, originally designed to identify equilibria in flows, into a tool for tackling composite optimization problems that are prevalent in statistical sparse

learning. By applying this framework to the Hager-Zhang conjugate gradient algorithm, we have crafted an effective and stable algorithm tailored to the challenges of sparse statistical learning. Given the abundance of methods for numerically identifying equilibria for globally Lipschitz flows, our approach significantly broadens the arsenal of techniques available to address sparse statistical learning optimization challenges.

In conclusion, our research positions the q Gaussian distribution, underpinned by maximizing Tsallis entropy, as a robust and adaptable alternative to Gaussian-based methodologies in statistical sparse learning on correlated data. This breakthrough not only confronts the traditional limitation of Gaussian assumptions, but also paves the way for expanded investigation into Tsallis entropy-maximizing distributions, particularly within the domain of biostatistics and allied disciplines.

Future directions for research include the exploration of the log-linear model through the lens of Tsallis entropy maximization, akin to approaches previously based on Shannon's entropy. Moreover, the study of the phenomenon called *volatility smirk* in financial return data may benefit from employing the log- q Gaussian distribution — a transformation of the q Gaussian distribution, which can provide deeper insights into the nuances of financial markets. Additionally, in the field of statistical computing research, our framework that transforms numerical methods for identifying flow equilibria into algorithms for solving composite optimization problems opens numerous avenues for future research, especially in a sparse learning context.

Chapter 6

Discussion

In the field of statistical analysis and supervised statistical machine learning applied to high-dimensional, extra-large datasets, which are prevalent in genetics and neuroimaging, the typical workflow initiates with the screening of variables to pinpoint those most relevant to the outcome, subsequently constructing the model based on these selected variables from the screening step. These procedures typically follow an unsupervised preprocessing step, such as genotyping quality control or Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium filtering in genetic data. For example, simulation studies and case studies utilizing preprocessed ABIDE data [Cameron et al., 2013, Barry et al., 2020], as presented in my first manuscript, exemplify this workflow in a real-world context. Within this structured approach of high-dimensional biostatistical analysis, the variable screening methods presented in my first manuscript emerge as a pivotal tool, effectively handling the nonlinear association between the outcome and covariates in the screening step. Furthermore, the q Gaussian modeling introduced in my third manuscript offers a flexible modeling framework that extends beyond the Gaussian assumption, enabling the adaptation of distributional shapes to encompass heavier tails, thus enhancing outlier accommodation and providing a more robust estimate of the volatility parameter. Furthermore, the optimization techniques developed in manuscripts 2 and 3

lay the groundwork for efficiently undertaking computationally intensive tasks from sparse learning in high-dimensional large datasets, thereby facilitating deeper insights from various statistical modeling approaches applied to high-dimensional biomedical data.

The mutual information-based screening tool developed in my first manuscript is adaptable for use in any high-dimensional dataset encountered in the field of biostatistics, including those in genetics and neuroimaging. This method's efficacy, as demonstrated in my first manuscript, stems from leveraging the computational speed using the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT), ensuring that the running time of FFT-based Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) remains competitive with alternative methods. It is important to underscore the inherent trade-offs in statistical analysis: between statistical efficiency and the breadth of underlying assumptions. Mutual information and copula methods, free from the constraints of linearity, excel with nonlinearly associated data for screening tasks but at the expense of statistical efficiency. Nonparametric methods like KDE, by relaxing distributional assumptions, similarly trade some statistical efficiency for robustness towards the underlying distributional assumptions. However, for univariate variable screening, where only two variables are considered at each iteration, this compromise on statistical efficiency is of less concern. Consider the idea behind the "curse of dimensionality": for two continuous variables, a dataset with as few as 900 data points will allow 30 data points per dimension – following this rule of thumb, the $2D$ surface for the bivariate density can be estimated fairly well using the information encompassed in the dataset, making nonparametric estimation of the measure of association particularly suited for variable screening tasks. Furthermore, the existence of nonparametric methods for estimating copulas, as highlighted in [Rabhi and Bouezmarni, 2019], opens up intriguing avenues for future research. Specifically, comparing the efficacy of nonparametric copula estimation with that of nonparametric mutual information estimation in the context of variable screening presents a promising direction for further research.

The first manuscript focuses on variable screening using marginal association. In some

cases, when certain variables exhibit significantly higher association measures than others, they should be selected. The number of variables to include is often based on external knowledge. Generally, the asymptotic distribution of the mutual information estimator can help guide the decision on the number of variables to include in the model. Therefore, further exploration of this topic presents an interesting direction for future research. Additionally, for variable selection based on a joint model, the number of covariates often depends on when it gives the best predictive performance. However, for ultra high-dimensional data, it is usually infeasible to find the set of variables that will give the best performance.

The case studies aimed at predicting age and autism diagnosis in my first manuscript predominantly utilized penalized (generalized) linear models, largely because these models are currently considered state-of-the-art. However, to address the potential limitations of linearity, I extended the scope of these studies by also fitting the models on the splines produced by Bernstein polynomials of degree 3 on the selected covariates [Racine, 2022] and repeating the same model fitting process. This spline transformation approach allows for a nuanced exploration beyond the underlying linearity assumptions of the (generalized) linear models. The results, illustrated in Figures 6.1 and 6.2, in fact, corroborate our observations from the first manuscript as shown in Figures 3.4 and 3.5.

Figure 6.1: Testing Set R^2 for age at the scan outcome v.s. the number of most associated brain imaging covariates based on the association measure rankings. *The most associated brain imaging covariates are then input to the spline transformer using Bernstein polynomial of degree 3 to produce the data for model-fitting.* Means with their 95% confidence intervals were plotted for 20 simulation replications.

Figure 6.2: Testing Set AUROC for autism diagnosis outcome v.s. the number of most associated brain imaging covariates based on the association measure rankings. *The most associated brain imaging covariates are then input to the spline transformer using Bernstein polynomial of degree 3 to produce the data for model-fitting.* Means with their 95% confidence intervals were plotted for 20 simulation replications.

In manuscripts 2 and 3, substantial advances are made in statistical computing, particularly in the optimization of composite problems that are commonly encountered in sparse learning – encompassing scenarios like penalized least squares, robust objective functions (for example, Huber loss), log-likelihood, partial log-likelihood, the generalized method of moments (GMM), and more. A common characteristic of these (unpenalized) objective functions is their Lipschitz smoothness; hence, when penalized with sparse penalties, the smooth component of the penalized objective function will retain the Lipschitz smoothness. Consider, for example, different forms of generalized linear models (GLM) that are often used in the

field of biostatistics, for the link function g , the general form of GLM is to model

$$g(\mathbb{E}(\mathbf{y}|\mathbf{X})) = \mathbf{X}\boldsymbol{\beta}.$$

A result from the fact that all norms are equivalent in finite-dimensional spaces is that all linear operators mapping from a finite-dimensional normed linear space to any normed linear space are bounded. Thus, the finite-dimensional design matrix \mathbf{X} clearly has a bounded operator norm, thus $\mathbf{X}\boldsymbol{\beta}$ is globally Lipschitz smooth with respect to $\boldsymbol{\beta}$. The link function, in fact, often satisfies $g \in \mathcal{C}^2$ and has a bounded second derivative, thus implies $g \in \mathcal{C}^{1,1}$. When the link function does not have a bounded second derivative over the Euclidean space such as exponential function for Poisson regression, restricting the regression on a compact set will make any locally Lipschitz-smooth optimization problem globally Lipschitz-smooth over the restricted compact set. As argued in our second manuscript, the vast majority of statistical learning problems can be considered as optimizing over a closed ball centered at the origin with a large but finite radius in practice. Subsequently, the log-likelihood function is usually globally Lipschitz-smooth with respect to the parameters of interest. Since continuity is invariant under function composition, the objective function is globally Lipschitz-smooth as long as differentiability conditions allow, which is mostly the case for (unpenalized) statistical loss functions.

The adaptation to mixed-effects models, frequently used in biological data modeling and longitudinal studies, involves incorporating finite-dimensional design matrices for mixed effects. As discussed previously, finite-dimensional design matrices have a bounded operator norm, thus their linear mapping is globally Lipschitz-smooth. This fact guarantees the preservation of Lipschitz smoothness for the objective functions of the mixed effects model variants stemming from the objective function of the GLMs discussed before, enabling the optimization methods developed in manuscripts 2 and 3 to be effectively applied to them. Consequently, these algorithms are computationally efficient, and their first-order nature ensures a low

memory consumption. This is vital for analysis of high-dimensional large biological datasets whose size by far exceeds the memory bottleneck.

Sometimes, the challenge of deriving closed-form expressions for the gradient necessitates the use of numerical tools such as auto-differentiation. This approach is feasible and practical, thanks to advances in various auto-differentiation technologies due to rapid research in training deep neural networks. Nevertheless, conducting error analysis in the application of auto-differentiation, particularly for gradient calculations in first-order optimization algorithms, presents a rich area for further investigation. This exploration is also pertinent given the explosive growth in neural network research, where insights from numerical analysis can significantly contribute to advances in both statistical computing and deep learning.

An important part of manuscripts 2 and 3 is established based on Moreau envelope, also known as Moreau-Yosida regularization, which was originally established as a crucial concept within functional analysis in Hilbert spaces [Moreau, 1965], before it was recognized for its extensive applicability in optimization and variational analysis in finite-dimensional settings. This concept also facilitates a nuanced discussion on the trade-off between statistical efficiency and robustness towards outliers. Traditionally, the mean, minimizing the L_2 norm, is considered statistically efficient but vulnerable to outliers as it has a breakdown point of 0; while the median, minimizing the L_1 norm, offers robustness towards outliers with a breakdown point of 0.5 at the expense of statistical efficiency. The Huber M-estimator balances between mean and median, is the result of minimizing Huber loss function, defined by:

$$L_\delta(a) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2}\theta^2, & |\theta| \leq \delta; \\ \delta (|\theta| - \frac{1}{2}\delta), & |\theta| > \delta. \end{cases}$$

Immediately,

$$\text{epi } \frac{L_\delta}{\delta} = \text{epi } |\cdot| + \text{epi } \frac{1}{2\delta} (\cdot)^2,$$

which, based on our discussion of variational and nonsmooth analysis in the third manuscript, gives the (exact) infimal convolution equality

$$\frac{L_\delta}{\delta} = |\cdot| \square \frac{1}{2\delta} (\cdot)^2 = M_\delta |\cdot|;$$

that is, the Huber loss function scaled by $\frac{1}{\delta}$ is the smoothing of the absolute value function by Moreau envelope parametrized by smoothing parameter δ . Figure 6.3 visualizes how the scaled Huber loss function acts as Moreau envelope smoothing the absolute value function. This fact connects the famous Huber M-estimator, which maintains a balance between statistical efficiency and robustness to outliers for central trend estimation, to the famous Moreau envelope, which is the foundational work for our discussion of proximal methods in manuscripts 2 and 3.

Figure 6.3: (scaled) Huber loss function and the absolute value function

Further on the trade-off between statistical efficiency and robustness towards outliers and distributional assumption, the q Gaussian distribution from my third manuscript, when compared to the conventional Gaussian distribution, allows adjustment to the shape parameter. Recall that when $q \searrow 1$, q Gaussian random variable becomes Gaussian. The trade-off here is that the estimation of q costs one degree of freedom. Nevertheless, we deem the trade-off of one degree of freedom usually a worthwhile exchange for the capability to account for the shape of the underlying distribution.

Moreau envelope, explored in detail within manuscripts 2 and 3, represents just one of the many concepts from functional analysis and operator theory that extends the relevance of statistics beyond statistical computing. Dynamical system also plays a crucial role in a broader statistical landscape, transcending research in statistical computing. The principle of maximum likelihood estimation, which seeks to minimize the negative log-likelihood, is intricately linked to dynamical systems through the concept of observed Fisher information.

Observed Fisher information measures the curvature of this minimizer to reflect its stability, which can be used to estimate the expected Fisher information, and provides a lower bound on the variance of any unbiased estimator as dictated by the Cramer–Rao Lower Bound (CRLB). To sum up in one sentence, the stability of the minimizer of the negative log-likelihood function directly reflects on the variance of any unbiased estimator.

Much of the content of this thesis content in manuscripts 2 and 3 focuses on sparse learning, as known as variable selection, using sparse penalties. A challenge in this area of statistical learning involves the determination of hyper-parameters, such as those for sparse penalties in sparse learning or the bandwidth matrix for kernel density estimation. Conventionally, selecting these hyperparameters has relied on a data-driven methodology employing zero-order techniques such as grid search, supplemented by bootstrap validation or cross-validation. This approach, while effective, can be computationally intensive, particularly with large, high-dimensional datasets. Recent developments in implicit differentiation offer a promising avenue for a more computationally efficient choice of hyperparameters [Blondel et al., 2022, Bertrand et al., 2020,0] – this research suggests that leveraging implicit differentiation to speed up hyperparameter optimization presents a compelling direction for future research in statistical computing, particularly in the realms of sparse learning and variable selection. The work presented in this thesis revolves around nonconvex penalties, which result in non-unique local minimizers. This poses a significant challenge for implicit differentiation in bi-level optimization when tuning penalty hyper-parameters. Unlike Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator (LASSO), where the set of minimizers can be proven to be a singleton under certain conditions, the presence of multiple local minimizers in nonconvex penalties complicates the adaptation of such methods.

The third manuscript extensively builds on the concept of Tsallis entropy maximization, leading to the formulation of the q Gaussian likelihood. This approach enables the modeling of distributions with power-law decay for their tails, thus allowing heavier tails compared

to the exponential decay observed in Gaussian distributions. Drawing parallels with Shannon entropy’s application in solving likelihood equations, as noted by [Calcagni et al. \[2019\]](#), leveraging the principle of entropy maximization often leads to the formulation of a dual problem alongside the primal likelihood maximization problem. This duality sometimes can reveal unique characteristics and computational strategies applicable to a wide array of models frequently used in biostatistics, for example, log-linear models. From this perspective, investigating the role of Tsallis entropy maximization in addressing likelihood maximization issues, particularly for cases related to the log- q Gaussian distribution, emerges as a compelling research pathway situated at the confluence of biostatistics and physics.

In addition to the discussion of proximal methods established based on Moreau envelope smoothing, detailed in manuscripts 2 and 3, there exists an alternative technique that applies smoothing directly to the nonsmooth objective function [[Chen and Zhou, 2010](#)]. This technique is akin to the concept of mollification, a term often encountered in discussions of partial differential equations or functional analysis. In manuscript 2, we showed that SCAD and MCP penalties can be represented in difference-of-convex form, combining a convex ℓ_1 norm with a smooth, concave term – refer to equations (4.1), (4.2), (4.3), and (4.4) in manuscript 2 for an in-depth explanation. Each term, including the ℓ_1 norm, undergoes independent smoothing if needed. Smoothing can be applied directly to both terms separately. To smooth out the ℓ_1 norm term, since the absolute value of the term takes value -1 on $\mathbb{R}_{<0}$ and 1 on $\mathbb{R}_{>0}$, the first-order derivative can be made continuous by any sigmoid function. For example: scaled and translated logistic function

$$\frac{1.0 e^{(\delta_{moll}\theta)} - 1.0}{1.0 e^{(\delta_{moll}\theta)} + 1.0},$$

with an integral serving as a smoothed out (“mollified”) version of ℓ_1 penalty

$$-\frac{\delta_{moll}\theta + 2 \log(2) - 2 \log(e^{(\delta_{moll}\theta)} + 1)}{\delta_{moll}}.$$

In the above equations, $\delta_{moll} \geq 0$ denotes the smoothing parameter and θ denotes the penalized coefficient; $\delta_{moll} = 0$ recovers the nonsmooth ℓ_1 penalty component. The figure shown in Figure 6.4 illustrates the smoothing (referred to as “mollification”) that is similar to, but not identical to, the role of a mollifier, which is defined as a function that is infinitely differentiable and has a compact support. A similar smoothing effect can be achieved for the ℓ_1 function using other sigmoid functions, such as \arctan , which ensure the derivative converges to -1 as $\theta \rightarrow -\infty$ and 1 as $\theta \rightarrow \infty$. Notably, most sigmoid functions possess infinite-order smoothness, rendering the smoothed out ℓ_1 infinitely differentiable. This approach to smoothing enables the application of smoothing techniques to nonsmooth objective functions [Chen and Zhou, 2010].

Figure 6.4: Scaled and Translated Logistic Function to Make the Discontinuous Derivative Continuous and Its Integral to “Mollify” ℓ_1

For the concave term within the oracle penalty, already first-order smooth, smoothing to achieve second-order smoothness \mathcal{C}^2 is feasible. The equation for the smoothed MCP concave

component serves as an illustration:

$$p_{MMCP,\lambda,\gamma,\delta_{MCP}}(\theta) = \begin{cases} -\frac{\theta^2}{2\gamma}; & |\theta| < \gamma\lambda - \delta_{MCP} \\ -\left(\frac{\gamma^3\lambda^3 - 3\delta_{MCP}\gamma^2\lambda^2 + 3\delta_{MCP}^2\gamma\lambda - \delta_{MCP}^3 + 3(\gamma\lambda + \delta_{MCP})\theta^2}{12\delta_{MCP}\gamma}\right) & \gamma\lambda - \delta_{MCP} \leq |\theta| < \gamma\lambda + \delta_{MCP} \\ -\left(\frac{(3\gamma^2\lambda^2 - 6\delta_{MCP}\gamma\lambda + 3\delta_{MCP}^2 + \theta^2)|\theta|}{12\delta_{MCP}\gamma}\right); & \\ -\lambda|\theta| + \frac{3\gamma^2\lambda^2 + \delta_{MCP}^2}{6\gamma}; & |\theta| \geq \gamma\lambda + \delta_{MCP} \end{cases}$$

In these expressions, $\delta_{MCP} \geq 0$ denotes the smoothing parameter for the MCP concave component, and θ the penalized coefficient, with the remaining parameters as defined in manuscript 2, aligning with the original MCP formulation [Zhang, 2010]; $\delta_{MCP} = 0$ recovers the original first-order smooth MCP concave component. Smoothing the first-order smooth concave component further to achieve \mathcal{C}^2 or higher smoothness potentially allows for establishing \mathcal{C}^2 -diffeomorphism, augmenting discussions in manuscript 3 on the dynamical system and optimization. This advancement could be pivotal for employing statistical computing algorithms within Morse theory, suggesting a unified framework for a broader spectrum of optimization problems discussed in this thesis. Mentioning this further smoothing of the smooth concave component, if leaving the ℓ_1 nonsmooth component unaltered, preserves the Oracle property of the estimator [Nikolova, 2000].

Throughout this thesis, the Bayesian methodology for analyzing high-dimensional data was not extensively covered, primarily due to the significant computational cost of posterior calculations. Such computations tend to be significantly more resource-intensive than those required by frequentist or likelihood-based approaches, making them less practical for large, high-dimensional datasets. However, recent advances have discussed posterior computations in a Hilbert space setting [Riutort-Mayol et al., 2022, Sprungk, 2017]. The work presented in manuscripts 2 and 3 primarily engages with concepts in a Euclidean space, which can be extended to an infinite-dimensional space. For example, the accelerated gradient technique discussed in the second manuscript is adaptable to a Hilbert space context, aligned with

prior analyses of first-order optimization algorithms analyzed using a dynamical system reflecting a Hessian-driven damping mechanism [[Attouch et al., 2020](#)]. Consequently, adapting optimization strategies to a Hilbert space setting may offer more efficient computational alternatives for Bayesian analysis, considering that posterior computations can be viewed as optimization problems within a function space.

Chapter 7

Conclusion

This thesis met its objectives by systematically addressing several challenges in statistical computing and modeling in the analysis of high-dimensional biological data that are frequently encountered in neuroimaging and genetics. Each manuscript within this thesis contributes to a cohesive workflow that enhances our ability to draw meaningful insights from complex datasets.

In the first manuscript, I introduced `fastHDMI`, a Python package specifically designed for efficient variable screening within high-dimensional contexts. This tool is robust to nonlinear associations, which is essential for the statistical analysis of many datasets. The application of `fastHDMI` to the preprocessed Autism Brain Imaging Data Exchange (ABIDE) [[Cameron et al., 2013](#), [Barry et al., 2020](#)] dataset exemplifies its practical utility and transformative potential in real-world scenarios. This manuscript establishes the groundwork for the typical workflow in biostatistical analysis, which starts with variable screening to identify those variables most relevant to the outcome, pivotal for the subsequent modeling steps.

Building on this, the second manuscript advanced our computational capabilities by developing efficient statistical computing methods for sparse learning that utilize nonconvex penalties, addressing significant computational challenges. The manuscript's focus on optimizing

hyperparameter settings based on complexity bounds significantly enhances the efficiency of statistical computing, particularly in handling large-scale high-dimensional data. This manuscript has been published on *Statistics and Computing* [Yang et al., 2024].

The third manuscript further refines our approach by introducing the q Gaussian linear mixed-effects model. This innovative model provides a robust alternative to conventional Gaussian models by accommodating broader distributional shapes and heavier tails. This advancement is critical for modeling correlated and heterogeneous data often encountered in biostatistics, such as in genetic and longitudinal studies, thus enhancing the robustness and flexibility of statistical analyses. In addition, the innovative framework for converting numerical methods for finding equilibria of dynamical systems into optimization algorithms for composite objective functions, often found in sparse penalized objectives, offers significant insights. As a result, various researches could leverage this using the proposed framework to adapt a numerical method for dynamical systems to a numerical algorithm for composite optimization problem that is prevalent in the statistical computation of sparse learning.

Collectively, these manuscripts create a comprehensive approach for robust and efficient analysis of high-dimensional data by seamlessly integrating solutions to variable screening robust to nonlinearity and distributional assumption, optimize objective functions with non-convexity and nonsmoothness induced by Oracle sparse penalties, and model correlated data structures robust to distributional assumptions and heavy tails. The implications of this research are substantial, providing robust, scalable, and computationally efficient methodologies that improve our capacity to analyze and interpret high-dimensional large datasets. By improving the efficiency and robustness of these statistical learning processes, this thesis supports significant advancements in personalized medicine, enhances our understanding of complex genetic interactions and brain functions, and fosters the development of better diagnostic and therapeutic strategies. The methodologies developed here set a new standard in statistical computing for high-dimensional data analysis, paving the way for future research

that will expand their applications in diverse fields in science and medicine.

Appendices

APPENDIX A

Appendix to Manuscript 1

A.1 Methodology Consideration

For a function f defined over an Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^n , its (continuous) Fourier transform is defined as

$$(\mathcal{F}f)(\xi) := \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} f(x) \exp(-2\pi i \cdot \langle x, \xi \rangle) dx, \quad (\text{A.1})$$

a linear operator. The Fourier series is then the synthesis formula. Consider a square-integrable function space $L^2([-\pi, \pi])$, the fundamental results of Fourier analysis [Stein and Shakarchi, 2003] conclude that $\{\phi_k := \exp(ikx) \mid k \in \mathbb{Z}\}$ is an orthonormal and complete basis for this Hilbert space with the inner product being defined by

$$\forall f, g \in L^2([-\pi, \pi]), \langle f, g \rangle := \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} f(x) \bar{g}(x) dx.$$

We remark that the inner product for a complex Hilbert space is linear for the first argument and anti-linear for the second argument. The Fourier series that represents any function $f \in L^2([-\pi, \pi])$ is then

$$f = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \langle f, \phi_k \rangle \phi_k.$$

Clearly, (1D continuous) Fourier transform is to extend the idea of decomposing functions on the interval $[-\pi, \pi]$ to analyzing them across \mathbb{R} by scaling the frequency domain. This approach applies analogously to higher-dimensional situations. The completeness of the Fourier basis is given by the Fourier theorem, while the uniqueness of continuous Fourier transform and the inverse Fourier transform under certain conditions is a key result in Fourier analysis [Stein and Shakarchi, 2003]. An important property of the Fourier series/continuous Fourier transform is the convolution property:

$$\forall f, g \in L^2([-\pi, \pi]), \mathcal{F}(f * g) = (\mathcal{F}f) \cdot (\mathcal{F}g),$$

where \mathcal{F} denotes the Fourier transform.

For a finite number of data points, *discrete Fourier transform (Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT))* can be used to approximate a function using the Fourier basis $\{\phi_k\}$ mentioned above. In the context of our discussion of DFT, for a slight abuse of notions, let \mathcal{F} also represent the Fourier series. In physical space, the equispaced grid of points is usually scaled first to match the domain of the DFT transform, often chosen as $[-\pi, \pi]$ for 1D data or $[-\pi, \pi] \times [-\pi, \pi]$ for 2D data. DFT then transforms the function values evaluated at the equispaced data points in the physical space to Fourier coefficients in the frequency space by multiplication of the following matrix, called DFT matrix:

$$\Psi := N^{-\frac{1}{2}} \begin{bmatrix} \psi^0 & \psi^0 & \psi^0 & \dots & \psi^0 \\ \psi^0 & \psi & \psi^2 & & \psi^{N-1} \\ \psi^0 & \psi^2 & \psi^4 & & \psi^{2(N-1)} \\ & \vdots & & \ddots & \vdots \\ \psi^0 & \psi^{N-1} & \psi^{2(N-1)} & \dots & \psi^{(N-1)(N-1)} \end{bmatrix},$$

where $\psi := \exp(-\frac{1}{N}2\pi i)$. Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) is an algorithm to efficiently perform the DFT for a finite number of data points, reducing the complexity from $O(N^2)$

to $O(N \log N)$ [Cooley and Tukey, 1965]. Inverse FFT can be done similarly.

In a two-dimensional space, the DFT of the function f is based on the projection on a $2D$ Fourier basis $\{\phi_k := \exp(ikx + i jy) | k, j \in \mathbb{Z}\}$. The convolution property and FFT in a $2D$ space is then similar to that of the $1D$ space [Stein and Shakarchi, 2003, Cooley and Tukey, 1965].

Based on above, kernel density estimation can be computed efficiently using the convolution property of Fourier transform and FFT [Silverman, 1982]. Silverman [1982] further demonstrated the outstanding numerical performance of Fast Fourier Transform-based Kernel Density Estimation (FFTKDE). Specifically, the kernel density estimation for N data points is

$$\hat{f}(x; \Omega) := N^{-1} \sum_{j=1}^N K(x - x_j; \Omega),$$

where K denotes the kernel and Ω denotes the bandwidth matrix. Thus, KDE can be carried out efficiently by

$$\hat{f}(x; \Omega) = N^{-1} \sum_{j=1}^N K(x; \Omega) * \delta(x - x_j),$$

where δ is Dirac delta, which functions as a “spike” and has Fourier transform being a constant function depending only on the chosen normalization constant of the Fourier transform. This allows \hat{f} to be calculated efficiently, since the convolution property of Fourier transform implies that

$$\mathcal{F}(\hat{f})(x; \Omega) = \mathcal{F}(K)(x; \Omega) \cdot \mathcal{F}(\delta)(x - x_j).$$

Then, $\hat{f}(x; \Omega)$ evaluated on a $2D$ equispaced grid can be calculated using IFFT. Therefore, the evaluated density value on the $2D$ equispaced grid can be used to calculate the mutual information estimation, specifically,

$$\widehat{MI}(Y, X_j) = \int_{\text{supp}(Y)} \int_{\text{supp}(X_j)} \hat{f}_{Y, X_j}(y, x_j) \cdot \log \frac{\hat{f}_{Y, X_j}(y, x_j)}{\hat{f}_Y(y) \cdot \hat{f}_{X_j}(x_j)} dx_j dy \quad (\text{A.2})$$

In (A.2), $\hat{f}_Y(y)$, $\hat{f}_{X_j}(x_j)$, and the expectation estimator itself can be numerically computed using the forward Euler method. Notably, employing the FFT for the integration of density functions often fails to deliver satisfactory numerical results, primarily attributed to the inherent periodic characteristics of the method. (A.2) is the equation that we use to calculate the FFTKDE mutual information estimator.

The estimation of mutual information using another nonparametric method, k NN [Faivishvsky and Goldberger, 2008, Kraskov et al., 2004, Victor, 2002, Pál et al., 2010, Lord et al., 2018, Gao et al., 2015], was also discussed in the paper. The estimation of mutual information based on k NN can be viewed through the lens of k NN density estimator. The bivariate k NN density estimator can be given by

$$\hat{f}(x; k) := \frac{k}{N} \cdot (\pi \cdot R^2(x; k))^{-1},$$

where $R(x; k)$ denotes the Euclidean distance from x to its k -nearest-neighbor. In the context of a bivariate density estimator, $\pi \cdot R^2(x; k)$ represents the area of the Euclidean-normed closed ball centered at x that includes the k -nearest-neighbors of x . Following the idea of empirical CDF, the probability that a data point is included in this closed ball is $\frac{k}{N}$; assuming that the density inside the closed ball remains constant, the estimate of such density will be the probability of being included in the closed ball divided by the area of the closed ball, which is the bivariate density estimator described above. The multivariate case with more than two variables can be established in a similar way.

APPENDIX B

Appendix to Manuscript 2

B.1 Proofs

We first establish the following Lemma needed for the proof of Theorem 1.

B.1.1 Proof of Theorem 1

The following lemma is needed in the proof of Theorem 1.

Lemma 19. *Assume that $\forall k = 1, 2, \dots, N$, the convergence conditions (4.8) and (4.9) hold, then we have the following recursive relation:*

$$\alpha_{k+1} \leq \frac{1}{1 + \frac{\delta_k/\delta_{k+1}}{\alpha_k}}. \quad (\text{B.1})$$

Proof. The convergence conditions (4.8) and (4.9) gives that $\forall k = 1, 2, \dots, N - 1$,

$$\alpha_{k+1}\delta_{k+1} \leq \omega_{k+1} \Leftrightarrow \alpha_{k+1} \leq \frac{\omega_{k+1}}{\delta_{k+1}}, \text{ and}$$

$$\frac{\alpha_k}{\delta_k\Gamma_k} \geq \frac{\alpha_{k+1}}{\delta_{k+1}\Gamma_{k+1}} \Leftrightarrow \frac{\alpha_k}{\delta_k} \geq \frac{\alpha_{k+1}}{\delta_{k+1}(1 - \alpha_{k+1})} \Leftrightarrow \alpha_{k+1} \leq \frac{\alpha_k\delta_{k+1}}{\alpha_k\delta_{k+1} + \delta_k}.$$

Following above two inequalities, we have that

$$\alpha_{k+1} \leq \min \left\{ \frac{\omega_{k+1}}{\delta_{k+1}}, \frac{\alpha_k \delta_{k+1}}{\alpha_k \delta_{k+1} + \delta_k} \right\}. \quad (\text{B.2})$$

We observe that in (B.2), $\frac{\omega_{k+1}}{\delta_{k+1}}$ is monotonically decreasing with respect to δ_{k+1} on \mathbb{R}_+ ; while $\frac{\alpha_k \delta_{k+1}}{\alpha_k \delta_{k+1} + \delta_k}$ is monotonically increasing with respect to δ_{k+1} on \mathbb{R}_+ . This suggests:

$$\arg \max_{\delta_{k+1} > 0} \left(\min \left\{ \frac{\omega_{k+1}}{\delta_{k+1}}, \frac{\alpha_k \delta_{k+1}}{\alpha_k \delta_{k+1} + \delta_k} \right\} \right) = \left\{ \frac{\omega_{k+1} + \sqrt{\omega_{k+1}^2 + \frac{4\omega_{k+1}\delta_k}{\alpha_k}}}{2} \right\}. \quad (\text{B.3})$$

That is, the inequality constraints conditions (4.8) and (4.9) for convergence are merely a lower bound on the *vanishing rate* of $\{\alpha_k\}$. Therefore it follows from (4.8) and the (necessary) optimality condition for (B.3) that

$$\alpha_{k+1} \leq \frac{2\omega_{k+1}}{\omega_{k+1} + \sqrt{\omega_{k+1}^2 + \frac{4\omega_{k+1}\delta_k}{\alpha_k}}} \leq \frac{2}{1 + \sqrt{1 + \frac{4\delta_k}{\alpha_k \omega_{k+1}}}} = \frac{2}{1 + \sqrt{1 + \frac{4\delta_k/\delta_{k+1}}{\alpha_k \alpha_{k+1}}}}. \quad (\text{B.4})$$

By simplifying (B.1), we have:

$$\alpha_{k+1} \leq \frac{1}{1 + \frac{\delta_k/\delta_{k+1}}{\alpha_k}}.$$

□

We now proceed with the proof of Theorem 1.

Proof. The complexity upper bound (4.10) under the given conditions can be simplified as:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\sum_{k=1}^N \Gamma_k^{-1} \omega_k (1 - L_\Psi \omega_k) \right]^{-1} \left[\frac{\|x_0 - x^*\|^2}{\delta_1} + \frac{2L_f}{\Gamma_N} (\|x^*\|^2 + M^2) \right] \\ &= \left[\sum_{k=1}^N \Gamma_k^{-1} \omega_k (1 - L_\Psi \omega_k) \right]^{-1} \cdot \frac{\|x_0 - x^*\|^2}{\delta_1} \\ &= \frac{1}{\omega (1 - L_\Psi \omega)} \left(\sum_{k=1}^N \Gamma_k^{-1} \right)^{-1} \cdot \frac{\|x_0 - x^*\|^2}{\omega} \end{aligned}$$

$$= \left(\sum_{k=1}^N \Gamma_k^{-1} \right)^{-1} \cdot \frac{\|x_0 - x^*\|^2}{\omega^2 (1 - L_\Psi \omega)}. \quad (\text{B.5})$$

Observe that $\left(\sum_{k=1}^N \Gamma_k^{-1} \right)^{-1}$ is monotonically decreasing with respect to α_k for all $k = 1, 2, \dots, N$. This property implies that (B.5) is minimized when α_k attains its greatest value for $k = 1, 2, \dots, N$.

Condition $\delta_1 = \omega_k = \omega$ gives that

$$\omega_1 = \delta_1 = \alpha_1 \delta_1.$$

Since the upper bound for α_{k+1} presented in (B.1) is monotonically increasing with respect to α_k , it then follows inductively from the (necessary) optimality condition of (B.2) that

$$\alpha_{k+1} \leq \frac{1}{1 + \frac{\delta_k / \delta_{k+1}}{\alpha_k}} = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{\alpha_{k+1}}{\alpha_k^2}},$$

which simplifies to

$$\alpha_{k+1} \leq \frac{2}{1 + \sqrt{1 + \frac{4}{\alpha_k^2}}}.$$

While $\omega^2 (1 - L_\Psi \omega)$ should be maximized to minimize the value of (B.5), which implies the minimizer for ω is

$$\bar{\omega} = \frac{2}{3L_\Psi}.$$

And $\bar{\lambda}_{k+1} = \frac{\bar{\omega}}{\bar{\alpha}_{k+1}}$ follows directly from the necessary optimality condition for (B.2). It is trivial to check that $(\{\bar{\alpha}_k\}, \{\bar{\delta}_k\}, \bar{\omega})$ is feasible under given constraints (4.8) and (4.9). \square

B.1.2 Proof of Theorem 2

Proof. Consider arbitrary $k = 2, \dots, N$, then $\alpha_k \in (0, 1)$ by definition. In the convergence conditions (4.8) and (4.9), this gives us that

$$\frac{\alpha_{k+1}}{\alpha_k} \leq \frac{2}{\alpha_k + \sqrt{\alpha_k^2 + 4}} \in \left(\frac{\sqrt{5} - 1}{2}, 1 \right).$$

Thus, $\{\alpha_k\}$ is a bounded monotonically decreasing sequence, and $\alpha_2 \leq \frac{2}{1 + \sqrt{1 + \frac{4}{1^2}}} = \frac{\sqrt{5} - 1}{2}$ further implies that $\forall k \geq 2, \alpha_k \in (0, \frac{\sqrt{5} - 1}{2}]$.

For all $k \geq 2, \alpha_k \in (0, 1)$ implies that $1 - \alpha_k \in (0, 1)$. Therefore, $\Gamma_k^{-1} = \frac{1}{(1 - \alpha_2)(1 - \alpha_3) \dots (1 - \alpha_k)}$ is monotonically increasing with respect to k . Thus, $\sum_{k=1}^N \Gamma_k^{-1} = O(N)$, which implies that $\left(\sum_{k=1}^N \Gamma_k^{-1} \right)^{-1} \cdot C_1 = O(1/N)$.

Observe that

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &< \left(\Gamma_N \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{1}{\Gamma_k} \right)^{-1} = \frac{1}{N \cdot \Gamma_N} \cdot \frac{N}{\sum_{k=1}^N \frac{1}{\Gamma_k}} \\ &\leq \frac{1}{N \cdot \Gamma_N} \cdot \left(\prod_{k=1}^N \Gamma_k \right)^{\frac{1}{N}} = \frac{1}{N} \cdot \left(\prod_{k=1}^N \frac{\Gamma_k}{\Gamma_N} \right)^{\frac{1}{N}} \\ &= \frac{1}{N} \cdot \left(\prod_{k=1}^N \frac{\Gamma_N}{\Gamma_k} \right)^{-\frac{1}{N}} = \frac{1}{N} \cdot \left(\prod_{k=2}^N (1 - \alpha_k)^k \right)^{-\frac{1}{N}} \\ &= \frac{1}{N} \cdot \prod_{k=2}^N (1 - \alpha_k)^{-\frac{k}{N}}, \end{aligned} \tag{B.6}$$

where the inequality in (B.6) follows from the harmonic mean-geometric mean inequality.

Consider arbitrary $N \in \mathbb{N}$, now we are to prove that $\forall k = 1, 2, \dots, N, \alpha_k \leq \frac{2}{k+1}$. By definition, $\alpha_1 = 1 \leq 1$. Assume that $\alpha_k \leq \frac{2}{k+1}$, then by the convergence conditions,

$$\alpha_{k+1} \leq \frac{2}{1 + \sqrt{1 + \frac{4}{\alpha_k^2}}}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&\leq \frac{2}{1 + \sqrt{1 + 4/\left(\frac{2}{k+1}\right)^2}} \\
&= \frac{2}{1 + \sqrt{2 + 2k + k^2}} \\
&< \frac{2}{k + 2}.
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, by mathematical induction, $\forall k = 1, 2, \dots, N$, $\alpha_k \leq \frac{2}{k+1}$. Hence, $\sum_{k=1}^N \frac{k}{N} \alpha_k < \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{k}{N} \cdot \frac{2}{k} = \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{2}{N} = 2 < \infty$ as $N \rightarrow \infty$.

Furthermore, we have that $\forall x \in (0, \frac{\sqrt{5}-1}{2}]$, $-\log(1-x) < x$. Combined with the fact that $\forall k \geq 2$, $\alpha_k \in (0, \frac{\sqrt{5}-1}{2}]$, we have that $\forall k \geq 2$, $-\log(1-\alpha_k) < \alpha_k$. Thus,

$$\log\left(\prod_{k=2}^N (1-\alpha_k)^{-\frac{k}{N}}\right) = -\sum_{k=2}^N \frac{k}{N} \log(1-\alpha_k) < \sum_{k=2}^N \frac{k}{N} \alpha_k \leq 2 < \infty.$$

Therefore, $\prod_{k=2}^N (1-\alpha_k)^{-\frac{k}{N}}$ is also upper bounded as $N \rightarrow \infty$, which implies that

$$\left(\sum_{k=1}^N \frac{\Gamma_N}{\Gamma_k}\right)^{-1} \leq \frac{1}{N} \cdot \prod_{k=2}^N (1-\alpha_k)^{-\frac{k}{N}} = O(1/N).$$

Hence, $\left(\sum_{k=1}^N \frac{\Gamma_N}{\Gamma_k}\right)^{-1} \cdot C_2 = O(1/N)$. Therefore, $\left(\sum_{k=1}^N \Gamma_k^{-1}\right)^{-1} \cdot C_1 + \left(\sum_{k=1}^N \frac{\Gamma_N}{\Gamma_k}\right)^{-1} \cdot C_2 = O(1/N)$. \square

B.1.3 Proof of Theorem 3

Proof. $\bar{\alpha}_k \leq \frac{2}{k+1}$ for $k = 1, 2, \dots, N$ has already been proved in the proof of Theorem 2. For the left inequality, note that $\bar{\alpha}_1 = 1 \geq \frac{2}{2+a}$ for $a > 0$; for $k \geq 2$, we are to prove a stronger inequality:

$$\bar{\alpha}_k \geq \frac{2}{\sqrt{(1+a \cdot k^{-b})k} [(1+a \cdot k^{-b})k + 2]}. \quad (\text{B.7})$$

For $k = 2$, condition (4.17) implies that

$$a \cdot 2^{-b} \geq \frac{1}{(1-b)(4-b)} > \frac{1}{4} > \sqrt{5} - 2 \text{ for } 0 < b < 1, \quad (\text{B.8})$$

which suggests $\bar{\alpha}_2 = \frac{2}{1+\sqrt{5}} \geq \frac{2}{\sqrt{(1+a \cdot 2^{-b}) \cdot 2[(1+a \cdot 2^{-b}) \cdot 2+2]}}$ by simple algebra. Assume (B.7) holds for $k = t$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\alpha}_{t+1} &= \frac{2}{1 + \sqrt{1 + \frac{4}{\bar{\alpha}_t^2}}} \\ &\geq \frac{2}{1 + \sqrt{1 + 4/\left(2/\sqrt{(1+a \cdot t^{-b})t[(1+a \cdot t^{-b})t+2]}\right)^2}} \\ &= \frac{2}{1 + \sqrt{1 + (1+a \cdot t^{-b})t[(1+a \cdot t^{-b})t+2]}} \\ &= \frac{2}{(1+a \cdot t^{-b})t+2} \\ &\geq \frac{2}{\sqrt{\left(1+a \cdot (t+1)^{-b}\right)(t+1)\left[\left(1+a \cdot (t+1)^{-b}\right)(t+1)+2\right]}}; \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.9})$$

and (B.9) follows from

$$\begin{aligned} &\left(1+a \cdot (t+1)^{-b}\right)(t+1)\left[\left(1+a \cdot (t+1)^{-b}\right)(t+1)+2\right] - \left[(1+a \cdot t^{-b})t+2\right]^2 \\ &= a^2 \left[(t+1)^{2-2b} - t^{2-2b}\right] + 2at \left[(t+1)^{1-b} - t^{1-b}\right] + 4a \left[(t+1)^{1-b} - t^{1-b}\right] - 1 \\ &\geq 2at \left[(t+1)^{1-b} - t^{1-b}\right] - 1 \\ &= 2at^{2-b} \left[\left(1+\frac{1}{t}\right)^{1-b} - 1\right] - 1 \\ &\geq 2at^{2-b} \left[1 + (1+b)t^{-1} - \frac{1}{2}b(1-b)t^{-2} - 1\right] - 1 \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.10})$$

$$= 2a(1-b)t^{1-b} - ab(1-b)t^{-b} - 1 \geq 0. \quad (\text{B.11})$$

(B.10) follows from binomial approximation inequality; $a > 0$ and $0 < b < 1$ suggest that $2a(1-b)k^{1-b} - ab(1-b)k^{-b} - 1$ is monotonically increasing with respect to k for $k > 0$, condition (4.17) therefore implies that $2a(1-b)k^{1-b} - ab(1-b)k^{-b} - 1 \geq 0$ for all $k \geq 2$, which is (B.11).

And proof of the left inequality for $k \geq 2$ proceeds as the following:

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{\alpha}_k &\geq \frac{2}{\sqrt{(1+a \cdot k^{-b})k[(1+a \cdot k^{-b})k+2]}} \\ &> \frac{2}{\sqrt{(1+a \cdot k^{-b})k[(1+a \cdot k^{-b})k+2]+1}} \\ &= \frac{2}{(1+a \cdot k^{-b})k+1}.\end{aligned}$$

□

B.1.4 Proof of Corollary 4

Proof. Observe that the lower bound of (4.16) is monotonically decreasing with respect to a under given conditions. Constraint (4.17) implies (B.8), which further suggests that

$$a \geq \frac{2^b}{(1-b)(4-b)} > 0 \text{ for } 0 < b < 1;$$

i.e., $\bar{a}_k = \frac{(2/k)^{\bar{b}_k}}{(1-\bar{b}_k)(4-\bar{b}_k)}$. Thus, maximizing the lower bound of (4.16) is equivalent to minimize the convex function $\log \frac{(2/k)^b}{(1-b)(4-b)}$ with respect to b over an open set $(0, 1)$. First-order sufficient optimality condition gives the unique optimizer

$$\bar{b}_k = \frac{2 + 5 \left(\log \frac{2}{k}\right) + \sqrt{9 \left(\log \frac{2}{k}\right)^2 + 4}}{2 \left(\log \frac{2}{k}\right)} \in (0, 1)$$

for $k \geq 8$. Simple algebra shows that $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\bar{a}_k k^{1-\bar{b}_k}}{\log k} = \frac{2}{3}e$. Thus, the lower bound in Theorem 3 becomes $\frac{k+1}{2} - \bar{\alpha}_k^{-1} = O(\log k)$. □

B.2 Further Simulations

B.2.1 Penalized Linear Model

In Figure B.1 and B.2, the red bar represents AG using our proposed hyperparameter settings, blue bar represents proximal gradient, and the purple bar represents AG using the original hyperparameter settings [Ghadimi and Lan, 2015]. It is evident that for penalized linear models, AG using our hyperparameter settings outperforms proximal gradient or AG using the original proposed hyperparameter settings considerably.

Figure B.1: Median for the number of iterations required for the iterative objective value to reach $g^* + e^3$ on SCAD-penalized linear model for AG with our proposed hyperparameter settings, AG with original settings, and proximal gradient over 100 simulation replications, across varying covariates correlation (τ) and q/n values. The error bars represent the 95% CIs from 1000 bootstrap replications, g^* represents the minimum per iterate found by the three methods considered.

Figure B.2: Median for the number of iterations required for iterative objective values to reach $g^* + e^3$ on MCP-penalized linear model for AG with our proposed hyperparameter settings, AG with original settings, and proximal gradient over 100 simulation replications, across varying covariates correlation (τ) and q/n values. The error bars represent the 95% CIs from 1000 bootstrap replications, g^* represents the minimum per iterate found by the three methods considered.

In Figure B.3 and B.4, the red bar represents AG using our proposed hyperparameter settings, blue bar represents proximal gradient, and the purple bar represents coordinate descent. It is evident that for penalized linear models, AG using our hyperparameter settings outperforms coordinate descent significantly in terms of computing time.

Figure B.3: Median for the computing time (in seconds) required for $\|\beta^{(k+1)} - \beta^{(k)}\|_\infty$ to fall below 10^{-4} on SCAD-penalized linear model for AG with our proposed hyperparameter settings, proximal gradient, and coordinate descent over 100 simulation replications, across varying covariates correlation (τ) and q/n values. The error bars represent the 95% CIs from 1000 bootstrap replications, g^* represents the minimum per iterate found by the three methods considered.

Figure B.4: Median for the computing time (in seconds) required for $\|\beta^{(k+1)} - \beta^{(k)}\|_\infty$ to fall below 10^{-4} on MCP-penalized linear model for AG with our proposed hyperparameter settings, proximal gradient, and coordinate descent over 100 simulation replications, across varying covariates correlation (τ) and q/n values. The error bars represent the 95% CIs from 1000 bootstrap replications, g^* represents the minimum per iterate found by the three methods considered.

Table B.1: Signal recovery performance (sample mean and standard error of $\|\beta_{\text{true}} - \hat{\beta}\|_2^2 / \|\beta_{\text{true}}\|_2^2$, Positive/Negative Predictive Values (PPV, NPV) for signal detection, and active set cardinality $|\hat{\mathcal{A}}|$) for **ncvreg** and AG with our proposed hyperparameter settings on SCAD-penalized linear model over 100 simulation replications, across varying values of SNRs and covariates correlations (τ).

$\ \beta_{\text{true}} - \hat{\beta}\ _2^2 / \ \beta_{\text{true}}\ _2^2$	$\tau = 0.1$	0.5	0.9
SNR = 1, AG	0.128(0.021)	0.521(0.114)	2.839(0.497)
SNR = 1, ncvreg	0.131(0.02)	0.485(0.102)	2.929(0.525)
SNR = 3, AG	0.05(0.009)	0.156(0.035)	2.075(0.339)
SNR = 3, ncvreg	0.052(0.009)	0.156(0.028)	2.087(0.357)
SNR = 7, AG	0.022(0.004)	0.085(0.014)	1.278(0.262)
SNR = 7, ncvreg	0.021(0.004)	0.083(0.015)	1.3(0.262)
SNR = 10, AG	0.016(0.003)	0.065(0.011)	1.163(0.207)
SNR = 10, ncvreg	0.015(0.003)	0.063(0.013)	1.167(0.22)
PPV	$\tau = 0.1$	0.5	0.9
SNR = 1, AG	0.747(0.134)	0.622(0.188)	0.488(0.25)
SNR = 1, ncvreg	0.255(0.061)	0.287(0.132)	0.286(0.19)
SNR = 3, AG	0.681(0.162)	0.551(0.206)	0.327(0.234)
SNR = 3, ncvreg	0.282(0.079)	0.307(0.098)	0.275(0.148)
SNR = 7, AG	0.58(0.138)	0.42(0.257)	0.197(0.141)
SNR = 7, ncvreg	0.32(0.065)	0.344(0.152)	0.175(0.101)
SNR = 10, AG	0.528(0.272)	0.437(0.09)	0.211(0.081)
SNR = 10, ncvreg	0.349(0.127)	0.409(0.1)	0.206(0.047)
NPV	$\tau = 0.1$	0.5	0.9
SNR = 1, AG	0.984(0.001)	0.984(0.001)	0.979(0.001)
SNR = 1, ncvreg	0.987(0.001)	0.986(0.001)	0.98(0.001)
SNR = 3, AG	0.989(0.001)	0.988(0.002)	0.98(0.001)
SNR = 3, ncvreg	0.99(0.001)	0.989(0.001)	0.98(0.001)
SNR = 7, AG	0.992(0.001)	0.991(0.001)	0.981(0.001)
SNR = 7, ncvreg	0.993(0.001)	0.991(0.001)	0.981(0.001)
SNR = 10, AG	0.993(0.001)	0.992(0.001)	0.982(0.001)
SNR = 10, ncvreg	0.993(0.001)	0.992(0.001)	0.982(0.001)
$ \hat{\mathcal{A}} $	$\tau = 0.1$	0.5	0.9
SNR = 1, AG	25.82(8.08)	31.58(17.056)	23.11(15.166)
SNR = 1, ncvreg	100.88(25.582)	94.32(41.572)	42.01(20.592)
SNR = 3, AG	42.78(14.003)	55.48(20.653)	42.83(16.308)
SNR = 3, ncvreg	120.17(33.554)	101.75(29.498)	46.72(16.252)
SNR = 7, AG	61.89(21.881)	97.88(36.736)	86.71(26.567)
SNR = 7, ncvreg	115.4(23.845)	107.19(31.445)	89.74(23.1)
SNR = 10, AG	101.21(66.968)	81.17(25.325)	70.8(11.642)
SNR = 10, ncvreg	123.5(52.077)	90.58(40.419)	71.47(10.954)

Table B.2: Signal recovery performance (sample mean and standard error of $\|\beta_{\text{true}} - \hat{\beta}\|_2^2 / \|\beta_{\text{true}}\|_2^2$, Positive/Negative Predictive Values (PPV, NPV), and active set cardinality $|\hat{\mathcal{A}}|$ for signal detection) for `ncvreg` and AG with our proposed hyperparameter settings on MCP-penalized linear model over 100 simulation replications, across varying values of SNRs and covariates correlations (τ).

$\ \beta_{\text{true}} - \hat{\beta}\ _2^2 / \ \beta_{\text{true}}\ _2^2$	$\tau = 0.1$	0.5	0.9
SNR = 1, AG	0.133(0.022)	0.563(0.124)	2.839(0.39)
SNR = 1, <code>ncvreg</code>	0.126(0.019)	0.494(0.112)	2.86(0.427)
SNR = 3, AG	0.049(0.01)	0.169(0.034)	1.997(0.329)
SNR = 3, <code>ncvreg</code>	0.048(0.009)	0.161(0.032)	1.92(0.34)
SNR = 7, AG	0.021(0.004)	0.088(0.016)	1.503(0.329)
SNR = 7, <code>ncvreg</code>	0.02(0.004)	0.086(0.017)	1.416(0.302)
SNR = 10, AG	0.014(0.003)	0.059(0.011)	1.084(0.272)
SNR = 10, <code>ncvreg</code>	0.014(0.003)	0.059(0.013)	1.134(0.248)
PPV	$\tau = 0.1$	0.5	0.9
SNR = 1, AG	0.85(0.081)	0.744(0.161)	0.616(0.208)
SNR = 1, <code>ncvreg</code>	0.435(0.085)	0.407(0.135)	0.387(0.154)
SNR = 3, AG	0.842(0.119)	0.732(0.21)	0.506(0.286)
SNR = 3, <code>ncvreg</code>	0.505(0.112)	0.514(0.121)	0.366(0.18)
SNR = 7, AG	0.761(0.175)	0.646(0.293)	0.505(0.218)
SNR = 7, <code>ncvreg</code>	0.541(0.128)	0.547(0.173)	0.483(0.201)
SNR = 10, AG	0.801(0.099)	0.489(0.134)	0.375(0.225)
SNR = 10, <code>ncvreg</code>	0.559(0.107)	0.476(0.135)	0.377(0.225)
NPV	$\tau = 0.1$	0.5	0.9
SNR = 1, AG	0.983(0.001)	0.982(0.001)	0.979(0.001)
SNR = 1, <code>ncvreg</code>	0.986(0.001)	0.984(0.001)	0.979(0.0)
SNR = 3, AG	0.988(0.001)	0.986(0.001)	0.98(0.001)
SNR = 3, <code>ncvreg</code>	0.989(0.001)	0.987(0.001)	0.98(0.001)
SNR = 7, AG	0.991(0.001)	0.989(0.001)	0.981(0.001)
SNR = 7, <code>ncvreg</code>	0.992(0.001)	0.989(0.001)	0.981(0.001)
SNR = 10, AG	0.992(0.001)	0.99(0.001)	0.982(0.001)
SNR = 10, <code>ncvreg</code>	0.993(0.001)	0.99(0.001)	0.982(0.001)
$ \hat{\mathcal{A}} $	$\tau = 0.1$	0.5	0.9
SNR = 1, AG	19.7(4.584)	20.6(9.45)	12.5(8.163)
SNR = 1, <code>ncvreg</code>	51.61(13.612)	47.32(16.093)	20.25(11.411)
SNR = 3, AG	30.55(8.437)	34.52(16.44)	25.37(14.373)
SNR = 3, <code>ncvreg</code>	60.14(15.873)	48.08(13.783)	31.0(13.981)
SNR = 7, AG	44.45(14.273)	56.95(32.804)	31.96(25.048)
SNR = 7, <code>ncvreg</code>	66.7(20.364)	58.36(24.633)	33.38(25.617)
SNR = 10, AG	43.23(11.26)	64.65(12.923)	46.58(18.186)
SNR = 10, <code>ncvreg</code>	65.36(13.06)	67.16(15.483)	46.07(19.223)

B.2.2 Penalized Logistic Regression

Figure (B.5) and (B.6) suggest that much less iterations are needed for our method to achieve the same amount of descent in comparison of AG with original proposed settings for penalized logistic models.

Figure B.5: Median for the number of iterations required for the iterative objective values to reach $g^* + e^2$ on SCAD-penalized logistic regression for AG with our proposed hyperparameter settings, AG with original settings, and proximal gradient over 100 simulation replications, across varying covariates correlation (τ) and q/n values. The error bars represent the 95% CIs from 1000 bootstrap replications, g^* represents the minimum per iterate found by the three methods considered.

Figure B.6: Median for the number of iterations required for iterative objective values to reach $g^* + e^2$ on MCP-penalized logistic regression for AG with our proposed hyperparameter settings, AG with original settings, and proximal gradient over 100 simulation replications, across varying covariates correlation (τ) and q/n values. The error bars represent the 95% CIs from 1000 bootstrap replications, g^* represents the minimum per iterate found by the three methods considered.

Table B.3: Signal recovery performance (sample mean and standard error of $\|\beta_{\text{true}} - \hat{\beta}\|_2^2 / \|\beta_{\text{true}}\|_2^2$, Positive/Negative Predictive Values (PPV, NPV), and active set cardinality $|\hat{\mathcal{A}}|$ for signal detection) for `ncvreg` and AG with our proposed hyperparameter settings on SCAD-penalized logistic model over 100 simulation replications, across varying values of SNRs and covariates correlations (τ).

$\ \beta_{\text{true}} - \hat{\beta}\ _2^2 / \ \beta_{\text{true}}\ _2^2$	$\tau = 0.1$	0.5	0.9
SNR = 1, AG	0.768(0.047)	0.81(0.041)	0.896(0.04)
SNR = 1, <code>ncvreg</code>	0.803(0.033)	0.84(0.033)	0.903(0.037)
SNR = 3, AG	0.556(0.057)	0.656(0.054)	0.839(0.056)
SNR = 3, <code>ncvreg</code>	0.603(0.053)	0.682(0.055)	0.813(0.053)
SNR = 7, AG	0.377(0.076)	0.521(0.073)	0.779(0.072)
SNR = 7, <code>ncvreg</code>	0.438(0.054)	0.537(0.074)	0.735(0.074)
SNR = 10, AG	0.311(0.077)	0.474(0.073)	0.757(0.079)
SNR = 10, <code>ncvreg</code>	0.377(0.064)	0.481(0.079)	0.712(0.078)
PPV	$\tau = 0.1$	0.5	0.9
SNR = 1, AG	0.8(0.079)	0.779(0.1)	0.697(0.126)
SNR = 1, <code>ncvreg</code>	0.221(0.045)	0.265(0.079)	0.309(0.169)
SNR = 3, AG	0.875(0.054)	0.859(0.065)	0.765(0.096)
SNR = 3, <code>ncvreg</code>	0.244(0.052)	0.273(0.072)	0.273(0.133)
SNR = 7, AG	0.901(0.052)	0.881(0.057)	0.788(0.098)
SNR = 7, <code>ncvreg</code>	0.27(0.04)	0.271(0.079)	0.267(0.136)
SNR = 10, AG	0.915(0.048)	0.899(0.054)	0.789(0.097)
SNR = 10, <code>ncvreg</code>	0.29(0.05)	0.279(0.072)	0.26(0.123)
NPV	$\tau = 0.1$	0.5	0.9
SNR = 1, AG	0.982(0.001)	0.98(0.001)	0.978(0.001)
SNR = 1, <code>ncvreg</code>	0.987(0.002)	0.985(0.002)	0.98(0.001)
SNR = 3, AG	0.985(0.002)	0.982(0.001)	0.979(0.001)
SNR = 3, <code>ncvreg</code>	0.99(0.002)	0.987(0.002)	0.98(0.001)
SNR = 7, AG	0.987(0.002)	0.984(0.001)	0.979(0.001)
SNR = 7, <code>ncvreg</code>	0.992(0.001)	0.988(0.001)	0.98(0.001)
SNR = 10, AG	0.988(0.002)	0.984(0.001)	0.979(0.001)
SNR = 10, <code>ncvreg</code>	0.992(0.001)	0.988(0.001)	0.98(0.001)
$ \hat{\mathcal{A}} $	$\tau = 0.1$	0.5	0.9
SNR = 1, AG	17.07(3.91)	13.4(3.365)	7.62(2.134)
SNR = 1, <code>ncvreg</code>	120.14(28.882)	86.49(24.421)	39.41(19.448)
SNR = 3, AG	23.34(4.203)	16.59(3.459)	8.69(2.082)
SNR = 3, <code>ncvreg</code>	134.85(29.96)	98.48(28.434)	42.47(15.014)
SNR = 7, AG	26.98(4.58)	19.46(3.659)	9.79(2.246)
SNR = 7, <code>ncvreg</code>	130.33(22.255)	105.03(28.123)	48.81(19.059)
SNR = 10, AG	27.95(4.462)	19.57(3.141)	10.24(2.346)
SNR = 10, <code>ncvreg</code>	124.58(23.016)	103.49(27.66)	50.64(21.138)

Table B.4: Signal recovery performance (sample mean and standard error of $\|\beta_{\text{true}} - \hat{\beta}\|_2^2 / \|\beta_{\text{true}}\|_2^2$, Positive/Negative Predictive Values (PPV, NPV), and active set cardinality $|\hat{\mathcal{A}}|$ for signal detection) for `ncvreg` and AG with our proposed hyperparameter settings on MCP-penalized logistic model over 100 simulation replications, across varying values of SNRs and covariates correlations (τ).

$\ \beta_{\text{true}} - \hat{\beta}\ _2^2 / \ \beta_{\text{true}}\ _2^2$	$\tau = 0.1$	0.5	0.9
SNR = 1, AG	0.769(0.044)	0.808(0.041)	0.897(0.043)
SNR = 1, <code>ncvreg</code>	0.795(0.036)	0.829(0.032)	0.903(0.038)
SNR = 3, AG	0.555(0.058)	0.654(0.053)	0.834(0.054)
SNR = 3, <code>ncvreg</code>	0.605(0.049)	0.674(0.054)	0.825(0.057)
SNR = 7, AG	0.383(0.08)	0.521(0.069)	0.779(0.07)
SNR = 7, <code>ncvreg</code>	0.438(0.057)	0.533(0.07)	0.761(0.071)
SNR = 10, AG	0.31(0.079)	0.469(0.073)	0.753(0.076)
SNR = 10, <code>ncvreg</code>	0.381(0.061)	0.48(0.082)	0.737(0.077)
PPV	$\tau = 0.1$	0.5	0.9
SNR = 1, AG	0.879(0.06)	0.859(0.058)	0.779(0.087)
SNR = 1, <code>ncvreg</code>	0.372(0.068)	0.401(0.106)	0.375(0.157)
SNR = 3, AG	0.906(0.05)	0.889(0.05)	0.805(0.086)
SNR = 3, <code>ncvreg</code>	0.43(0.065)	0.445(0.106)	0.395(0.126)
SNR = 7, AG	0.919(0.044)	0.903(0.05)	0.809(0.102)
SNR = 7, <code>ncvreg</code>	0.463(0.063)	0.45(0.104)	0.417(0.145)
SNR = 10, AG	0.918(0.045)	0.911(0.038)	0.804(0.111)
SNR = 10, <code>ncvreg</code>	0.502(0.069)	0.468(0.095)	0.412(0.137)
NPV	$\tau = 0.1$	0.5	0.9
SNR = 1, AG	0.981(0.001)	0.98(0.001)	0.978(0.001)
SNR = 1, <code>ncvreg</code>	0.986(0.002)	0.983(0.001)	0.978(0.001)
SNR = 3, AG	0.985(0.002)	0.982(0.001)	0.979(0.001)
SNR = 3, <code>ncvreg</code>	0.989(0.002)	0.985(0.001)	0.979(0.001)
SNR = 7, AG	0.987(0.002)	0.984(0.001)	0.98(0.001)
SNR = 7, <code>ncvreg</code>	0.991(0.002)	0.986(0.001)	0.98(0.001)
SNR = 10, AG	0.988(0.002)	0.984(0.001)	0.98(0.001)
SNR = 10, <code>ncvreg</code>	0.991(0.001)	0.987(0.001)	0.98(0.001)
$ \hat{\mathcal{A}} $	$\tau = 0.1$	0.5	0.9
SNR = 1, AG	13.86(3.082)	11.42(2.776)	6.72(1.744)
SNR = 1, <code>ncvreg</code>	59.83(14.138)	42.1(12.546)	19.72(8.393)
SNR = 3, AG	21.86(4.313)	15.84(3.036)	8.84(1.938)
SNR = 3, <code>ncvreg</code>	66.57(13.203)	48.28(14.5)	22.81(9.784)
SNR = 7, AG	25.75(4.776)	18.78(3.189)	10.33(2.565)
SNR = 7, <code>ncvreg</code>	69.44(11.876)	52.54(13.638)	24.63(8.741)
SNR = 10, AG	27.53(4.649)	19.55(3.093)	11.06(2.877)
SNR = 10, <code>ncvreg</code>	65.38(10.776)	51.66(12.785)	25.59(9.428)

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